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**BURIAL OF CHILDREN AT THE BRONZE
AGE NECROPOLIS OF OSTOJIĆEVO (1650 -
1550 BCE): A BIOARCHAEOLOGICAL
PERSPECTIVE**

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Burial of children at the Bronze Age Necropolis of Ostojićevo (1650 - 1550 BCE): A bioarchaeological perspective

Abstract

This study aims to shed light on the circumstances that shaped the lives and health of boys and girls during the Middle Bronze Age at the Ostojićevo necropolis (1650–1550 BCE), as well as to explore specific aspects of the funerary ritual given to children. The research examines the interrelationship between health status, sex, and age, as well as the extent to which these biological characteristics were associated with the nature of the burial ritual.

The Ostojićevo necropolis is located in northern Banat, where a total of 285 graves have been discovered and excavated. Of these, 205 graves belong to the Middle Bronze Age horizon, which is the focus of this study. In the overall sample, 142 individuals fall into the subadult age category, and 103 children were buried in large ceramic vessels. This funerary practice is unparalleled in the region, particularly considering the exceptionally high number of individuals interred in ceramic funerary recipients.

A total of 74 subadult skeletal remains attributed to the Middle Bronze Age were sufficiently preserved for paleopathological and metric analyses. These examinations enabled the reconstruction of the health status and growth trajectories of the children. Radiographic methods applied to preserved dentitions provided accurate age estimation, while the analysis of the neonatal line allowed for the identification of potentially stillborn individuals within the sample. Biological sex was determined through the analysis of sex-specific peptides in dental enamel. Reliable determination of age and sex made it possible to further explore differences between boys and girls, as well as among different age categories, in terms of health, growth patterns, and funerary practices.

The paleopathological analysis revealed a high number of skeletal lesions that represent potential indicators of nutritional deficiencies and infectious diseases. In addition, the generally poor health of the population buried at the Ostojićevo necropolis is further reflected in the slower-than-expected growth observed in many children for whom height and weight were estimated.

Social and economic context in the Middle Bronze Age affected the overall health of the population, as evidenced by the high prevalence of nutritional deficiencies (*Cribra orbitalia*, porotic hyperostosis, scurvy, rickets) and indicators of infectious diseases (malaria, tuberculosis) in the analyzed subadult population. These results suggest possible periods of famine, monotonous diet, and close contact with domestic animals, as well as exposure to environmental disease vectors, directly highlighting the impact of unfavorable social and living conditions on the overall health of individuals and the community.

One of the hypotheses of this research, proposing that children's health correlates with biological sex and age, was partially confirmed, but not in the part that concerns sex based differences. No significant differences in health status were found between boys and girls, suggesting that children, regardless of biological sex, had equal access to resources, similar exposure to pathogens, and were subjected to comparable health risks. This indicates that, in the analyzed subadult population, social practices did not differentiate care or living conditions based on sex.

The proposed hypothesis was confirmed in the part that concerns age differences. Younger subadults more frequently exhibited scurvy (68.4% in less than 1-year-olds), porotic hyperostosis (60.9%), malaria and tuberculosis indicators. Trauma affected a total of 8 individuals, mainly cranial sharp-force injuries in children up to 7.5 years. Growth retardation was observed in

71.9% of subadults, with underweight children in 54.5%, and reduced stature in 60%, particularly in 1-5-year-olds. These results suggest that in younger subadults, pathological changes may have contributed more strongly to mortality, indicating that children affected by these conditions were at higher risk of death, reflecting the generally higher vulnerability of younger age groups.

This study also examined differences in funerary practices between boys and girls. The proposed hypothesis posited that boys and girls would exhibit different burial orientations and grave goods. The analysis indicates that the hypothesis is partially supported. Differences in burial orientation are evident, whereas differences in the grave assemblage are not. A sex-specific pattern of orientation, similar to that observed in adult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis, was identified: boys were most frequently oriented north–south (62.5%), while girls were predominantly oriented south–north (61.9%). In contrast, no significant sex-based differences were observed in the number of grave goods or in the choice of burial vessel type.

A correlation was observed between the dimensions of the vessels and the age and stature of the children, suggesting a deliberate intention in the selection of the vessels and indicating that each vessel was most likely intended for a specific child.

With regard to age, the analysis of the neonatal line showed that potentially stillborn children of both sexes were also buried within the perimeter of the necropolis, following the same funerary norms as other children that were interred in funerary vessels. This result implies that the funerary norm intended for children was applied from the very moment of birth and most likely also in cases of stillbirth.

With regard to age, clear differences were observed in the burial practices of children depending on their age category. A marked shift in the funerary ritual occurs around the age of six: up to this age, most children were buried in funerary vessels, while after this point burials predominantly took place outside of them. The oldest child interred in a vessel was 8.5 years old, and beyond this age no further burials in funerary containers were recorded. Such a change in the funerary ritual could be interpreted as an indicator of a potential shift in the child's social status at this stage of life or the assumption of a particular new social role.

Key words: Physical Anthropology, Ostojićevo necropolis, Middle Bronze Age, peptide analysis, neonatal line, bioarchaeology of childhood.

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Sahranjivanje dece na nekropoli bronzanog doba Ostojićevo (1650-1550 g. p. n. e.): Bioarheološka perspektiva

Sažetak

Ova studija ima za cilj da rasvetli niz okolnosti koje su uticale na život i zdravlje dečaka i devojčica tokom srednjeg bronzanog doba na nekropoli Ostojićevo (1650-1550 g. p. n. e.), kao i pojedinosti pogrebnog rituala koji je bio namenjen deci. Istraživana je međusobna povezanost zdravstvenog statusa, pola i uzrasta dece, kao i veza ovih bioloških karakteristika i prirode pogrebnog rituala.

Nekropola Ostojićevo nalazi se u severnom Banatu, a na njoj je otkriveno i istraženo ukupno 285 grobova. Horizontu srednje bronzne koji je u fokusu ovog istraživanja pripada 205 grobova. Ukupno 142 individue u celom uzorku spadaju u starosnu kategoriju subadulta, dok je 103 individue dečijeg uzrasta sahranjeno u keramičkim posudama većih dimenzija. Ovo je pogrebni običaj koji na našim prostorima nema paralele, uzimajući u obzir i brojnost individua koje su sahranjene u keramičkim posudama.

U materijalu je bilo očuvano ukupno 74 subadultna skeleta koji su pripadali periodu srednjeg bronzanog doba na kojima su vršene paleopatološke i metričke analize. Na ovaj način analiziran je zdravstveni status i tempo rasta dece.

Radiografske metode primenjene na očuvanim denticijama omogućile su precizno utvrđivanje starosti kod dece, a analiza neonatalne linije identifikovanje potencijalno mrtvorodne dece u uzorku. Pol dece je određen analizom polno specifičnih peptida zubnog enamela. Pouzdano utvrđivanje pola i starosti kod dece omogućilo je dalje analiziranje razlika između dečaka i devojčica, kao i različitih starosnih kategorija, kada je u pitanju zdravlje, tempo rasta, ali i pogrebni ritual.

Paleopatološka analiza otkrila je veliki broj skeletnih promena koje su potencijalni indikatori nutritivnih deficita i infektivnih oboljenja. Pored toga o opštem lošem zdravlju populacije sahranjene na nekropoli Ostojićevo svedoči i rast sporiji od očekivanog kod velikog broja dece kod kojih je aproksimirana visina i težina.

Društveno-ekonomske prilike u srednjem bronzanom dobu uticale su na opšte zdravstvlje populacije, što potvrđuje visoka prevalenca nutritivnih deficita (*Cribra orbitalia*, porotična hiperostoza, skorbut, rahitis) i indikatora infektivnih oboljenja (malarija, tuberkuloza) u analiziranoj subadultnoj populaciji. Ovi rezultati ukazuju na moguće periode gladi, jednolične ishrane i bliske kontakte sa domaćim životinjama, kao i prenosiocima vektorskih oboljenja iz okoline, što direktno ukazuje na uticaj nepovoljnih društvenih i životnih uslova na opšte zdravlje pojedinca i kolektiva.

Hipoteza kojom se pretpostavlja da je zdravstveni status dece u korelaciji sa biološkim polom i uzrastom, delimično je potvrđena, ali ne u delu koji se tiče polno uslovljenih razlika. Nisu uočene značajne razlike u zdravstvenom statusu između dečaka i devojčica, što ukazuje da su deca, bez obzira na biološki pol, imala jednak pristup resursima, sličnu izloženost patogenima i bila izložena sličnim zdravstvenim rizicima. Rezultati tako otkrivaju da u analiziranoj subadultnoj populaciji nega i resursi nisu distribuirani po osnovu pola dece. Hipoteza je potvrđena u delu koji se tiče razlika među starosnim kategorijama. Kod mlađe dece učestaliji su indikatori skorbuta (68,4% kod individua mlađih od 1 godine), porotične hiperostože (60,9%), kao i indikatori malarije i tuberkuloze. Traumatske povrede su zabeležene kod ukupno 8 individua, kod dece do 7,5 godina starosti. Zastoji u rastu uočeni su kod 71,9% subadulta i to

manja telesna masa kod 54,5%, a manja od očekivane telesna visina kod 60%, sa najvećom učestalošću u uzrastu od 1–5 godina. Ovi rezultati ukazuju da je starost, a ne pol, bila u korelaciji sa većinom patoloških stanja i da su mlađe individue bile ranjiviji deo dečije populacije.

Ovim istraživanjem su takođe razmatrane razlike u pogrebnom ritualu između dečaka i devojčica. Postavljenom hipotezom je pretpostavljeno da dečaci i devojčice imaju različite pogrebne orijentacije i grobne priloge. Analiza pokazuje da je hipoteza delimično potvrđena. Prisutne su razlike pogrebne orijentacije, dok razlike u grobnom asemblažu nisu potvrđene. Kod dečaka i devojčica uočen je polno uslovljen obrazac orijentacije sličan onome kod odraslih individua sa nekropole Ostojićevo: dečaci su najčešće bili orijentisani sever–jug (62,5%), dok su devojčice uglavnom bile orijentisane jug–sever (61,9%). Nasuprot tome, nisu uočene značajne polno uslovljene razlike u broju grobnih priloga niti u odabiru tipa pogrebnog recipijenta. Dečaci i devojčice bili su gotovo podjednako zastupljeni u različitim tipovima posuda.

Uočena je korelacija između dimenzija posuda i starosti i telesne visine kod dece što pokazuje izvesnu intenciju prilikom odabira posude i da je ona najverovatnije bila namenjena sahrani određene dece.

Kada je reč o starosti individua analiza neonatalne linije pokazala je da se i potencijalno mrtvorodena deca oba pola sahranjuju u okvirima nekropole po istom pogrebnom običaju kao i ostala deca u pogrebnim recipijentima. Ovaj rezultat pokazuje da se pogrebna norma namenjena deci primenjuje od samog trenutka dolaska na svet, čak i u slučajevima mrtvorodenosti.

Uočene su izrazite razlike u načinu sahranjivanja dece u zavisnosti od starosne kategorije kojoj pripadaju. Ključna promena u pogrebnom ritualu zapaža se oko šeste godine života: do tog uzrasta većina dece bivala je sahranjivana u pogrebnim recipijentima, dok se nakon tog perioda sahranjivanje odvijalo van njih. Najstarije dete položeno u posudu imalo je 8,5 godina, a nakon tog uzrasta više nema potvrda o korišćenju pogrebnih recipijenata u sahranjivanju. Ovakva promena u pogrebnom ritualu mogla bi se tumačiti kao indikator potencijalne promene društvenog statusa deteta u ovoj životnoj dobi ili preuzimanja određene nove društvene uloge.

Ključne reči: fizička antropologija, nekropola Ostojićevo, paleopatologija, srednje bronzano doba, analiza peptida, neonatalna linija, bioarheologija detinjstva

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1. INTRODUCTION

During the Bronze Age (c. 2500-800 BCE; Harding 2000), increasing sociocultural complexity and the emergence of social stratification reshaped the social roles and status of males and females within the community. Funerary practices indicate that men and women were treated differently in death, reflecting culturally reinforced gender roles and expectations (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020, 2022, 2025). Distinct burial positions and associated grave goods demonstrate the material expression of gender identity (Pape and Ialongo 2024). These material markers not only express gendered roles but also demonstrate the ways in which biological sex could shape an individual's access to resources, social opportunities, and overall standing within the hierarchical structures of Bronze Age communities. During the Bronze Age, clear distinctions between adult males and females have been observed, prompting the question of whether similar patterns of gender differentiation are reflected among children. The gap in knowledge regarding the material expression of gender in subadult individuals during the Bronze Age motivates a closer examination of burial practices, health, and growth in a Bronze age subadult sample from Ostojićevo.

This study examines the lives and deaths of boys and girls within the Middle Bronze Age horizon of the Ostojićevo necropolis (1650–1550 BCE), seeking to illuminate the complex relationship between biological sex, age, health, social roles, and the material remains of both life and death during this period, shaped by profound social transformations.

The Ostojićevo necropolis is located in northern Banat, at the site of Stari Vinogradi (Okruglica–Kera Bara), on the outskirts of the village Ostojićevo, approximately 25 kilometers northwest of the modern city of Kikinda. The necropolis remained in continuous use throughout the Early, Middle, and Late phases of the Bronze Age, spanning the period from 2000 to 1450 BCE (O'Shea et al., 2019). The necropolis was discovered in 1954, when curator of the Kikinda National Museum Milorad Girić recorded certain artifacts that were collected at this location when he documented the presence of artefacts during the survey in 1959 (Girić 1961; Milašinović et al., 2024). The first archaeological excavations were undertaken several decades later, in the 1980s and 1990s and uncovered a total of 285 graves over an excavated area measuring 3,886 square meters (Girić 1995). The predominant burial practice during the Early and Middle Bronze Age was inhumation, whereas in the Late Bronze Age phase, 4 cremation burials were also identified. A total of 77 graves dating to the Early Bronze Age phase of the necropolis. This study focuses on the Late Middle Bronze Age phase of the Ostojićevo necropolis, specifically within the chronological span of 1650 to 1550 BCE, and a total of 205 graves are attributed to this phase. According to the chronological framework proposed by F. Gogâltan (2015), the Middle Bronze Age is broadly subdivided into three phases: MBA I (2000–1900 BCE), MBA II (1900–1700 BCE), and third MBA III phase (1700–1550 BCE), to which the Ostojićevo necropolis is dated. This periodization is derived from absolute dates obtained from archaeological sites in the Romanian part of the Banat, as well as from Marosh culture sites such as Pecica-Șanțul Mare. During this phase, a high mortality rate among subadult individuals is observed (49.28%). Children under the age of seven were typically interred in ceramic containers, known as pithoi. A total of 103 such graves containing subadult individuals buried in ceramic vessels have been documented (Girić 1995; 1996). The high mortality rate of subadult individuals observed at the necropolis, along with the unusual funerary practice of interring children in ceramic containers, raises a number of questions regarding the social position of children within this Bronze Age community, as well as the broader circumstances in which childhood was experienced. These unresolved questions about the lives of the Bronze Age children have provided the central impetus for this research.

Children make up a large portion of every society and as such they represent an important element of social organization (Schwartzman 2005). We often overlook the role of children in prehistory, focusing more on other archaeological topics, such as agriculture, ore smelting, house building, although we learn from ethnological sources that children are often involved in these activities (Haughton 2021). As significant social agents, children inevitably influenced material culture, leaving discernible traces in the archaeological record (Baxter 2008a, 2008b), both within settlement contexts and in funerary settings. In addition to the archaeological context and burial practices, which are an important source of data about children's lives in the past, perhaps the most direct way to gain insights into them is through the analysis of skeletal remains of infants (Mays et al., 2017). The children's skeleton carries a wealth of information about the physical and social aspects of life: birth, growth and development, nutrition, age, as well as social and economic factors that may have exposed infants to trauma and disease. Cultural beliefs determined how the burial of a child would be conducted (Lewis 2018). Through the analysis of skeletal remains of children, bioarchaeology has addressed numerous questions related to the lifestyle of subadults in the past, their roles in the community, and the treatment by adults (Roberts and Manchester 2005). Accordingly, this study employs a dual approach, integrating the analysis of funerary contexts with the bioarchaeological examination of subadult skeletal remains.

The social status of children in past societies may have been shaped by biological factors such as sex, age, and health condition, variables that can be identified, analyzed, and quantified through osteological evidence. A key question arises as to how these biological attributes, alongside children's social roles, are manifested in mortuary practices, and furthermore whether biological sex had a discernible impact on health outcomes, as well as on patterns of growth and physiological development in subadult individuals. Although the archaeological study of children has gained increasing attention in recent decades, it remains a relatively recent area of inquiry, and our knowledge of children's lived experiences and their roles within past communities is still limited. In particular, the influence of biological sex on the social positioning of children has been insufficiently explored. The limited knowledge regarding the lives of girls and boys primarily stems from the fact that biological sex in children cannot be reliably determined using standard anthropological methods. For this reason, it was, until recently, difficult to provide clear answers to key questions concerning childhood in the past. How did biological sex shape access to resources, participation in daily activities, and the provision of care? Did the course of childhood differ for boys and girls across various historical periods? Ultimately, researchers seek to understand how boys and girls were treated in death, and whether variations in funerary practices reveal differential social perceptions and treatment based on biological sex. These questions remain largely unresolved, pointing to a significant gap in our understanding of how childhood was constructed and experienced in the past. In recent years, advances in proteomic analysis have significantly expanded the range of methods available to archaeologists, enabling the accurate determination of biological sex in a growing number of subadult individuals from archaeological contexts. This methodological innovation has begun to resolve longstanding limitations in the study of childhood, allowing for more nuanced investigations into sex-based differences in social roles, and mortuary practices (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020; Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2022; Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2025).

In order to contribute to emerging field of interests and to address existing gaps in our understanding of the lives of boys and girls during the Middle Bronze Age, this study will evaluate burial practices, growth, development, and health status in a sample of subadult individuals from the Ostojicevo necropolis, whose biological sex has been determined through proteomic analysis of sex-specific peptides extracted from dental enamel. The study will assess whether funerary norms associated with adult males and females were applied from the earliest stages of life, and if not, at what age such gender-differentiated practices begin to appear. During the Early and Middle Bronze Age, burial

practices at the Ostojićevo necropolis exhibited a distinct pattern of gender differentiation: male individuals were interred on their left side with a head directed toward the north, while female individuals were placed on their right with a head directed toward the south. This spatial and bodily arrangement reflects a culturally encoded binary system, suggesting that gender identities were materially expressed and ritually reinforced through mortuary customs. Similar burial orientations and funerary patterns are observed in subadult individuals, suggesting that gendered burial practices may extend beyond adults. By determining the biological sex of the children, this study will explore whether the same gender-specific mortuary norms were applied to them, thus providing insights into the social construction of gender roles from an early age.

The examination of biologically sexed roles in past societies offers critical insight into the complex social processes that structured human behavior across various spheres, including daily life, the organization of labor along lines of biological sex, and the distribution of power within social hierarchies (Masclans et al., 2021).

An important question pertains to the temporal boundaries of childhood, when it is understood to begin, and when it is considered to end. Age categories, both historically and in contemporary contexts, have been defined and shaped by societal norms and contextual circumstances and they vary significantly (Kamp 2001). Childhood is typically regarded as commencing at birth and extending until the onset of adolescence (Ilias and Akter 2017). Funerary treatment of children in the Ostojićevo necropolis offers valuable insight into culturally defined milestones on the trajectory toward adulthood, and the stages at which these thresholds were socially acknowledged.

This research will focus on the age of the youngest individuals buried at the Ostojićevo necropolis, investigating the minimum age at which children were included in formal burial practices, as well as the presence of stillborn individuals within the cemetery. This will to some extent address the question of when childhood begins, that is, the point at which the newborn comes to be recognized as an individual and as a social subject categorized as a child.

Children were interred in ceramic containers from the earliest stages of life. However, the cessation of this burial practice, which typically occurred around the age of 7, may indicate a culturally meaningful threshold in the life course. This shift likely reflects a significant stage in the social perception of childhood, marking the point at which children began to be viewed differently within the community. The research will investigate whether the key transitional threshold was determined by the child's biological age or by other physical characteristics, such as body height and weight. To ensure precise age-at-death estimation, the analysis will include the presence and position of the neonatal line, and radiographic imaging interpreted using the London Atlas of Human Tooth Development and Eruption (AlQahtani et al., 2010).

Paleopathological examination of subadult skeletal remains will play a crucial role in reconstructing aspects of the daily lives and health conditions of boys and girls. The analysis of child skeletons from the Ostojićevo necropolis aims to gain insights into the health status of children. Since this is a vulnerable group whose health is directly influenced by lifestyle and the degree of adaptation of the entire community to environmental conditions, this approach might provide data on the living conditions, housing, and diet of this Bronze Age group. The final goal is to establish any potential correlation between the social and health status of individuals, and to examine whether living conditions, the environment, and diet negatively impact the health status of children. It will be determined whether the overall health of child individuals is conditioned by biological sex and age.

1.1 Middle Bronze Age socio-political complexity

The use of the Ostojićevo necropolis and the life of this population took place within a historically dynamic and socially complex period in the broader narrative of human history. The European Bronze Age was a period of increasing socio-political complexity, marked by the emergence of vertical social stratification, the consolidation of chiefdom-like political structures, and significant transformations in kinship and household organization (Harding 2000; Kristiansen and Larsson 2005). An important question is what actually happens to family relationships during the Bronze Age and what role children occupy within this dynamic. Prehistoric family relations and the evolution of family ties and organization was of great interest for researchers since the second half of the 19th century (Backhoffen 1861; McLennan 1865), and this topic continues to engage many researchers to this day (Žegarac et al., 2021; Haughton 2021; Herrero-Corral 2025). During the Bronze Age, radical societal changes disrupted existing structures, and the emergence of social stratification led to significant transformations (Harding 2000; Kristiansen and Larsson 2005). These developments fundamentally altered the structural and relational contexts in which children were embedded and socialized. These transformations are evident in the archaeological record, both within funerary contexts (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020, 2022, 2025; Pape and Ialongo 2024) and in patterns observed at settlement sites (Harding 2000). The cultural-historical evolution of archaeological and ethnic groups during the Bronze Age in Europe is a series of complex processes, and its reconstruction has raised numerous questions that archaeology has yet to answer. During this period of great transformation, various burial practices were employed, including burials with or without mounds, inhumation, and cremation (Schmid 2019). The Carpathian Basin during the Bronze Age is typically described as a period marked by cyclical fluctuations in population concentration and dispersal, spanning approximately from 2700/2500 to 900/750 BC (Visy 2003; Marková and Ilon 2013; Staniuk 2021). During the Middle Bronze Age (c. 2000/1900–c. 1550 BCE; Gogâltan 2015), the emergence of multilayered settlements represents a significant development in the region's settlement patterns. These settlements, characterized by multiple occupational layers, became one of the dominant forms of land utilization, reflecting complex societal organization and evolving patterns of habitation. The widespread establishment of such settlements marks a pivotal phase in the intensification of human activity, signaling a peak in the cultural, economic, and social dynamics within the region during this period (Gogâltan 1999; Staniuk 2021). Between c. 1600 and 1500 BCE, the Pannonian Plain experienced social upheaval, marked by the abandonment of long-established settlements and cemeteries (Molloy et al., 2023).

During the Bronze Age, in addition to the emergence of vertical social stratification, there is a noticeable increase in the complexity of kinship structures and the institutionalization of marriage as a new social framework most frequently evidenced through the funerary record and kinship patterns inferred from communal burial contexts (Lull et al., 2013). Analyses of kinship relationships and the distribution of grave goods in individual burials indicate that during the Bronze Age social status, and potentially associated property, in addition to benign acquired, was also being transmitted hereditarily (Mittnik et al., 2019).

In addition to ongoing social transformations, the eruption of Thera constituted a large-scale environmental disruption with far-reaching consequences in the period, contributing to climatic variability that affected human societies across the Mediterranean and broader European region (Pearson et al., 2018). Regarding the absolute dating of the Thera eruption, it remains a subject of debate and research, and some of the proposed chronologies include Pearson et al. (2018), who dates the eruption to approximately 1620-1530 BCE, as well as LaMoreaux (1995), who proposes a series of eruptions between approximately 1628-1450 BCE. In the time of the eruption of the volcano on the island of Thera (Santorini) (LaMoreaux 1995), significant social changes occurred in the

Mediterranean but also in the Carpathian Basin (Fischl et al., 2013). For around 100 years, beginning about 1620 BCE (Pearson et al., 2018), there were a series of eruptions that took place near the center of the Mediterranean on the island of Stronghlyli. The eruption of Thera induced substantial climatic alterations and a global temperature decline in the Carpathian Basin in the period from c. 1600-1500 BCE (Demény et al., 2019; Molloy et al., 2023), which may have had profound implications for agriculture, settlement dynamics, and economic activities. Those catastrophic events could have exerted a significant influence on the lived experiences of populations in the region of Pannonia during the Middle Bronze Age, particularly during the phase of active use of the necropolis at Ostojíčevo (1650-1550 BCE).

1. 2. Archaeology of childhood

The phenomenon of childhood and its stages, along with the transition into adulthood and the various social roles of boys and girls, represent important issues in ethnological and archaeological studies today. The perception of children and childhood in an archaeological context has changed alongside shifts in contemporary paradigms in social sciences. Childhood, as a sensitive period during which the physical development of an individual occurs and their social role is determined, has not been given much significance in archaeology until recently (Lillehammer 1989; Rebay-Salisbury 2020). It was presumed that people in the past shared our current views on childhood as a phenomenon. Children were considered an economically unproductive group and a minor factor in the formation of material culture (Meskell and Preucel 2008). Anthropological and sociological studies since the 1990s have increasingly recognized children as an essential economic and social factor. During this period, the social status of subadult individuals came to the forefront of interest in archaeology, with one of the significant questions being their health status (Lewis 2006).

The term "childhood" remains imprecise when defining the chronological span of the earliest stages of human development, as it encompasses varying temporal ranges across different historical periods and cultural contexts. Childhood is typically regarded as commencing at birth and extending until the onset of adolescence. In contemporary society, many countries have established a legal age at which an individual ceases to be considered a minor and transitions into adulthood. The age range varies from 13 to 21 years, with 18 years typically serving as the legal threshold in most cases (Illas and Akter 2017). The transition from childhood to adulthood, as observed in ethnological sources, does not occur at a uniform age across cultures, and it is associated with various rites of passage that take place at different stages of lives of children who are about becoming adults. The process of growing up and the chronological framework of childhood are largely conditioned by socio-economic circumstances, since children are most often understood as an age group without authority, whose social and occupational roles depend on the adult members of the community (Barth 1976; Lillehamer 1989). The adult world thus shapes the sphere of childhood, influencing it through the choice of caregivers and educators, the character of occupational conditions, the tasks assigned to children, and the time available to mothers and other community members to care for the youngest, which varies according to the demands of other subsistence and social activities (Lillehamer 1989).

1. 3. Research Aim, Hypotheses and Research Questions

This study aims to examine whether social factors, such as gender and social status, had a significant impact on children's health during the Middle Bronze Age. Analysis of paleopathological alterations including nutritional deficiencies, infectious diseases, and growth patterns will provide insight into how social roles and gender have influenced access to resources, exposure to pathogens and overall health. The analysis of child skeletons from the Ostojićevo necropolis also aims to gain insights into the life conditions of the community. The children are a vulnerable group whose health is directly influenced by lifestyle and the degree of adaptation of the entire community to environmental conditions. Their health status will provide indirect data on the living conditions, and nutritional strategies of this Bronze Age group. The study will examine whether living conditions, the environment, and diet negatively impacted the health status of child individuals.

Hypotheses

1. The first hypothesis considered in this research proposed that funerary practices correlate with sex of children, and that during the Middle Bronze Age at the Ostojićevo necropolis, children were buried in the same, sex-based orientation as adults. Previous studies suggest that during the Bronze Age children were buried similarly to adults and followed the same biologically conditioned funerary practices (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2022). At Ostojićevo, children's skeletons display orientations comparable to adults. This study further examines the extent to which adult sex-based funerary practices were applied to children, with associated grave goods analyzed to assess sex-related burial patterns among subadults.

2. The second hypothesis to be considered is that children's health correlates with gender and individual age. It will be based on the premise that these biological categories were treated differently by the community and had different access to resources and care. Belonging to a specific social or biological category may have influenced differences in health status. In this case, child individuals belonging to different groups would have had different living conditions and access to resources, as well as different occupational activities, which would result in differences in health status. Analyzing the overall health of child individuals represents a good way to gain insight into the potential stratification of society in the Bronze Age, and highlight potential differences in lifestyle between the sexes, even at the earliest stages of life. Immature immunity in younger children (Ygberg and Nilsson 2012) may have contributed to higher mortality and more frequent pathological manifestations, and caution is required when interpreting differences in health status between age categories.

Research Questions

1. This research could answer the question of how social stratification in the Bronze Age affected the health status of children. Possible differences in the social standing of children buried at the Ostojićevo necropolis will be explored through the nature and number of their grave assemblages. It will be then examined whether the greater number of grave goods, which might suggest higher social status in children, necessarily reflects better health and well-being during life.

2. The analysis aimed to determine whether there is a correlation between the biological characteristics of the individuals (sex, age) and the attributes of the vessels used as funerary containers (dimensions, vessel type, and decorative style), burial orientation of the deceased and number of grave goods. In this way, differences in funerary norms reserved for various biological categories were analyzed, revealing the relations of social and biological distinctions within the population buried at Ostojićevo.

3. This study also sought to determine the age at which the practice of burying subadults in funerary vessels began and when it ended. If the funerary vessel was considered a marker of social status, this approach helped identify the transitional point between the social categories of ‘child’ and ‘adult.’

4. Equally important was the question of whether the stillborn and live-born infants were treated differently in mortuary practice, and at what age children begin to be buried within the necropolis. Analyses of neonatal lines (NNL) allowed the identification of stillborn children, because the absence of a neonatal line indicated stillbirth. In this way, these analyses provided a clearer understanding of the biological aspects of the population and offered insight into how these factors influenced burial practices and which categories of individuals were selected for interment in vessels.

5. Is there a high prevalence of certain diseases among individuals, which would indicate some form of unfavorable factors, such as living conditions in the settlement, ecological factors, or lifestyle? Particular attention was given to nutritional deficiencies that may indicate limited access to food, as well as to infectious diseases that could reflect inadequate living conditions or environmental factors beyond the control of this Bronze Age community.

6. Was the volume and size of the vessels used for child burials correlated with the age or the stature of the individuals? This analysis allows for an investigation into the criteria that community members may have followed when selecting a particular ceramic container for a child’s burial, and whether vessels of specific size or volume were chosen for certain age groups, or whether the choice of vessel was circumstantial, with no standardized practice applied in selecting a ceramic container for interment.

1. 4. Ostojićevo necropolis - Excavations and previous research at the Ostojićevo necropolis

At the necropolis in Ostojićevo, dating to the Middle Bronze Age, individuals up to 7 years of age, including neonates, were buried within a necropolis that was also designated for older children and adults. However, their burial practices differed, as children under the 7 years of age were interred in ceramic vessels (Marin et al., 2024).

This specific method of skeletal burials in the ceramic vessels appears in the Middle Bronze Age in the southeastern part of the Pannonian Plain, specifically in the area influenced by the Bronze Age Maros culture (centered in the interfluvium of the Tisza, Zlatica, and Marosh in the northwestern part of Banat, now in the territories of Romania, Serbia, and Hungary) (Girić 1971, 1995).

Figure 1. Map of Serbia showing the location of Ostojićevo site.

At the Early and Middle Bronze Age necropolis of Ostojićevo, located approximately 6 km south of Čoka, a total of 285 burials were excavated. Of these, 77 graves belong to the earlier Horizon I of the Maros culture. Within Horizon II of the Middle Bronze Age, 142 subadult individuals were identified, including 103 children buried in large ceramic pithoi (Girić 1995, 1996).

The Ostojićevo necropolis was discovered in 1954 by Milorad Girić, then a curator at the National Museum in Kikinda. He discovered several artifacts originating from the Ostojićevo necropolis in the Museum in Senta, which was later confirmed during the 1959 site survey at the location of Stari Vinogradi, near Ostojićevo, 25 km northwest from Kikinda (Girić 1961; Milašinović 2008; Milašinović et al., 2024). The site is situated on the left bank of a former branch of the Tisza River, in a site known as Okruglica Bara-Kera. The site is located on the southern slope of the Novi Kneževac loess plateau and is naturally protected from potential flooding by the Tisza and Tamiš rivers (Girić 1995; Milašinović et al., 2024).

The first systematic archaeological research at the site, under the direction of Milorad Girić, curator of the National Museum in Kikinda, was conducted several decades after its initial identification through reconnaissance. Excavations were carried out in multiple campaigns from 1981 to 1991. During these archaeological investigations, a total area of 3,886 square meters was excavated.

The sizable skeletal series of 285 individuals, which was uncovered during these excavations, has provided numerous researchers with the opportunity to study the Ostojićevo necropolis from a bioarchaeological perspective. In recent years, bioarchaeological research has shown an increasing interest in the Bronze Age, with the Ostojićevo necropolis becoming an important subject of study that has given rise to a series of relevant research questions and notable scientific contributions. Early

Bronze Age skeletal material was analysed in the thesis of D. Vučetić (2015), which examined indicators of musculoskeletal stress at Ostojićevo. Health status was explored in the doctoral dissertation of M. Krečković Gavrilović (2022), focusing on skeletal and archaeological markers of health and social status, with particular attention to dental enamel hypoplasia. K. M. Pompeani (2020) carried out a broad bioarchaeological study of the Bronze Age community at Ostojićevo.

Figure 2. Map showing the spatial distribution of graves in the Middle Bronze Age horizon at the Ostojićevo necropolis. The map is based on a map of the Ostojićevo site in documentation from the National Museum of Kikinda.

1. 5. Burials of subadult individuals in vessels

The skeletal burial of children in vessels is neither a funerary custom exclusive to the Bronze Age nor an isolated local phenomenon. This practice is recorded worldwide across various periods. Given the complexity of human societies and the diverse material expressions of beliefs, it is unlikely that a single, universal interpretation can explain this phenomenon across all contexts (Mc George 2011). Archaeologists have proposed multiple interpretations, ranging from the use of vessels as coffins, to symbolic notions of the container as a womb intended to protect or prepare the child for rebirth (Naumov 2007; Nikhai 2019).

The idea of using ceramic vessels as funerary containers emerged almost simultaneously with the appearance of pottery. The earliest evidence comes from the southern Levant, where pithos burials appear during the Ceramic Neolithic (7th–4th millennium BCE). The practice continued through the Chalcolithic, Early, and Middle Bronze Ages, reaching its peak in the Iron Age (1200–587 BCE) (Perrot and Ladiray 1980; Eisenberg et al., 2001; Ilan 1995; Orrelle 2008). By the late 4th and early 3rd millennium BCE, child pithos burials were documented in Mesopotamia, where the custom became widespread during the 2nd millennium BCE, especially in Mesopotamia and Syria (Dornemann 1979). From there, it spread into Anatolia and, during the Early Neolithic (beginning ca. 6500 BCE; Reingruber et al., 2018), to the territory of present-day Greece. Intramural pithos burials occur throughout the Bronze Age both in mainland Greece and the Aegean region (Mc George 2011).

In Southeastern Europe, the earliest burials in vessels were recorded in the Early Neolithic (6th millennium BCE) in the valleys of the Struma and Vardar rivers and in the western Rhodopes (Bacvarov 2008). During the Bronze Age in the Pannonian Basin, isolated cases of child vessel burials are documented, differing in treatment from the dominant funerary customs for subadults. Early Bronze Age necropolises such as Szöreg, Deszk “A,” and Deszk “F” yielded the first finds (Bona 1975). Burials in vessels also appear at necropolises of the Hügelgräber (Tumulus) culture, including Tapé, Tiszafüred, Rákóczifalva–Kastélydomb, and Ménfőcsanak (Trogmayer 1975; Kovács 1975; Motzoi-Chicidenau 2011; Ilon 2014).

At Deszk “A,” 4 of 83 individuals were children interred in large pithoi, differing in shape and dimensions from other ceramics at the site. Their form and decoration resemble urns from the Kelebia necropolis near Subotica, on the Serbian–Hungarian border (Bona 1975). At Szöreg, 3 children were buried in vessels placed in a supine position among 229 graves (Foltinny 1941; Bona 1975; Girić 1981). Although the individuals are cremated and placed in urns, reference also will be made to 126 skeletons excavated at the Kelebia necropolis from the Vatya and Szeremle cultures where 25 urns containing incompletely charred children’s remains were discovered, often covered with smaller vessels. At Tapé, two pithoi containing poorly preserved skull bones of subadults were found (Trogmayer 1975). Tiszafüred had 4 child pithos burials among 365 graves, originating from the Majorshalom site (Kovács 1975). Rákóczifalva–Kastélydomb yielded six (Motzoi-Chicidenau 2011), while at Ménfőcsanak (north-western Hungary), a child (Infans I/II) was found in a pithos within a sacrificial pit (Ilon 2014). The Pir-Cetate necropolis in Romania also yielded a Middle Bronze Age pithos burial of a child (Infans I) (Urák et al., 2015).

A strikingly large number of 103 children at the Ostojićevo necropolis were buried in pithoi belonging to the younger horizon II of the Middle Bronze Age (Girić 1995, 1996; Marin et al., 2024). At Ostojićevo, as in earlier phases of the Bronze Age, skeletal burials followed strict orientation rules: males were positioned north–south, females south–north, usually flexed and facing east, lying on the left or right side depending on sex (Girić 1971, 1995). Sex-based differentiation in funerary treatment did not originate in the Bronze Age; such distinctions are already evident in the Early Neolithic and continue through the Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age (Girić 1995; Sørensen 2013).

The practice of burying children in vessels persists even in historical periods (Buljević and Matić 2024), reappearing sporadically in various regions up to the nineteenth century. Recent ethnographic examples involve newborns and infants in parts of Africa. At the Sudanese site of El Kadada, vessel burial has continued since the Neolithic (Geus 1984). Interpretations vary widely: some associate the practice with a special social status of the child (Gopher and Orrelle 1995; Gopher 1996), others view the vessel as a symbolic womb, human or divine (Von der Osten and Schmidt 1932; Ilan 1995; Hallote

1994, 1995, 2001; Kulemann-Ossen and Novák 2000; Bacvarov 2006; Orrelle 2008; Boeyens et al. 2009; Garroway 2014; Wagner-Durand 2014), or as a symbolic preparation for rebirth (Garroway 2014). A contrasting view suggests that vessel burials were reserved for children who died a violent death, including cases of infanticide or sacrifice (Kahila Bar-Gal and Smith 2001). Among southeastern Bantu communities, stillborn children are considered ritually dangerous; placing them in a vessel and burying them in shade or near water prevents imbalance and potential harm, including drought (Boeyens et al. 2009).

The unusually high number of child vessel burials at Ostojićevo offers a rare opportunity to examine this custom in depth. To better understand the reasons behind this practice at Ostojićevo, it was analyzed whether children buried in vessels differ from those buried outside them. Precise age estimation was conducted to determine up to what age children received this treatment. Potential contributing factors, stillbirth, pathological conditions, trauma, deviation from expected growth patterns, and biological sex, were evaluated as possible markers of “otherness” that could explain differences in funerary treatment. In addition to biological variables, funerary attributes, such as body orientation and grave assemblages, were examined to assess potential variation in mortuary practice among subadult individuals at the necropolis.

2. HEALTH STATUS OF CHILDREN

2. 1. Growth and development of children

Development and physical growth of children is a sensitive indicator of life quality and different environmental factors. Disease, nutrition and social as well as genetic factors all potentially could have a negative impact on human growth tempo (Goodman and Armelagos 1989).

When discussing growth and development in children from the archaeological sample, it is important to note that this was not a healthy population; rather, the majority of individuals represent children affected by various pathological conditions, which consequently became part of the archaeological record (Johnston 1962; Saunders 2008). Conversely, Lovejoy et al. (1990) contend that the majority of infant mortality in earlier populations was due to acute, rather than chronic, illnesses, and thus would have minimal impact on dental or skeletal development.

Both arguments may be equally valid, and both mechanisms contributing to the formation of the sample could be represented even within a single necropolis, or alternatively, only one mechanism might dominate. Therefore, growth and development should not be considered in isolation but interpreted alongside other, primarily paleopathological analyses, which can provide deeper insights into the health status of the child population.

The stature and body weight of children was analysed at the Ostojićevo sample, and subsequently compared with the expected ranges proposed by the World Health Organisation (WHO 2006; 2007). The aim of this comparison is to assess whether the stature and body mass of subadult individuals fall within the expected parameters for their respective age categories.

The reconstruction of growth tempo, stature, and body mass in subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis will enable a comprehensive assessment of the overall health of the population, signaling the potential environmental stressors, pathogenic influences, and nutritional deficiencies. Additionally, potential differences between male and female individuals will be examined to explore possible disparities in health status and access to resources. Comparative analysis across age categories

will further highlight critical developmental periods during childhood and adolescence that may have been particularly affected by growth disruption and physiological stress.

2. 2. Paleopathological conditions on children's skeletons

Paleopathological analysis of children's skeletons offers valuable insight into the health status, living conditions, and nutritional and environmental stresses experienced during early life. By examining indicators of disease, metabolic and non-specific stress, trauma, infectious conditions, and dental pathologies, this study provides an indirect understanding of the broader living environment and daily challenges faced by children in this Bronze Age community.

2. 2. 1. Trauma

During this study, macroscopic analysis was conducted to record the presence of traumatic lesions on both the cranial and postcranial skeleton of subadult individuals. The presence, type and frequency of these lesions, both at the individual and populational level, may provide insight into occupational activities, social circumstances, interpersonal violence, environmental conditions and potential medical procedures and healing interventions or postmortem corpse treatment.

Trauma can be defined in various ways, but it is generally understood as an injury inflicted on living tissue by an external force or mechanism (Lovell 1997). Two types of trauma, blunt and sharp force, traumas are classified based on the different mechanisms of origin (Cohen et al., 2012). Blunt force trauma is caused by blunt impact on the body, with any conceivable blunt object, that includes objects and also parts of the human body such as the head, hands, fists, elbows, knees, legs and feet. Sharp force trauma is caused by objects with cutting edges or pointed ends (Eze and Ojifinni 2022).

The identification of trauma in subadult skeletal remains is more challenging than in adult skeletons. One of the primary reasons lies in the different biological response to injury, due to the ongoing skeletal development, trauma in children often presents with distinct morphological features or may completely remodel during the healing process, leaving minimal or no visible traces on the bone (Lewis 2009). Currey and Butler (1975) demonstrated that pediatric bones often exhibit so-called greenstick fractures, which heal rapidly and without periosteal reaction. These fractures are characterized by a bowed appearance of the metaphysis, which may remain visible and, during skeletal analysis, can be misinterpreted as cases of rickets or scurvy, since it is difficult to distinguish them visually.

In the past, children were exposed to trauma through play, labor, warfare, and abuse, and while the causes of injury have changed over time, the biological response of developing bone to trauma remains the same (Lewis 2009). Injuries in children often have more severe consequences and are more likely to be fatal due to the immature and softer structure of their bones, which provides less protection to vital organs compared to adults. Additionally, anatomical characteristics of children, such as a proportionally larger cranium and shorter limbs, increase the risk of serious injuries from falls and impacts (Wilber and Thompson, 1998; Lewis 2009).

Despite the difficulties that are linked to analysing and recording trauma in infant skeletal remains in the archaeological records it is very important for reconstruction of occupational activities, interpersonal relations in the past communities, accidents, birth difficulties (birth trauma), subsistence and trauma treatment. Since children participated in various daily and occupational activities, evidence of trauma in their remains provides insight into apprenticeship age, parental care, domestic life, and possible abuse (Lewis 2009).

2. 2. 2. Metabolic disease and associated skeletal changes

2. 2. 2. 1. *Cribra orbitalia*

Cribra orbitalia is a nonspecific skeletal indicator of pathological conditions, which, due to its frequent occurrence in archaeological contexts, is of exceptional importance for reconstructing the lifestyles of past communities. The cause of the development of *Cribra orbitalia* in previous research has primarily been sought in nutritional stress, leading to the conclusion that individuals with this pathology have, in some way, limited access to food. Various factors can influence diet quality, with socio-economic factors and culturally conditioned restrictions in food choices cited as the main ones (Walker et al., 2009).

There is a general consensus that anemia is the primary factor affecting the development of porotic lesions, with various causes of anemia (Rivera and Mirazon Lahr 2017). Acquired anemia is caused by parasitic infestations and dietary deficiencies, while congenital anemias are genetically conditioned, such as thalassemia (both major and minor) and sickle cell anemia (Scianò et al., 2021). Beyond anemia, any pathological condition resulting in tissue hypoxia, whether due to a reduced erythrocyte count or impaired oxygen-carrying capacity, induces compensatory hyperplasia of the bone marrow. This hematopoietic response increases trabecular activity in the orbital region, ultimately manifesting as *Cribra orbitalia*. These pathological conditions include various nutrition deficiencies (Brickley and Ives 2008), malaria (Smith-Guzman 2015), and infections including pulmonary infections that reduce oxygen uptake by obstructing the respiratory pathways with pulmonary exudates (O'Donnell et al., 2020).

The term *Cribra orbitalia* (CO) is used to describe the porosity of the orbital roof, similar to how the term porotic hyperostosis (PH) is used to describe the porosity of the outer surface of the parietal and occipital bones. The appearance and position of lesions on the orbital roof, as well as their correlation with other pathological changes in the skeleton, vary significantly (Roberts 2016). The terms *Cribra orbitalia* and porotic hyperostosis are often used interpretatively in paleopathology and bioarchaeology, although many aspects of their presence have not been thoroughly clarified. An unresolved question is whether *Cribra orbitalia* and porotic hyperostosis are different manifestations of the same pathological process (Stuart-Macadam 1989).

Radiographic and computed tomography analyses, alongside detailed examination of the supraorbital arch and subcortical bone structures, may yield important insights into the etiology of *Cribra orbitalia*, as it is shown by previous research. The study conducted in 2015 at the Department of Archaeology and Anthropology at the University of Bristol (Galea et al.) was to demonstrate the advantages of micro-computed tomography (μ CT) in analyzing the microstructure of human orbital bones from an archaeological context that show pathological changes in the form of lesions on the upper orbital roof. These changes are characteristic of the pathological condition known as *Cribra orbitalia* (Galea et al., 2015). Metabolic disorders such as anemia and scurvy (Ortner 2003, Walker et al., 2009), malaria (Smith-Guzman 2015), and infectious diseases including respiratory infections (O'Donnell et al., 2020) are considered the main causes of these skeletal alterations. Radiography has confirmed in many cases the thickening of trabecular bone in the presence of *Cribra orbitalia*, with the assumption that this was a response to iron deficiency (Stuart-Macadam 1987). Histological studies have deepened knowledge of this pathological process, providing insight into the internal structures of cortical and trabecular bone. Paleopathological studies have revealed differences between *Cribra* caused by anemia and external cortical damage whose causes may be various other diseases (Schultz 2001).

Archaeological evidence indicates that the mortality risks associated with *Cribra orbitalia* are highest in childhood (McFadden and Oxenham 2020), but recent findings suggest that the impact of *Cribra orbitalia* may extend into older adulthood (Anderson et al., 2025).

2. 2. 2. 2. Porotic hyperostosis

Porotic hyperostosis is a pathological condition characterized by porous expansion of the cranial vault, most often parietal bones, caused by marrow hypertrophy due to increased demand for red blood cell production (erythropoiesis), resulting in thinning of the outer cortical bone and spongy-like appearance of the cortical bone (Stuart-Macadam 1992).

This condition can have different etiologies, but most frequently is associated with anemia (iron-deficiency anemia, megaloblastic anemia, anemia caused by parasite infestation) (Stuart-Macadam 1992; Walker et al., 2009), but also with infections and nutritional deficits like scurvy and rickets (Schultz 2001; Steckel et al., 2005).

2. 2. 2. 3. Scurvy

In order to reconstruct different aspects of children's lives during the Middle Bronze Age in Ostojićevo, skeletal manifestations of certain nutritional deficiencies were analyzed in this sample. One of the nutritional deficits that leaves a characteristic pattern of osseous lesions on the human skeleton is scurvy (Ortner et al., 2001; Brickley and Ives 2008).

Scurvy develops in individuals whose diets are of generally low quality or limited diversity, particularly when dominated by foodstuffs deficient in essential vitamins and minerals. The cluster of specific symptoms referred to as scurvy is most notably correlated with ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) deficiency (Snoddy et al., 2017; Snoddy et al., 2018; World health organization 1999). Vitamin C (L-ascorbic) is essential for proper functioning of human organism. Ascorbic acid acts as an antioxidant and plays a critical role in multiple biological functions, including regulation of immune responses, catecholamine and carnitine biosynthesis, enhancement of non-hem iron absorption and hydroxylation reactions essential for collagen synthesis (Padayatty and Levine 2016; Alberts et al., 2025). While most mammals are capable of synthesizing vitamin C endogenously from glucose, primates, including humans, lack the hepatic enzyme gulonolactone oxidase, which is essential for the biosynthesis of ascorbic acid, and therefore they rely on dietary intake of this important vitamin (Drouin, Godin and Page 2011; Du, Cullen and Buettner, 2012; Snoddy et al., 2018). Vitamin C is present in a broad range of dietary sources, predominantly in fresh fruits (notably citrus) and vegetables, with lower concentrations in milk, meat, and fish, and is absent in cereals (Brickley and Ives, 2008). Given that vitamin C is prone to thermal degradation, deficiencies are more prevalent in populations reliant on extensively cooked diets compared to those consuming minimally processed or raw foods (Ortner 2003). The recommended daily intake of vitamin C is 30 mg/day, although some studies indicate that a daily consumption of 6.5–10 mg is sufficient to prevent scurvy. Nonetheless, the optimal requirement is modulated by multiple factors, including individual physiological differences, levels of physical activity, pregnancy, and lactation (Brickley and Ives 2008).

The most frequently observed traces of scurvy on both osteological material and in the clinical practice is the consequence of inadequate collagen synthesis. Ascorbic acid is essential for hydroxylation of lysine and proline and stabilisation of collagens triple helix. If the collagen integrity is compromised, connective tissue damage and also insufficient or absent osteoid formation occurs (Boskey and Robey 2013; Snoddy et al., 2018). A key pathological consequence of this deficiency and soft tissue destruction is the impairment of blood vessel epithelium, leading to hemorrhage within tissues and the

appearance of petechiae and purpura on the skin surface, gingival bleeding and subperiosteal hemathoma (Francescone and Levitt 2005; Popovich et al., 2009).

This metabolic disorder can occur in both adults and children. Developing subadult skeletons are more severely affected with a hypovitaminosis C than those of adult individuals because of increased requirement for the ascorbic acid due to rapid growth (Fain 2005; Snoddy et al., 2018). Notably, in neonates and children, tissue damage predominantly involves the periosteum, while in adults, hemorrhaging is more frequent in soft tissues, leading to the degradation of muscle and vital organs (Buckley et al., 2014). Musculoskeletal lesions are commonly observed in presumptive scurvy subadult cases in clinical practice. Most of the lesions relevant for diagnosis are localized on the metaphyseal region and are linked to disturbances in endochondral ossification (Riepe et al., 2001). The majority of skeletal lesions utilized in the paleopathological diagnosis of scurvy are considered to arise primarily from the secondary effects of chronic hemorrhage, particularly within the subperiosteal spaces of long bones, the cranial vault, orbits, facial bones, alveolar process of the mandible and maxilla, and at enthesal attachment sites (Brickley and Ives, 2008; Ortner, 2003; Snoddy et al., 2018). The majority of skeletal markers usually employed by the bioarchaeologists for differential diagnosis of scurvy were initially proposed by Ortner and colleagues (Ortner et al., 1999; 2001), whereby they identified macroscopic skeletal lesions that may result from hemorrhagic events associated with scurvy, particularly microvascular bleeding induced by mechanical stress during masticatory muscle activity (Snoddy et al., 2018). Pathologically, scurvy is manifested by cranial porosity, which may occur with or without periosteal reaction, accompanied by new bone deposition on the frontal, parietal, occipital, zygomatic, temporal, and greater wings of sphenoid bones, as well as on the maxilla and mandible. In the postcranial skeleton, vitamin C deficiency is characterized by pathological lesions predominantly affecting the ribs, scapula, metaphyseal regions of long bones, and the iliac portions of the pelvis (Ortner 2001, 2003; Brickley and Ives 2008). The precise etiology of endocranial lesions remains indeterminate, and several questions regarding their origin persist. Nonspecific meningeal reactions, while observed in cases of scurvy, may also arise from other pathological processes, including tuberculosis-associated meningitis, osseous neoplasms, subdural hematomas, and anemia (Lewis, 2018).

Scurvy is generally rare in neonates and is uncommon before the fifth month of life, as the fetus typically receives sufficient vitamin C through the placenta, allowing the accumulation of reserves for the early postnatal period. However, if the mother experienced scurvy or had inadequate dietary intake during pregnancy, this vitamin C deficiency may be transmitted to the infant (Brickley and Ives, 2008). Nutritional deficiencies observed in neonates and very young individuals not only reflect dietary practices and subsistence strategies within past communities but also provide insight into maternal health, access to resources, and potential prenatal or perinatal nutrient deficits.

2. 2. 2. 4. Rickets

From a public health standpoint, rickets continues to represent a significant burden in developing countries, with the highest prevalence observed in children between 3 and 18 months of age (Pettifor 2004; Alzahrani, 2022). Rickets is a metabolic disorder resulting from a deficiency of vitamin D (25-hydroxyvitamin D), defined as a serum concentration below 30 nmol/L (Holick, 2012). Vitamin D plays a crucial role in the metabolic regulation of calcium and phosphorus within the body (DeLuca, 1986), and the deficiency of this vitamin causes disruption of normal bone mineralisation during the period of growth and development, leading to skeletal deformities in the youngest individuals in the population (Pettifor 2004). Skeletal manifestations commonly include bowed long bones, flaring of the

metaphyses of long bones, deformities of the rib cage (Mays et al., 2006), cranial porosity, thinning of the superior orbital roof, carious lesions, and deformities of the mandible (Brickley et al., 2020).

The pathogenesis of this condition may be influenced by various ecological and cultural factors shaping the living conditions of a community. Among the most significant are insufficient dietary intake of vitamin D, exclusive breastfeeding by mothers who are themselves vitamin D deficient, and, importantly, limited exposure to sunlight (Pettifor 2004).

2. 2. 3. Infectious diseases

Anthropological studies of human remains from ancient necropolises offer a glimpse into a world before antibiotics, a world where even a tiniest wound could seal one's faith. Infections nowadays considered trivial once carried a sting of mortality, revealing the fragile balance between life and death in the past. Prior to the clinical use of the first antibiotic, salvarsan (salvation arsenic), in 1910 (Hutchings et al., 2019), numerous infectious diseases imposed considerable distress and hardship to those affected. In just over a century, the continuous development of increasingly effective antibiotics has enabled the treatment of diverse infectious diseases and contributed to an increase in average life expectancy by 23 years (Hutchings et al., 2019). Analysis of aDNA confirmed the presence of numerous pathogens during the Bronze Age. *Yersinia pestis*, hepatitis B virus, human parvovirus B19, and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex were all detected across Eurasia and Europe (Müller et al., 2014; Mühlemann et al., 2018; Spyrou et al., 2018; 2019), which is summarized in the work of Martín-Vela and Jiménez-Jáimez (2025), illustrating the relatively easy transmission of these pathogens within the populations. It is widely inferred that, as observed in contemporary developing regions, infectious diseases constituted a major source of morbidity and mortality among young individuals in past populations. Regrettably for paleopathological research, many infectious diseases that still cause significant child mortality in modern populations, like those in the past, do not leave observable markers on subadult skeletal remains. Because the majority of infectious diseases predominantly impact soft tissues rather than skeletal structures, relatively few can be identified in the osteological record. Notable exceptions include osteomyelitis, tuberculosis, syphilis, leprosy, and poliomyelitis (Waldron 2020). Some recent pathological research suggests potential correlation between certain skeletal lesions and malaria (Smith-Guzman 2015). Mastoiditis, as a complication of middle ear infection, can also potentially leave pathological changes on the mastoid process. Also it is observed more frequently in children than in adult individuals (Flohr and Schultz 2009). In this study within the framework of the paleopathological analysis, the research protocol encompassed also the assessment of tuberculosis, mastoiditis and malaria, because they possess the potential to produce detectable skeletal alterations. In order to identify potential infectious diseases, observation and documentation focused also on pathological alteration that may have both metabolic and infectious etiologies. These included endocranial lesions (*Serpens endocrania symmetrica* and other non-specific meningeal reactions), osteoperiostitis of long bones, *Cribra orbitalia* and porotic hyperostosis (Abegg et al., 2020).

2. 2. 3. 1. Malaria

Throughout the past malaria caused by *Plasmodium Falciparum* and other parasites from the same genus was one of the deadliest diseases in the past populations (World Health Organisation 2024). *Plasmodium* species parasites are transmitted by female mosquitos from the genus *Anopheles* (Gozalo et al., 2024).

Malaria does not cause any pathognomonic lesions on the skeleton (Gowland and Western 2012; Nerlich 2016), but disease has been studied on the skeletal remains with a focus on porose lesions that are commonly associated with anemia (Smith-Guzman 2015a, 2015b) which is a major consequence of

malaria as a result of a distraction of red blood cells in active phase of a diseases course (Gansane et al., 2013).

Recent pathological research has suggested a potential association between certain skeletal lesions and malaria infection. Smith-Guzman (2015) established, using two modern Ugandan populations and individuals with documented clinical histories, a statistically significant correlation between malaria infection and five skeletal indicators: *Cribra orbitalia*, spinal porosity, *Cribra humeri*, *Cribra femora*, and periostitis. The sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis will also be analyzed using this approach.

2. 2. 3. 2. Mastoiditis

When antibiotics became widely available, mastoiditis became a very rare pathological condition in the population. However, it still occurs in developing regions of the world, where populations have a limited access to medical care. Accordingly, it may be inferred that mastoiditis was once a prevalent and life-threatening infection, and as such, its traces merit careful consideration within paleopathological analyses (Flohr and Schultz 2009). Before the onset of antibiotics, more children have been hospitalized because of acute mastoiditis than for any other disease or condition (Bluestone 1998). Middle ear infection remains highly prevalent in contemporary populations. Acute otitis media (AOM) is primarily induced by bacterial pathogens entering via the Eustachian tube, leading to subsequent infection of the tympanic cavity. In addition to bacteria, viral and fungal agents may also contribute to the pathogenesis of AOM. In acute otitis media (AOM), inflammation is not confined solely to the mucosa of the tympanic cavity. From the onset of the disease, it also involves the mucosa of adjacent pneumatized spaces, such as the mastoid process. (Boenninghaus and Lenarz 2005; Flohr and Schultz 2009). Mastoiditis is characterized by osteoclastic resorption in pneumatized cells, and also new bone formation that fills former pneumatized cells in chronic cases leading to visible osteolytic lesion and periosteal reaction on the surface of mastoide processus (Fleischer 1979; Flohr and Schultz 2009).

Mastoiditis occurs more frequently in children than in adults, due to anatomical differences in the structures of the ear. In early childhood the Eustachian tube is shorter, wider and more horizontally oriented. These anatomical characteristics of the auditory system facilitates the spread of pathogens from nasopharynx to the middle ear cavity (Bluestone and Klein 2007). If left untreated, which was the most likely outcome in the pre-antibiotic era, mastoiditis can progress beyond the temporal bone, leading to septicemia. In severe cases systemic infection can lead to septic shock and death, especially in children whose immune systems are still developing (Lillie 1925; Olge and Laurel 1986).

Given that children are particularly susceptible to the development of mastoiditis and its associated complications, it is crucial to document the occurrence of such pathological changes in the subadult sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Future research aimed at identifying cases of mastoiditis not detectable through macroscopic observation could focus on the analysis of samples with well-preserved temporal bones using radiographic techniques or computed tomography (CT), in order to diagnose changes in the mastoid process that are not visible macroscopically (Purchase et al., 2019).

2. 2. 3. 3. Tuberculosis

Tuberculosis remains a major global health concern even in the era of antibiotics. According to the World Health Organisation, more than 10 million people develop tuberculosis every year, resulting in over 1 million deaths, making it the second leading cause of death from an infectious disease worldwide (WHO 2023). Historical resources and reflections from the times before humanity had

access to efficient treatment for tuberculosis, testify to the relentless nature of this disease and the human lives it claimed (Dubos and Dubos 1952; Daniel 2006).

Human tuberculosis is caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, also known as Koch's bacillus (Ryan and Ray 2004). *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is responsible for the so-called human form of the disease, while *Mycobacterium bovis* is also a member of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (Brites and Gagneux 2015). The disease is transmitted from host to host via airborne droplets, with the primary site of infection typically localized in the lungs. The progression of the disease may result in the hematogenous spread of infection to distant organs, including the skeletal system. The proportion of individuals who develop skeletal lesions during the course of tuberculosis is relatively small, accounting for only about 2–5% of all cases (Pigrau-Serrallach and Rodríguez-Pardo 2013; Waldron 2020). The other variant, *Mycobacterium bovis*, causes the anthroponotic form of tuberculosis and, in addition to humans and cattle, can infect a variety of other animals, including dogs, cats, pigs, deer, and primates (O'Reilly and Daborn 1995). In addition to airborne transmission from the cattle to a human host, infection can also occur through the consumption of milk from infected animals (Michael et al., 2010). Increased interaction between humans and animals in the time of intensification of agriculture and domestication of animals during the Neolithics facilitated the transmission of the pathogens (Pearce-Duvel 2006). These changes in occupational strategies may also contribute to the more rapid transmission of pathogens that cause tuberculosis both in domestic animals and in humans (Pearce-Duvel 2006; Michael et al., 2010).

Regardless of the species of *Mycobacterium* that causes the disease, skeletal lesions may form during the course of a disease, most commonly on vertebrae (Waldron 2020). Tuberculosis in most cases results in destruction of skeletal tissue, and in some cases can manifest as erosive lesions on vertebrae of the lower back (lower thoracic and upper lumbar vertebrae). Restorative and proliferative changes of pleural surface of ribs may be also indicative of tuberculosis, although when examined independently, they are not diagnostically conclusive (Steckel et al., 2005).

2. 2. 3. 4. *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES)

Serpens endocrania symmetrica (SES) is a specific pathological condition that can be recorded on the endocranial surface of parietal and frontal bones. In most cases it is characterized by bilaterally symmetrical and serpentine or maze-like vascular impressions. These impressions are snake-like (*serpens*) patterns that follow the distribution of meningeal blood vessels on both sides of sagittal sulcus (Schultz 2001; Hershkovitz et al., 2002). Macroscopic features of SES include a remodeled and porous surface of endocranium. These lesions are usually well defined, shallow, and bilaterally expressed, which helps to differentiate them from other endocranial pathological changes like localized periosteal reaction, trauma, and other infectious processes that lack symmetry (Schultz 2001).

SES in paleopathological studies had been interpreted as skeletal manifestation of chronic meningitis or leptomeningitis. The etiology of these endocranial changes in some cases has been linked with systemic infectious diseases, most notably tuberculosis, syphilis, and other chronic bacterial infections (Herschovitz and Rothschild 1997; Shultz 2001; Hershkovitz et al., 2002).

The condition therefore provides a valuable osteological indicator of intracranial infection in paleopathological contexts, offering insights into patterns of systemic and chronic disease in past populations (Schultz, 2001; Hershkovitz et al., 2002).

In the study of Abbeg et al., (2020), on specimen of subadult individuals from Western Switzerland Neolithics, authors identified and recorded endocranial lesions consistent with SES, but also noted in the same individuals the presence of porotic alterations and abnormal bone formations indicative of nutrition deficits such is scurvy.

As this study will examine both the potential presence of lesions consistent with tuberculosis, bone alteration consistent with scurvy and occurrences of *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES), it is of particular importance to investigate any correlation and co-occurrence of these pathological changes within individual specimens.

2. 2. 4. Dental pathologies

2. 2. 4. 1. Enamel hypoplasia and caries

In children due to occasionally very poor skeletal preservation, teeth that are more durable and less prone to taphonomic changes are a valuable source of information about the life and habits of children and populations in general (Stránská et al., 2015). Dental pathologies such as enamel hypoplasia and dental caries are valuable bioarchaeological indicators, reflecting physiological stress, dietary composition, oral hygiene and overall health status of past populations (Hillson 1996; Hillson 2008). Dental caries is an important indicator of dietary patterns and trends in prehistoric communities (Lee et al., 2019). The identification and analysis of these dental structural defects on skeletal remains thus provide significant insight into the biological and environmental conditions that shaped both individual and population health within an archaeological context. Given its significance as an indicator of physiological stress during growth, diet, and overall stress, enamel hypoplasia and dental caries on the dentitions of subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis will be analyzed both macroscopically and microscopically, with recording of observed defects.

3. FUNERARY PRACTICE AT THE OSTOJÍČEVO NECROPOLIS: SEX AND AGE RELATED DIFFERENCES

During the Bronze Age in Europe, significant social transformations took place, with social relations becoming increasingly complex at multiple levels. Foremost among these developments were the stratification of society and the differentiation of gender roles, both of which are also reflected in mortuary practices. The issue of binary gender role division during the Bronze Age has long attracted scholarly attention. Robb and Harris (2017), for instance, observe that from the Bronze Age onward, the division of gender roles became more rigid compared to preceding periods and more closely correlated with biological sex, with these tendencies persisting into later times. The binary nature of Bronze Age mortuary practices is particularly evident in the sex-differentiated orientation of the deceased and in the presence of characteristically male and female grave goods (Pape and Ialongo 2024). While researchers have thus extensively addressed the question of gender roles among adults in the Bronze Age, only recently has attention turned to whether children in these societies were likewise ascribed male or female roles, and from what age, whether from birth or only at a later stage of life (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020; Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2022; Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2025).

An important research question concerns whether the subadult individuals buried at the Ostojićevo necropolis follow the sex-based binary burial pattern that has been documented among the adult population. The archaeological context in which the child individuals were found will serve to reconstruct their post-mortem treatment by the community. The status of children and the way they were integrated into the family and broader community during the Bronze Age, as well as the age at which they were fully integrated into the community, represent an important element for understanding the social conditions of this period. At the Ostojićevo necropolis, the funerary practices for a significant group of subadults differ from those of adult individuals, most notably through the practice of burial

within ceramic vessels. At a certain age, individuals are no longer buried in pithoi, which could help establish the age at which a change in the social role of subadults occurs.

The analysis of differences in funerary treatment between boys and girls aims to explore whether specific elements of the burial ritual were influenced by the sex of the child. Particular attention will be given to potential differences in the burial orientation of boys and girls, the number of grave goods, as well as to determining whether children of both sexes were interred in ceramic vessels.

An important question is whether sex was a decisive factor in the orientation of child individuals, as is the case with adult individuals, where a determined sex shows that female individuals were predominantly buried with a head oriented toward south, while male individuals were buried with a head oriented toward north (Pompeani 2020). Also the burial orientations East-West (E–W), and West-East (W–E) were recorded (Girić 1995; Field documentation-National Museum Kikinda). Four exceptions have been noted where the burial receptacle was placed vertically. In the case of grave Ostojićevo 271, the recipient was positioned with the opening facing down (Field documentation-National Museum Kikinda). The orientation of skeletons of subadult individuals is a particularly significant issue, and this study addressed how children were oriented and whether there are statistically significant differences in orientation between boys and girls buried in the Ostojićevo necropolis. It was also examined whether the orientations align with those observed in adult individuals.

Regarding grave goods, they are scarce at the Ostojićevo necropolis, but any potential differences in the number of grave goods across different sex and age categories will be investigated.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Given that this study encompassed both anthropological analyses of skeletal material and investigations of grave assemblages, including the spatial orientation of interred individuals, the Materials and Methods chapter has been organized into two distinct sections: the first addresses the analysis of skeletal material, while the second focuses on the study of grave assemblages.

4. 1. Materials and Methods: Analysis of Skeletal Material

4. 1. 1. Skeletal series of Ostojićevo necropolis

During the Middle Bronze Age at the Ostojićevo necropolis, a total of 142 subadult individuals were buried, of which 103 children under the age of seven were interred in ceramic burial receptacles (Girić 1995). The skeletal remains of Middle Bronze Age children preserved and available for analysis in the National Museum of Kikinda, and included in this study, comprise a total of 74 subadult individuals.

Skeletal preservation in the subadult sample varied notably between individuals. Some burials retained only isolated teeth, cranial bones and postcranial elements, while some individuals retained more complete skeletal elements. Overall, the sample exhibited poor preservation of cortical bone surface due to taphonomic processes, soil acidity and other factors, as well as limited preservation of dental enamel surfaces, which in many cases considerably hindered or completely precluded further paleopathological analysis.

Peptide-based biological sex determination was conducted in 49 subadult individuals. Biological sex was determined for 49 subadult individuals, revealing 24 males (48.98%) and 25 females (51.02%) in the analyzed sample, indicating that both sexes were nearly equally represented within the sample.

Table 1. Peptide-based biological sex determination in the Ostojicevo necropolis subadult sample.

Biological sex	Male (n)	(%)	Female (n)	(%)	Total (n, %)
Number of individuals (n)	24	48.98%	25	51.02%	49 (100.0%)

Individuals under 1 year of age (including perinatal and neonates) accounted for 42 individuals (56.75%) of the sample, indicating a high proportion of very young children. The 1–10 years category included 20 individuals (27.09%). Individuals older than 10 years totaled 12 (16.28%), representing older children and adolescents. This categorization highlights the predominance of infants in the necropolis, while older subadults and adults are comparatively less represented.

Table 2. Age distribution of subadults whose individual age could be determined.

Age category	Number of individuals (n)	(%)
Less than 1 year	42	56.75 %
1-10 years	20	27.09%
More than 10 years	12	16.28%
Total (n, %)	74	100.00%

4. 1. 2. Age Estimation

Chronological and biological age are two distinctive measures by which we can define individual age. On osteological material we are able to observe in most cases biological age, by which we mean the degree of development of certain bony and dental structures. Chronological age or the exact number of days that passed from birth to the moment of death of an individual is usually unknown in the archaeological context (Baldsen et al., 2022). Age estimation in subadult individuals within archaeological contexts is most reliably and frequently based on the assessment of dental development stages. To estimate dental age, which correlates strongly with the chronological age of children, the formation and eruption of the dentition are most commonly subjected to analysis (Stull et al., 2021).

4. 1. 2. 1. Radiographic methods of age estimation (London Atlas and Kvaal's method)

Radiographic methods for age estimation are non-destructive, which is particularly important when working with archaeological samples. Dental age in this study was evaluated through radiographic analysis of preserved dentitions and maxillary and mandibular structures. Imaging was performed using orthopantomograms (OPG) and retroalveolar radiographs, allowing precise visualization of dental development stages for age estimation. The obtained radiographic images were subsequently analyzed, and dental age was assessed based on the London Atlas of Human Tooth Development and Eruption, which is the most recent atlas of tooth development, and it was used as the primary reference.

Figure 3. Retroalveolar radiograph of the mandible with dentition. Grave Ostojićevo 285 (Photo: Bojan Petrović and Marija Marin).

The study data was obtained from 176 individual's skeletal remains from the collection of the National History Museum, London and the Royal College of Surgeons of England, and dental radiographs of 528 living individuals (Weems and Seen 2013).

This approach divides dental development into 31 stages (a total of 31 diagrams depicting the median dental development), covering both primary and permanent dentition, and evaluates crown formation, root development, and eruption status. Each stage is associated with a defined chronological age range, enabling standardized age estimation from 30th week in utero to 15.5 years for all teeth and 16,5 to 23.5 years for third molar only (AlQahtani et al., 2010). In this study the London Atlas was used for precise age assessment for the individuals up to 23.5 years old.

Figure 4. Orthopantomogram of the mandible with dentition. Grave Ostojićevo 275 (Photo: Bojan Petrović and Marija Marin).

Kvaal's method for age estimation is a non-invasive method based on regression analysis of dental pulp size. Panoramic radiographs are used to measure the width and height of the dental pulp. The varying relationships observed in different teeth can be correlated with chronological age, allowing for age estimation (Mu-Jia Li et al., 2019). Since dental pulp regression is a continuous process it can be used as a parameter of age estimation from 18, and even beyond the 25 years (Mittal et al., 2016).

4. 1. 2. 2. Neonatal line analysis method

In this research it has been investigated whether stillborn children were interred within the necropolis perimeter and subjected to similar burial practice as their live counterparts. This question is mostly prompted by the considerable number of newborns and generally infants under one year of age.

To address this question, a histological analysis was conducted on a sample of 15 individuals under the age of one year buried inside the perimeter of the necropolis with the aim of assessing the presence or absence of neonatal line (NNL). Based on the enamel formed after the neonatal line, the time of death after the child's birth can be more accurately determined, as well as whether the individual was stillborn, based on the presence or absence of the neonatal line (Eli et al., 1989).

Neonatal line forming during the stressful event of birth and is positioned between prenatally and postnatally formed enamel. During the tooth formation in utero the enamel layers are formed in a circadian rhythm of constant speed which is interrupted during the birth process by metabolic stress which becomes visible as the incremental line, a distinct histological landmark, also known as neonatal line (NNL) (Nergis et al., 2014). In this study the presence or absence of neonatal line, an indicator of live birth was examined, in order to assess whether stillborn infants were also interred alongside other children at the Ostojićevo necropolis. Subsequently the perinatal status of individuals

lacking an observable neonatal line was evaluated through the measurement of formed enamel thickness.

For microscopic analysis, dental thin sections were prepared using a Dremel rotary tool fitted with a diamond cutting disc. Each section was subsequently polished with progressively finer abrasive papers (up to 1600 grit) to obtain a smooth and reflective surface. Following sectioning and polishing, the specimens were stabilized in dental base plate wax to ensure optimal positioning during imaging. Teeth were prepared to visualize the neonatal line (NLL) within the enamel. All samples were thoroughly cleaned to remove debris and surface contaminants prior to analysis. No chemical etching was applied in order to preserve the natural microstructural appearance of the enamel and maintain the integrity of the neonatal line (Antoine et al., 2009).

Microscopic imaging was conducted using a Biomager Metallurgical Microscope B500 under reflected light at 50 x magnification. The condenser and fine focus were carefully adjusted to maximize the contrast between incremental enamel growth lines. Digital micrographs were captured using the microscope's integrated camera system, and all images were subsequently analyzed to identify the presence or absence of the neonatal line, as well as to document its morphological characteristics for correlation with perinatal developmental indicators.

In this study the mean secretion rate of enamel was calculated at 3.74 μm per day, the value consistent with a lower range of previously documented enamel secretion rates (Mahoney 2012; Dean et al., 2020).

The initiation age of in utero mineralization for incisors (98 days) and canines (118 days) was incorporated into the cumulative duration of enamel formation. This approach enabled the identification of potential preterm individuals through the assessment of maximal enamel thickness (Dean et al., 2020).

4. 1. 2. 3. Age Estimation in Subadult Individuals Using Postcranial Indicators

For individuals in the sample with no preserved dentition, the estimation of age relied entirely on postcranial skeletal indicators. Measurements of the diaphyseal lengths of long bones were taken and systematically compared to established growth standards for subadult individuals, as proposed by Maresh (1970), allowing for the approximation of chronological age. A standard anthropological method for age assessment based on epiphyseal fusion was also applied (Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994). For fetal and perinatal individuals, where skeletal development is particularly rapid and variable, age assessment was based on the reference data provided by Fazekas and Kósa (1978), which consider measurements of long bones in combination with other skeletal elements to improve the accuracy of age determination.

4. 1. 3. Sex estimation

Determining the sex of individuals is key information that should be obtained from the archaeological record and it is crucial for the subsequent analysis. Biological sex plays a significant role in human experience, affecting both biological and social aspects of life. Sex and gender shape various cultural behaviors including kinship, economic roles and identity (Sear and Mace 2008; Gomila Grau 2012; Buonasera et al., 2020).

In addition to the sex of adult individuals, the biological sex of subadults is also crucial, as it allows for the analysis of biological and cultural aspects of children's lives and provides insight into dynamic

interplay between gender and biological sex in younger age categories (Perry 2005; Lewis 2022). Sex determination in human remains from archaeological context is most commonly based on morphological analysis of osteological features, with the *os coxae* providing the most reliable features (Buikstra and Ubelacker 1994). Because sexual dimorphism is weakly expressed in infants and prepubertal subadults in general, skeletal morphology is not a reliable indicator of biological sex in children (Schutkowski 1993). Accurate determination of sex in children provides a foundation for further analysis of sex-related funerary practices (Rebay-Salisbury, K., et al. 2022). Currently in addition to morphometric osteological methods, there are two more approaches available for determining sex in adults and children. Genomic analyses provide reliable results, but material preservation does not allow for analyses in all cases, which gives a certain advantage to proteomic analyses, including the analysis of sex-specific peptides (Buonasera et al., 2020). For this reason, proteomic methods were employed in the present study to determine the sex of subadult individuals.

4. 1. 3. 1. Proteomic Analysis of a Middle Bronze Age Ostojićevo sample

The sex of subadult individuals with preserved dentitions from the Ostojićevo necropolis was determined through the analysis of sex-specific peptides, conducted at the Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of Vienna, in collaboration with the Austrian Archaeological Institute, Austrian Academy of Sciences.

The biological sex has been determined from a sample of 49 subadult individuals from the Bronze Age horizon of the Ostojićevo necropolis, using proteomic analysis of sex-specific enamel peptides through nano-liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (nano LC-MS/MS). Peptides identified as AMELY and AMELX can be found in male samples, while only the AMELX peptide can be isolated in female samples. The protocol developed by Stewart et al. (2017) will be utilized. Recent studies based on peptide analysis have enabled the determination of sex in children from various archaeological deposits spanning from the Neolithic to the 19th century (Froment et al., 2020; Rebay-Salisbury, K., et al. 2020, 2022).

The samples were prepared following a slightly modified protocol (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020) based on that described by Stewart et al. (2017). Tooth enamel was mechanically abraded with sandpaper, followed by treatment with hydrogen peroxide and rinsing with MS-grade water. The abraded tooth surface was immersed in 120µL of 5% hydrochloric acid in a 0.5-mL Eppendorf tube and etched for 2 minutes; the first solution was discarded. A second etch was performed and processed further. C18 ZipTip (Pierce® C18 Tips, Thermo Scientific) was conditioned with 10 µL of 100% acetonitrile and 10 µL of 0.1% formic acid. The etch solution was bound to the resin by pipetting 20 times, followed by 6 washes with 10 µL of 0.1% formic acid. Peptides were eluted with two 10 µL aliquots of 60% acetonitrile, 0.1% formic acid, dried in a vacuum concentrator, and reconstituted in 2 µL of 30% formic acid with synthetic standard peptides. For quality control, 10 µL of eluent A was added (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020). Analysis was conducted using a Dionex Ultimate 3000 nanoLC system coupled with a Q Exactive Classic Orbitrap mass spectrometer and nanospray ion source. LC and MS conditions followed a recently published method (Stewart et al., 2017). Briefly, peptides were trapped on a Thermo Scientific Acclaim™ PepMap™ 100 C18 column (20 mm, 100µm ID, 5µm particle size), then separated on a 500 mm C18 column (75µm ID, 3µm particle size). A nonlinear gradient from 1 to 45% eluent B (20% MS-grade water, 79.9% MS-grade ACN, 0.1% FA) was applied over 55 minutes, followed by a 5-minute increase to 99% B and 19-minute equilibration at 1% B. The mass spectrometer scanned from 300 to 1400 m/z at a resolution of 70,000 and 17,500 for MS1 and MS2, respectively, with AGC targets of 3e6 and 2e4. MS2 was performed with an isolation width of 1.8 m/z and HCD fragmentation at 30% normalized collision energy for charge states 2-4. Data interpretation was performed using Max Quant (version 1.6.3.4) with the Andromeda search engine (Cox and Mann,

2008). Positive protein identification required at least one unique peptide. Peptide mass tolerance was set to 50 ppm for the first search and 25 ppm for the main search, with a fragment mass tolerance of 20 ppm. The false discovery rate (FDR) was set to 0.01 for both peptides and proteins. ‘Match between runs’ was enabled with time windows of 15 and 1 minute for alignment and matching, respectively. The human Uniprot database (version 03/2018) was used for identification, with methionine oxidation and N-terminal acetylation as variable modifications. Additionally, MS1 filtering was performed using Skyline (version 20.1.0.79) to monitor peptide candidates from the Max Quant search, focusing on mass deviation and isotope distribution. Raw data was analyzed for peptides with Max Quant scores ≥ 40 , and isotope distribution was evaluated with a Skyline IDOTP score >0.95 and a mass tolerance of 5 ppm (Rebay-Salisbury et al., 2020).

In all analyzed samples from the Ostojićevo necropolis, proteomic analysis successfully identified sex-specific peptides, allowing for the reliable determination of biological sex, for a total of 49 subadult individuals (Table 7.). Knowing the sex of the individuals allowed for deeper insight into the differences between boys and girls in terms of health, growth, and development, as well as variations in funerary practices between male and female subadults at the Ostojićevo necropolis during the Middle Bronze Age.

4. 1. 4. Methods for assessing subadult growth patterns

4. 1. 4. 1. Comparison of dental age and postcranial longitudinal growth in subadults

For the purpose of this study dental age and postcranial longitudinal growth were compared in order to estimate whether the growth of long bones follows the expected patterns, and dental age has been taken as closest to chronological age for each subadult individual. The primary aim of this comparative analysis was to evaluate whether dental age, widely regarded as the most reliable proxy for chronological age in subadult individuals (Saunders et al., 1993; Cardoso, 2007), accurately reflects the degree of postcranial skeletal growth. Individuals were therefore categorized according to the relationship between their dental development and long bone growth, distinguishing those whose postcranial growth was consistent with, delayed relative to, or accelerated compared with the expected trajectory based on dental age. This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of growth variability within the population and provides insight into potential influences of environmental, nutritional, or pathological factors on skeletal development

Age estimation was performed using radiographic analysis, with dental development evaluated according to the London Atlas of Tooth Development and Eruption (AlQahtani et al., 2010). For older subadults, particularly those over 18 years of age with fully erupted permanent dentition, the method proposed by Kvaal et al. (1995) was applied to estimate age based on pulp/tooth ratios. These dental age estimates were then systematically compared to postcranial age estimates derived from diaphyseal length measurements of long bones, following the growth standards established by Maresch (1970). For fetal and perinatal individuals, age assessment relied on the reference data provided by Fazekas and Kósa (1978), which incorporate measurements of long bones alongside other skeletal elements.

4. 1. 4. 2. Subadult growth patterns

Stature and body weight of children from the Ostojićevo sample were analysed and subsequently compared with the expected age-specific reference ranges proposed by the World Health Organization (WHO 2006; 2007). The aim of this analysis was to evaluate whether the observed values fall within the expected anthropometric parameters for the corresponding age categories. Based on their deviation

from the WHO reference standards for height and weight, individuals were classified into three categories: below, within, or above the expected WHO range.

Stature of children

Stature of the subadult sample was estimated using the regression equations of Murray et al. (2024), which predict stature from diaphyseal lengths of the humerus, radius, ulna, femur, and tibia, that was calculated based on the formulas for the body height of subadult individuals provided by Maresh (Maresh 1955, 1970).

Formulas for the body height of subadult individuals (Murray et al., 2024):

$$\text{Humerus: stature} = 4.95 \times \text{humerus length} + 23.26 \text{ (SEE} = 3.73 \text{ cm)}$$

$$\text{Radius: stature} = 6.57 \times \text{radius length} + 23.27 \text{ (SEE} = 4.19 \text{ cm)}$$

$$\text{Ulna: stature} = 6.27 \times \text{ulna length} + 18.64 \text{ (SEE} = 4.45 \text{ cm)}$$

$$\text{Femur: stature} = 3.27 \times \text{femur length} + 31.20 \text{ (SEE} = 4.02 \text{ cm)}$$

$$\text{Tibia: stature} = 3.97 \times \text{tibia length} + 31.07 \text{ (SEE} = 4.08 \text{ cm)}$$

Body weight

Body weight in children was estimated using a regression derived equation based on humeral, tibial and femoral midshaft diameter (anteroposterior diameter of the long bone midshaft) and age of individual. Measurements were taken at the narrowest portion of the femoral diaphysis using digital calipers (± 0.1 mm). Anteroposterior diameter of the femoral midshaft of individuals was then entered into a regression formula to calculate and estimate body weight of subadult individuals aged from 3 to 12 years (Visser 1998).

Regression equation derived from Maresh (1961) for estimation of body mass (kg) using humeral, tibial and femoral midshaft anteroposterior diameter (Visser 1998):

$$\text{Humerus: Body weight} = \text{Hap} 0.02 + \text{Hap} 4.269 - 38.2229 \pm 0.5$$

$$\text{Tibia: Body weight} = \text{Tap} 0.02 + \text{Tap} 2.728 - 18.7439 \pm 0.3$$

$$\text{Femur: Body weight} = \text{Fap} 0.02 + \text{Fap} 2.46 - 19.3059 \pm 0.4$$

4. 1. 5. Methods for recording pathological alterations on skeletal remains

Paleopathological analysis of the children's skeletons will be undertaken to identify markers of disease and episodes of nutritional or physiological stress. Traumatic lesions on both the cranial and postcranial skeleton were systematically recorded and described (Cohen et al., 2012). Non-specific stress indicators, including porotic hyperostosis and *Cribra orbitalia*, were analysed, documented, and quantified (Steckel et al., 2005). The potential presence of metabolic diseases such as scurvy (Ortner and Erickson 1997; Ortner et al., 1999, 2001; Geber and Murphy 2012) and rickets (Buikstra 2019) were assessed, alongside evidence of non-specific infections on the skeleton (osteoperiostitis) (Steckel

et al., 2005). Markers of infectious diseases such as tuberculosis (Rogers and Waldron 1989; Buikstra and Ubelaker 1994; Steckel et al., 2005) and malaria (Smith-Guzman 2015), as well as signs of localized infections such as mastoiditis, which is frequently observed in subadult skeletal samples (Flohr and Schultz 2009) were recorded.

Additionally, dental pathologies, including enamel hypoplasia and dental caries, were examined and documented (Halcrow et al., 2013; Hillson 2014).

4. 1. 5. 1. Methods for trauma recording

During this study all skeletal elements (cranial and postcranial) are systematically examined. Macroscopic examination of the bone was performed by using a magnifying glass and strong lighting to identify the possible presence of a lesion. The anatomical position of the lesion on the skeleton was precisely determined, along with its dimensions. The characterization of trauma involves two categories: blunt force trauma and sharp force trauma. The morphological description of each lesion, in addition to shape and dimensions, included measurements of depth and assessment of the incision profile (U- or V-shaped) (Cohen et al., 2012).

4. 1. 5. 2. Methods for recording *Cribra orbitalia*

Although *Cribra orbitalia* represents a nonspecific indicator of physiological stress, its recording on Ostojićevo subadult sample was crucial for reconstructing patterns of childhood anemia, nutritional deficiencies, potential parasitic infections like malaria, and developmental stress.

Active *Cribra orbitalia* is observed almost exclusively in subadults, while in adult individuals, it is in the process of healing (Stuart-Macadam 1985). During the analysis of the sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis, the presence of *Cribra orbitalia* was recorded, noting whether the lesions were active or healed (Stuart-Macadam 1991).

The quantification system for *Cribra orbitalia* was developed by Stuart-Macadam in 1991. In this research quantification protocol developed by Steckel et al., 2005 was applied, in which at least one orbital roof must be preserved, and lesions are classified as: no orbits present for observation, 1: absent with at least one orbital roof preserved, 2: a cluster of mostly fine foramina coverings small area ($\leq 1 \text{ cm}^2$), and 3: a substantial area ($>1 \text{ cm}^2$) covered by small and/or larger foramina with tendency to cluster.

Skeletal material was examined macroscopically and under magnification using a hand lens.

For the purposes of the statistical analyses conducted in this study, despite recording severity grades and distinguishing between active and healed manifestations of *Cribra orbitalia*, the variable was operationalised in a binary form, considering only its presence or absence on a sample with at least one preserved orbital roof.

4. 1. 5. 3. Methods of recording porotic hyperostosis

For the purposes of this study, the presence or absence of porotic hyperostosis was recorded macroscopically in individuals with at least one preserved parietal bone. The condition was quantified using the following scoring system: 0; no parietals present for observation, 1; absent with at least one observable parietal, 2; presence of slight pitting or severe parietal porosity, and 3; gross parietal lesion with excessive expansion and exposed diploë (Steckel et al., 2005).

Skeletal remains were examined both macroscopically and under low-power magnification using a hand lens.

For the purposes of the statistical analyses in this study, although severity grades of porotic hyperostosis were recorded, the variable was operationalised in a binary format, considering only its presence or absence on a sample with at least one preserved parietal bone.

4. 1. 5. 4. Methods of recording skeletal indicators of scurvy

In the course of paleopathological assessment of the skeletal material of subadult individuals from the Necropolis at Ostojićevo, macroscopic lesions indicative of vitamin C deficiency were comprehensively documented, allowing for the identification of individuals in whom the skeletal evidence strongly supports a diagnosis of hypovitaminosis C.

Skeletal material was examined for pathological changes associated with vitamin C deficiency (scurvy) following established bioarchaeological protocols (Ortner et al., 1999; 2001; Ortner, 2001, 2003; Brickley and Ives, 2008; Snoddy et al., 2018). Cranial lesions were assessed for porosity on the frontal, parietal, occipital, zygomatic, temporal, and greater wings of the sphenoid bones, as well as on the maxilla and mandible. Postcranial analyses focused on lesions affecting the ribs, scapula, metaphyseal regions of long bones, and iliac portions of the pelvis. Endocranial lesions were also recorded, though their etiology remains indeterminate, as nonspecific meningeal reactions may result from other pathological processes such as tuberculosis-associated meningitis, osseous neoplasms, subdural hematomas, or anemia (Lewis, 2018).

The skeletal remains were analyzed via macroscopic assessment and low-power magnification with a hand lens. In individuals exhibiting more than three skeletal alterations consistent with scurvy, the condition was operationalized as a binary variable, recorded as either present or absent in the sample with preserved skeletal elements that were analysed.

This approach allows for the identification of potential individual cases of nutritional deficiency in specific children, as well as the analysis of broader dietary strategies within this Bronze Age community.

4. 1. 5. 5. Methods of recording skeletal indicators of rickets

During the macroscopic analysis of the skeletal material from the Ostojićevo necropolis, the presence of these bone changes potentially indicative of vitamin D deficiency and consistent with rickets was systematically recorded as proposed in studies by multiple authors in previous decades (Mays et al., 2006, Brickley et al., 2020, Pitre et al., 2023); Porotic Hyperostosis, *Cribra orbitalia*, carious lesions, deformed mandibular ramus, bowing of arm and leg long bones, porosity of concave side of bowed long bones, flaring, swelling or cupping of growth plates, fraying or irregularity of growth plates, porosity or roughening of growth plates, angulation of femoral neck, flattening of femoral head, thickening of long bone diaphyses, costochondral flaring, swelling or cupping, deformity of costochondral rib end margin, rib angle deformities, anterior protrusion of sternal body and iliac deformities.

The analysis was conducted through direct examination of the osteological material using a magnifying lens, following the criteria for diagnosing rickets in subadults as proposed by Brickley et al. (2020). Observed changes were quantified based on their presence or absence.

4. 1. 5. 6. Methods for recording malaria

In order to isolate subadult individuals that potentially could suffer from malaria the skeletal material was analysed and macroscopic pathological changes indicative of Malaria were comprehensively documented, allowing for the identification of individuals in whom the changes support a potential diagnosis of malaria. For the differential diagnosis that was conducted based on the following formula proposed by Smith-Guzman (2015) was used: $C_i = 1$ if $\{(CO \text{ or } HC \text{ or } FC = 1) \text{ and } (SP \text{ or } P = 1)\}$; else $C_i = 0$. The formula includes indicators proposed by the author, where CO stands for *Cribra orbitalia*, HC for *Cribra humera*, FC for *Cribra femora*, SP for Spinal Porosity and P for Periostitis. This algorithm was tested on 450 individuals (skeletal remains of known individuals from anatomical or forensic samples (Galloway and Louisiana State University)), of which 142 had observable lesions. It yielded two false positives (3%) and 23 false negatives (30%) (Smith-Guzman 2015).

Periostitis was recorded following the guidelines of the Global History of Health Project codebook (Steckel et al., 2005), which provides criteria for identifying periosteal reactions on long bones. In the present study, periostitis was operationalized as a binary variable for statistical analysis, scored as present if any periosteal reaction meeting the criteria was observed on accessible skeletal elements, or absent if no such lesions were detected. *Cribra humeri* and *Cribra femora* were assessed macroscopically on the epiphyses and diaphyses of the humeri and femora following the approach described by Steckel et al. (2005). As with periostitis, these lesions were recorded as binary variables (present/absent) for each individual. In this study, periostitis, *Cribra humeri*, and *Cribra femora* were examined specifically as potential skeletal indicators of malaria exposure.

Procedures for the recording of spinal porosity and *Cribra orbitalia* are detailed in separate sections of the Materials and Methods.

4. 1. 5. 7. Methods for recording mastoiditis

For the purposes of this study, preserved temporal bones in subadults at the Ostojićevo necropolis were analyzed through macroscopic observation as well as the use of a magnifying lens, with particular attention to the mastoid processes. The presence or absence of lytic lesions and periosteal reactions on the bone surfaces was recorded. The methods for macroscopic observation follow standard paleopathological protocols for the identification of temporal bone lesions (Flohr and Schultz, 2009; Purchase et al., 2019).

4. 1. 5. 8. Methods for recording tuberculosis

In this study lesions potentially indicative of tuberculosis were examined following the protocol proposed by Steckel et al. (2005). The analysis includes macroscopic examination of thoracic and lumbar vertebrae to identify possible erosive lesions, and in addition the inspection of pleural surfaces of preserved ribs and recording of eventual presence of proliferative lesions. Lesions were recorded using a scoring system, with 1 indicating absence of pathological changes, 2 indicating their presence, and 0 denoting unavailable thoracic or lumbar vertebrae and ribs.

In the statistical analyses, the presence of tuberculosis was scored as a binary variable, with cases coded as either present or absent.

Furthermore, the analysis will explore possible correlations between the identified lesions on vertebrae and ribs and the presence of *Serpens endocrania symmetrica*, a skeletal manifestation that also has been associated with tuberculosis (Abegg et al., 2020).

4. 1. 5. 9. Methods for recording *Serpens endocrania symmetrica*

For the purpose of this study the preserved endocranial surfaces were subjected to macroscopic inspection and magnification analysis using a hand lens, with systematic recording of presence and absence of lesions indicative of *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (Schultz 2001).

The presence or absence of *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* was recorded as a binary variable and used in this form for statistical analyses.

4. 1. 5. 10. Methods for recording Enamel hypoplasia and caries

Enamel hypoplasia (EH) was recorded following standard macroscopic criteria, noting the presence, number, and location of linear defects on the labial, buccal, and lingual surfaces of permanent and deciduous teeth. Dental caries were identified and recorded according to macroscopic inspection, including the location (occlusal, interproximal, cervical, or root surface), number, and severity of lesions (Hillson 2014). For both types of dental pathologies, presence or absence was recorded and subsequently used in the statistical analyses

4. 2. Materials and Methods: Funerary Context Assessment

The funerary dataset analyzed in this study includes 103 funerary vessels recorded during the excavation of the Ostojićevo necropolis. Of these, 87 vessels were sufficiently preserved for typological analysis, 46 vessels allowed reconstruction of volume, and 48 vessels allowed measurement of height. Biological sex could be established for 23 subadults whose burials were also associated with specific vessel types.

Grave goods were analyzed in 74 subadult burials where the skeletal remains were also preserved. A total of 35 grave items were recorded, with individual graves containing up to four items. Among these, 49 graves (66.2%) contained no grave goods, while 25 graves (33.8%) contained at least one item.

Burial orientation was analyzed for 43 adults and 45 subadults of determined biological sex. Four primary orientations were recorded: North-South (N–S), South-North (S–N), East-West (E–W), and West-East (W–E).

4. 2. 1. Orientation of the burial

During the Middle Bronze Age at the Ostojićevo necropolis, adult individuals were interred according to a sex-specific pattern: males predominantly in a north–south orientation, placed on the left side, and females in a south–north orientation, placed on the right side, in both cases with the face directed eastward. The bodies were deposited in a flexed position. Nevertheless, certain deviations from this normative mortuary practice were documented, including interments oriented east–west or west–east, as well as burials deviating by several tens of degrees from the north–south axis (Girić 1995). Comparable orientation patterns of the deceased at the Ostojićevo necropolis were also documented in the earlier horizon associated with the Early Bronze Age, as well as at the nearby Early Bronze Age necropolis of Mokrin (Girić 1971; Girić 1995).

These orientations are equally represented in both individuals buried in vessels and those buried outside of them. Certain deviations from expected values are noted, but these differences are not statistically significant.

Regarding individuals in vessels, with one exception (Grave Ostojićevo 124), the skeletons have the same orientation as the vessel itself, meaning the skull of the individual is oriented towards the opening of the vessel.

For the purpose of this study the burial orientation of 43 adult individuals of known sex was analyzed. Biological sex of adults was determined through standard anthropological methods by Katharina Pompeani (2020), while data on orientation were obtained from field documentation (National museum Kikinda). Burial orientations of adult individuals were compared with subadult burial orientations in a sample of 45 subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis. Sex of the individuals from the subadult sample was established through the analysis of sex-specific peptides.

4. 2. 2. Grave goods

At the Ostojićevo necropolis, the majority of burials are modestly furnished, typically containing few, if any, grave goods. The most numerous graves are those without offerings, and offerings are even rarer among individuals buried in vessels. The burial vessel is most often the only grave inventory. Ceramic vessels are the most common grave assemblage, and in one case, a metal object, a stone object, a shell, and an animal bone were also found (Fieldwork documentation, National Museum of Kikinda).

The number of grave goods, excluding the burial vessels which served as funerary containers, will be analysed in order to determine potential differences in the quantity of grave goods between boys and girls, as well as across different age categories.

Comparing funerary treatment, including the presence of grave goods, with the biological characteristics, such as sex and age, that can be determined through skeletal analysis may reveal potential differences in the social status of different groups.

Vertical social status will be determined based on the assumption that different number of grave offerings indicate a different position within the community (O'Shea 1996), which will serve to assess the relationship between social standing and overall health of children. The analysis will consider the total number of grave goods across the sample. Based on previous studies (O'Shea 1996; Vučetić 2015), burials can be characterized by the types of accompanying items. Graves of individuals with more elaborate goods often include axes, daggers, and head decorations in males, and belt fittings, head decorations, or bone needles in females. Graves with simpler offerings may contain ceramics, necklaces made of various materials, or small animal bone items. Graves without grave goods, according to this framework, may reflect lower social differentiation.

4. 2. 3. Burial receptacles

4. 2. 3. 1. Dimensions of burial receptacles and measuring methods

The following dimensions were recorded during the measurement of the vessels: external diameter, internal diameter, height, and the internal volume of the vessels.

The volume of burial receptacles was measured using the direct measurement method, which was facilitated by the level of preservation of the vessels in the case of both complete and reconstructed receptacles. Direct measurements are ideal due to their precision. These measurements are conducted directly on the containers, allowing us to ascertain their true capacity, which will serve as the reference value for subsequent comparisons. The method involves filling the vessel with a suitable material that conforms to its internal shape, ideally distilled water for enhanced accuracy. If this is not feasible, small plastic particles or pulses can be used instead (Senior and Birnie, 1995; Velasco Felipe and Celdrán Beltrán 2019). Due to the degree of preservation, direct volume measurement using liquid was not feasible for the burial receptacles from the Ostojićevo necropolis. As an alternative, polystyrene

beads with a diameter of up to 5 mm were utilized. To determine the maximum capacity, the vessels were filled to the brim. Subsequently, the volume of the contents was measured in graduated containers with an accuracy of one cubic centimeter.

External diameter, internal diameter and height were measured directly by using a measuring tape. These vessel dimensions were recorded in order to determine potential correlation between vessel size and stature or body mass of subadult individuals that were interred inside the receptacles. The degree of correlation between the child's age, stature and the volume and height of the burial recipient will be analyzed, which could indicate certain aspects of burial practices. That association could potentially mean that these vessels were selected for each individual child with their body dimensions in mind and potentially intent and care of the relatives and community.

4. 2. 3. 2. Type of burial receptacles

Funerary recipients at the Ostojićevo necropolis, exhibit variations not only in dimensions, but also in shape, and handle form, and were therefore classified into six typological categories. Typological differences may reflect different preferences in the selection and production of funerary vessels through the necropolis's century-long use (1650-1550 BCE). The type of burial vessel may also correlate with sex and age of children. For the purpose of this study statistical analysis was conducted to explore potential correlation between the typological categories and sex, and age of children buried inside the vessels. One important question that should also be addressed is whether the children of both sexes were interred inside the vessels, or this burial custom was reserved for only one.

All recorded vessel types were produced in various dimensions, with variations in height, rim diameter and vessel capacity. Differences were also recorded in forms, type of handles and decorations. The quality of craftsmanship and the temperature of firing of funerary pottery can also vary.

Vessel type A

Pithos-type funerary vessel with an elongated biconical body, short neck and large diameter slightly flared rim, and a flat base of smaller diameter. Two (Figure 5a.) or four (Figure 5c) small, oval in sections, horizontal lug handles are visible below the rim. Or the same shape vessel can be made without handles (Figure 5b). The surface is unevenly fired with a range of colors from reddish brown to dark grey.

Figure 5 a. Burial Vessel, Grave 173.

Figure 5 b. Burial Vessel, Grave 20

Figure 5 c. Burial Vessel - Grave 2 (Photo a, b, c: Parditka, Gyöergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Vessel type B

Vessels of biconical, almost ovoid form, with slightly flared rim, short necks, and narrower base. Two small loop shaped handles are positioned at the transition between the neck and shoulder. The entire rim is decorated with fingerprint impressions, and plastic ornaments running along the shoulder of the vessels. As with the previous types of vessels, the firing temperature was uneven resulting in irregular surface color ranging from reddish-brown to dark-grey.

Figure 6. Burial Vessel - Grave 70 (Photo: Parditka, Gyöergyi, National Museum Kikinda).

Vessel type C

Vessels of biconical form, with markedly flared rim, short neck and narrow base with one or two loop-shaped handles at the transition between the neck and shoulder. The vessel's surface exhibits irregular coloration, ranging from yellowish-brown to dark grey.

Figure 7. Burial Vessel - Grave 16 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi, National Museum Kikinda).

Vessel type D

Type D comprises funerary vessels of distinctly biconical form, characterized by a slightly smaller rim diameter, flared rim, strongly pronounced shoulder and belly, and a sharply contracted base, with two ribbon-shaped handles extending from the rim of the vessel to the shoulder. On the belly, decorations consist of linear grooves executed as parallel incisions, as well as plastic ornaments in the form of applied ribbon-like bands bearing fingerprint impressions. At the junction between the shoulder and belly, small symbolic tongue-shaped plastic handles may be present.

Figure 8. Burial vessel from the grave Ostojićevo 195 (Photo: Parditka, Gyöergyi, National Museum Kikinda).

Vessel type E

The type E includes vessels of biconical form, with slightly flared rim, short neck, and narrow base, resulting in a pyriform shape recipient. Below the rim, at the transition between the neck and the shoulder, two tongue-shaped or loop-shaped handles are positioned. The shoulder bears an applied plastic appendage in canopy-like form.

Figure 9. Funerary vessel Ostojićevo 37. (Photo: Parditka, Gyöergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 10. Funerary vessel Ostojićevo 75. (Photo: Parditka, Gyöergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Vessel type F

The type F includes vessels of biconical form, with a short neck, markedly flared rim and pronounced shoulder. Along the shoulder a band of plastic decoration with fingerprint impressions might be present. Two ribbon shaped handles extending from the rim to the shoulder of the vessel. The vessel's surface exhibits irregular coloration, ranging from yellowish-brown to dark grey.

Figure 11. Burial Vessel - Grave 10
(Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi, National Museum Kikinda).

5. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 23 (IBM Corp., 2015). The level of significance for all tests was set to; $p \leq 0.05$. The following analyses were conducted for statistical significance estimation of age and sex differences within the subadult sample: Chi-square test of independence, Fisher's Exact Test, Pearson's chi-square test, Spearman's Rank Correlation Test and Mann-Whitney U test. All results were independent at the 95% confidence level.

6. RESULTS

6. 1. Age structure of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis

Dental age was assessed using a degree of eruption and development according to standards for deciduous and permanent teeth (AlQahtani et al., 2010) and the Kvaal et al., (1995) method in a total of 49 individuals. Postcranial age estimation relied on the length of the long bones (Marshe 1970; Fazekas and Kosa (1978) and epiphyseal fusion (Buikstra and Ubelacker 1994), for 25 individuals in the analysed sample.

Age was determined for a total of 74 individuals, of which 17 (22.97%) belonged to the perinatal and neonatal category (Table 3). In 25 (33.78%) cases children were younger than 1 year, but did not belong to the perinatal or neonatal cohort. Three individuals (4.05%) were assigned to the 1–2- year age category, and other three (4.05%) to the 2–4-years age category. Eight individuals (10.88%) were classified in the 4–7-year, while 6 individuals (8.11%) belonged to the 7–10-years category. Only one individual (1.35%) was identified within the 10–15-years age category. In the 15–20-years category eight individuals (10.88%) were identified, along with three individuals older than 20 years, who were included in analysis due to incomplete epiphyseal fusion.

The age distribution of children demonstrates predominance of infant and early child mortality. The largest proportion of the sample consists of individuals younger than one year of age, 42 individuals (56.76 %) combined, when both perinatal/neonatal and infants under one year of age are considered. More than half of individuals excavated within Ostojićevo necropolis were under one year of age at the time of death. This period seems to constitute the most critical phase for survival during early childhood. The 10–15-year age group is also noticeably underrepresented, comprising only one individual from the entire Ostojićevo necropolis sample (1.35%).

Table 3. Age structure of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage of sample (%)
Perinatus/Neonatus	17	22.97%
<1 year	25	33.78%
1-2 years	3	4.05%
2-4 years	3	4.05%
4-7 years	8	10.88%
7-10 years	6	8.11%
10-15 years	1	1.35%
15-20 years	8	10.88 %
Over 20 years	3	4.05 %
Total number (n)	74	100%

6. 1. 1. Neonatal line (NNL) as an indicator of stillbirth and live-birth

Figure12. Neonatal line visible under transmitted light microscopy at 50x magnification, observed on tooth 63, grave Ostojićevo 218 (Photo: Bojan Petrović and Marija Marin).

The sample consisted of 15 individuals and in total 15 teeth of children up to 1 year of age, including central and lateral incisors as well as canines from both the maxilla and the mandible. Of the 15 deciduous teeth analyzed, the neonatal line was successfully observed in 9 specimens. In 4 individuals the neonatal line was not visible, and 2 samples were excluded from further analysis due to taphonomic degradation.

In four individuals in whom the neonatal line was not identified, maximum enamel thickness was assessed, revealing that the stage of enamel mineralization at the time of death corresponded to an *in utero* age of less than 37 weeks (World Health Organisation 2023). This finding is consistent with a preterm birth status and consequently increases the probability that these individuals were stillborn.

Table 4. Enamel thickness, age, and Neonatal Line Assessment of Deciduous Teeth from the Ostojićevo Necropolis.

Grave number	FDI Tooth number	Sex	NNL (present/absent)	Enamel thickness (µm)	Enamel mineralisation time scale (days)
1	73	Female	Present	523.97	258.10
2	53	Female	Present	849.38	245.10

5	73	Female	Present	797.93	331.30
13	63	Female	Present	628.65	286.09
19	73	Female	Present	603.59	279.39
37	62	Male	Absent	592.94	256.50
48	61	Male	Absent	482.57	227.03
95	73	Male	Present	603.32	279.32
183	62	Male	Not estimated	686.31	281.51
195	63	Male	Present	646.49	290.86
205	72	Female	Absent	396.83	204.10
218	63	Female	Present	685.88	301.39
242	82	Female	Absent	440.69	215.83
248	63	Female	Present	685.80	301.36
249	52	Male	Not estimated	548.04	244.53

Certain methodological limitations have to be also discussed when interpreting the absence of neonatal line (NNL) as evidence of stillbirth in individuals recovered from necropolises in general, and in Ostojićevo. The visibility of the NNL can be influenced by several biological, methodological, and post-mortem factors. Variations in enamel thickness and mineralization may render the line faint or incomplete, particularly in late-forming teeth such as lateral incisors.

Technical aspects of sample preparation, including polishing, reflected light adjustments, and surface orientation, can further obscure the NNL. Consequently, the absence of a visible NNL alone cannot be taken as definitive evidence of stillbirth; corroborating evidence from multiple teeth and morphological evidence should also be taken into account (Estivals et al., 2025).

Individuals lacking a discernible neonatal line, and exhibiting no detectable pre- or postnatal enamel formation, were recovered from graves Ostojićevo 37, 48, 205, and 242. The absence of NNL further supports the interpretation that these individuals were preterm and potentially stillborn.

Figure 13 a, b. a) Neonatal line not visible under light microscopy at 50x magnification, observed on tooth 61, grave 48. b) Ostojićevo-Grave 48. (Photo: National Museum Kikinda).

Table 5. Burial ritual for stillborn children.

Grave number	Sex	Burial orientation	Burial vessel (present/absent)
Ostojićevo 37	Male	Northwest-Southeast	Present
Ostojićevo 48	Male	North-South	Present
Ostojićevo 205	Female	North-South	Present
Ostojićevo 242	Female	Not estimated	Not estimated

Regarding the funerary treatment, of the individuals who can be considered potentially stillborn, 3 out of 4 (75%) were interred in burial receptacles. For one individual (Ostojićevo 242), it is unknown whether the burial was within a receptacle or outside of it (25%).

Regarding burial orientation, the male individuals presumed to be stillborn (graves Ostojićevo 37 and 48) were interred predominantly in a north–south orientation, which represents the typical male burial orientation, although individual Ostojićevo 37 shows slight deviation. The female individual (grave Ostojićevo 205) was buried in the opposite orientation (south–north). For individual Ostojićevo 242, the burial orientation was not recorded. Of the four potentially stillborn individuals, 2 (50%) were buried in the expected orientation, 1 (25%) in the opposite orientation, and 1 (25%) had an unknown orientation. Analysis of burial orientation among potentially stillborn individuals at Ostojićevo indicates that 50% (2/4) were interred in the expected north–south orientation consistent with typical male burial practices, 25% (1/4) were interred in an orientation opposite to what would be expected for their sex (female individual), and 25% (1/4) had unknown orientation. Fisher’s Exact Test did not reveal a statistically significant association between sex and burial orientation (one-tailed $p=0.667$).

With regard to the sex of the children in this sample, it was determined through the analysis of sex-specific peptides. The results indicate that among the youngest individuals interred, both boys and girls are represented, and that in the case of potentially stillborn individuals, both sexes are equally represented. Therefore we can conclude that the biological sex of newborn children did not influence the decision whether they should be interred inside the necropolis.

Table 6. Sex distribution of live-born and stillborn children at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Birth outcome	Male (n, %)	Female (n, %)	Total (n)
Live-born	2 (22.2%)	7 (77.8%)	9
Stillborn	2 (50.0%)	2 (50.0%)	4
Total (n)	4	9	13

Analysis of sex distribution among live-born and stillborn children at the Ostojićevo necropolis shows that 30.8% of the total sample were male and 69.2% female. Among live-born children, 22.2% were male and 77.8% female, whereas stillborn children were evenly distributed between males and females (50% each). Fisher's Exact Test indicates no statistically significant association between sex and birth outcome (two-tailed; $df=1$, $N=13$, $p=0.530$; one-tailed $p=0.354$).

6. 2. Biological sex of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis

As a part of this study, biological sex determination was conducted using sex-specific peptide analysis allowing the identification of biological sex of 49 subadult individuals from the Middle Bronze Age horizon at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Sex-specific peptide analysis of the subadult sample from the necropolis revealed a nearly balanced sex distribution, comprising 25 females and 24 males.

Table 7. Sex distribution of the subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis ($n=49$).

Biological sex	Number of the individuals	Percentage (%)
Female	25	51.02%
Male	24	48.98%
Total	49	100.00%

This roughly equal distribution suggests no sex-biased mortality in the subadult age group, and also a similar survival rate for boys and girls in the early life.

Table 8. Age and sex distribution of subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis ($n=49$).

Age (years)	Male	Percentage (%)	Female	Percentage (%)	Total	Percentage (%)
<1	10	20.41%	9	18.37%	19	38.78%
1–5	5	10.20%	3	6.12%	8	16.33%

5–10	4	8.16%	6	12.24%	10	20.41%
10–15	1	2.04%	0	0.00%	1	2.04%
15–20	3	6.12%	5	10.20%	8	16.33%
>20	1	2.04%	2	4.08%	3	6.12%
Total	24	48.98%	25	51.02%	49	100.00%

In younger age groups, up to 5 years of age, male individuals are slightly more represented (15 individuals) compared to the female group younger than 5 years (12 individuals). In later childhood and early adolescence (5-20 years) females are more represented, which possibly could reflect higher mortality of females in these age groups. Fisher's exact test (one-tailed) revealed no statistically significant difference in the distribution of boys and girls across the age categories under 5 years and 5–20 years (df=1, N=49, p=0.232), indicating that the trend observed within the sample does not reach statistical significance.

6. 3. Growth and development of subadult children from the Ostojićevo

6. 3. 1. Growth pattern and dental age comparison

Age estimation for subadult individuals was performed using radiographic analysis and evaluated using the London Atlas of Tooth Development and Eruption (AlQahtani et al., 2010). For the older categories of subadults (for individuals over 18 years of age) with all permanent dentitions erupted, Kvaal et al., (1995) method was applied. The obtained dental age estimates were subsequently compared to postcranial age estimates based on diaphyseal length measurements of long bones, which were evaluated according to the growth standards compiled by Maresh (1970). For fetal and perinatal individuals, age assessment was based on the reference data provided by Fazekas and Kósa, based on long bone measurements and also other skeletal elements (1978).

The aim of this comparison was to determine whether the dental age, which is considered the most reliable proxy for chronological age in subadult individuals (Saunders et al., 1993; Cardoso 2007), corresponds to the degree of postcranial skeletal growth. Individuals were categorized based on the consistency between their dental development and long bone growth, distinguishing those with growth rates consistent with, delayed, or accelerated relative to the expected pattern derived from dental age.

Out of a total of 74 analyzed individuals, 49 subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis had sufficiently preserved dentitions to allow for a reliable assessment of dental age. In 32 individuals, both dental age was determined and postcranial elements necessary for reconstructing the growth rate of long bones were preserved.

Considering that the dental age is the closest approximation of the chronological age, in 23 (71.9%) out of the 32 compared individuals, the growth and development of postcranial long bones were slower than expected for that dental age. In six individuals (18.8%), postcranial growth corresponded to the expected tempo based on dental age, while in three individuals (9.4%) growth tempo was accelerated.

Table 9. Growth pattern and dental age comparison in the Ostojićevo necropolis subadult group.

Growth pattern relative to dental age	Number of individuals (n)	Percentages (%)
Slower than expected	23	71.9%
Consisted with dental age	6	18.8%
Accelerated growth	3	9.4%
Total	32	100.00%

When examined by sex, the majority of both males (68.8%) and females (75.0%) displayed delayed growth, whereas accelerated growth was observed exclusively among male individuals (18.8%).

Table 10. Growth Patterns by Sex.

Growth pattern relative to dental age	Males (n, %)	Females (n, %)	Total (n, %)
Slower than expected	11 (47.8%)	12 (52.2%)	23 (71.9%)
Consisted with dental age	2 (33.3%)	4 (66.7%)	6 (18.8%)
Accelerated growth	3 (100.00%)	0 (0%)	3 (9.4 %)
Total (n, %)	16 (50 %)	16 (50%)	32 (100%)

Fisher's Exact Test indicated no statistically significant association between sex and growth pattern (two-tailed, $df=2$, $N=32$, $p = 0.212$), suggesting that observed differences may reflect individual developmental variability rather than sex-based biological trends.

Accelerated growth pattern is observed only in male subadults, which may indicate certain biological or development trends. However, given the relatively small sample size, these results should be interpreted with caution.

Table 11. Age distribution of different growth patterns at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Midpoint (years)	Slower than expected (n, %)	Consisted with dental age (n, %)	Accelerated growth (n, %)
<1	0.5	4 (17.4%)	3 (50.0%)	2 (66.7%)
1–5	3	4 (17.4%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0.00%)

5–10	7.5	5 (21.7%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (33.3%)
10–15	12.5	1 (4.3%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
15–20	17.5	7 (30.4%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
>20	22.5	2 (8.7%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
Total		23 (100.0%)	6 (100.0%)	3 (100.0%)

Spearman's rank correlation was performed to assess the relationship between age and postcranial growth tempo relative to dental age and it indicated a very weak and not statistically significant positive association between age and growth tempo ($\rho = 0.112$, $df=30$, $N=32$, $p = 0.542$), suggesting that there are no differences in deviations from expected growth rate relative to dental age in different age categories.

6. 3. 2. Body mass of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis

Of the total sample of 74 subadult individuals, body mass was estimated in 11 individuals with sufficiently preserved skeletal elements for assessing body weight. Body mass was estimated for individuals aged between 3 and 12 years, using a regression equation proposed by Visser (1998), which derived body mass from long bone length. The estimated values were then compared to contemporary reference standards provided by the World Health Organization (WHO 2006; 2007) allowing assessment of growth patterns to be compared to modern populations.

Table 12. Body mass estimation of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Grave number	Age	Sex	Body Mass (mean) (kg)	Weight for age (kg) (WHO 2006; 2007)
Ostojićevo 4	5.5-6 years	Not estimated	18.94	15.3-28.3
Ostojićevo 14	8.5 years	Female	19.49	20-37.4
Ostojićevo 18	8.5 years	Female	12.13	20-37.4
Ostojićevo 77	4.5 years	Male	21.84	13-24
Ostojićevo 112	4.5 years	Not estimated	5.78	13-24
Ostojićevo 130	6.5 years	Female	11.36	16.3-28.9
Ostojićevo 157	6.5-7.5 years	Male	11.42	17-32
Ostojićevo 160	7.5 years	Male	14.22	18.8-32
Ostojićevo 165	7.5 years	Male	21.44	18.8-32

Ostojićevo 219	8.5-9 years	Female	30.70	20-40
Ostojićevo 276	5.5-6.5	Female	22.21	14.8-27.3

For six individuals, estimated body mass was significantly lower than the reference ranges provided by the World Health organisation (2006: 2007), for their respective age groups. Compared to contemporary weight standards these six subadult individuals were significantly underweight, while five individuals had estimated body mass within reference ranges.

Table 13. Estimated body mass of subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis by sex, compared to WHO reference ranges.

Sex	Number of individuals (n)	Estimated body mass below WHO range (n, %)	Estimated body mass within WHO range (n, %)
Male	4	2 (50.0%)	2 (50.0%)
Female	5	3 (60.0%)	2 (40.0%)
Not estimated	2	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)
Total	11	6 (54.5%)	5 (45.5%)

Analysis of estimated body mass for subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis revealed that 6 out of 11 individuals (54.5%) had body mass below the WHO reference range for their age, while 5 individuals (45.5%) fell within the expected range. When stratified by sex, 50% of males and 60% of females were below the WHO range, whereas the remaining individuals were within the reference values.

Fisher’s Exact Test, p-value one-tailed, indicated no statistically significant association between sex and body mass category (df=1, N=9, p =0.643), suggesting that the observed variation in body mass relative to modern reference ranges is not dependent on sex in the Ostojićevo subadult sample. Having in mind that this sample is relatively small, one must be careful with conclusions based on these observations.

6. 3. 3. Stature of children from Ostojićevo necropolis

Stature of the subadult sample that included 40 individuals was estimated using the regression equations of Murray et al. (2024), which predict stature from diaphyseal lengths of the humerus, radius, ulna, femur, and tibia, that was calculated based on the tables for the body height of subadult individuals provided by Maresh (Maresh 1955; 1970). The estimated values of height of subadult individuals were then compared to contemporary reference standards provided by the World Health Organization (WHO 2006; 2007) allowing the comparison of growth in Ostojićevo children to modern populations.

Table 14. Stature estimation of children at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Grave number	Age	Sex	Stature (mean) (cm)	Stature for age (cm) (WHO 2006; 2007)
Ostojićevo 1	6-7.5 months	Female	49.91	67.62-74.2
Ostojićevo 2	7.5 months	Female	64.39	67.28-72.7
Ostojićevo 4	5-6 years	Not estimated	116.16	109.60-127.4
Ostojićevo 5	10.5 months	Female	65.14	71.48-77.2
Ostojićevo 12	34-36 gestational weeks	Not estimated	51.83	49.14-54.3
Ostojićevo 14	8.5 years	Female	106.26	129.49-143.4
Ostojićevo 15	34 gestational weeks	Not estimated	50.49	49.14-54.3
Ostojićevo 17A	14.5-15.5 years	Male	137.08	166.30-189.3
Ostojićevo 18	8.5 years	Female	104.94	129.49-143.4
Ostojićevo 20	34 gestational weeks	Male	52.12	49.88-54.3
Ostojićevo 24	38-40 gestational weeks	Not estimated	56.86	49.14-54.3
Ostojićevo 38	16.5-17.5 years	Male	175.34	174.22-193.4
Ostojićevo 77	4.5 years	Male	97.97	106.66-116.9
Ostojićevo 89	1-1.5 years	Male	75.44	75.74-88.5
Ostojićevo 96	10.5 months	Male	71.42	73.28-78.6
Ostojićevo 102	16.5 years	Female	143.55	162.71-178.4
Ostojićevo 108A	15.5 years	Male	147.01	171.14-189.3
Ostojićevo 112	4.5 years	Not	97.51	106.17-116.9

		estimated		
Ostojicevo 130	6.5 years	Female	102.46	117.97-130.3
Ostojicevo 133	1.5 months	Female	57.06	53.68-58.2
Ostojicevo 133A	38-40 gestational weeks	Not estimated	48.69	49.14-54.3
Ostojicevo 134	6-12 months	Not estimated	68.97	65.73-81.3
Ostojicevo 146	15.5-16.5 years	Female	168.54	162.18-178.4
Ostojicevo 150	1.5 month	Not estimated	60.63	53.68-59.3
Ostojicevo 157	6.5-7.5	Male	95.32	118.87-137.3
Ostojicevo 160	7.5 years	Male	107.23	124.53-137.3
Ostojicevo 165	7.5 years	Male	137.11	124.53-137.3
Ostojicevo 170	32-38 gestational weeks	Not estimated	49.88	49.14-54.3
Ostojicevo 176	23 years	Female	169.27	163.15-178.4
Ostojicevo 183	10.5 months	Male	70.72	73.28-78.6
Ostojicevo 195	10.5-12 months	Male	69.16	73.28-81.3
Ostojicevo 205	1 month	Female	65.89	53.68-58.2
Ostojicevo 207	4.5-5 years	Male	72.76	106.66-120.7
Ostojicevo 219	8.5-9 years	Female	133.88	129.49-150.1
Ostojicevo 231	16.5-17.5 years	Female	153.22	162.71-178.4
Ostojicevo 237	19-20 years	Female	137.48	163.15-178.4
Ostojicevo 245	25 years	Male	176.15	176.54-193.5
Ostojicevo 275	16.5-17.5	Male	163.93	174.22-193.4
Ostojicevo 276	5.5-6 years	Female	113.02	112.17-127.0
Ostojicevo 277	2.5 years	Male	69.73	91.93-99.9

In 24 individuals (60.0%), estimated height was lower than the reference ranges provided by the World Health Organisation (2006; 2007) for their age groups. Compared to contemporary height standards these 24 individuals were lower in height, while for 13 individuals (32.5%) estimated stature was within reference ranges. In three individuals (7.5%) height accelerated ranges provided by WHO (2006; 2007).

Table 15. Estimated height of subadult individuals from the Ostojićevo necropolis by sex, compared to WHO reference ranges.

Sex	Number of individuals (n)	Estimated height below WHO range (n, %)	Estimated height within WHO range (n, %)	Estimated height over WHO range (n, %)
Male	16	13 (81.3%)	3 (18.7%)	0 (0%)
Female	15	9 (60.0%)	5 (33.3%)	1 (6.7%)
Not estimated	9	2 (22.2%)	5 (55.6%)	2 (22.2%)
Total	40	24 (60.0%)	13 (32.5%)	3 (7.5%)

Fisher’s Exact Test (two-tailed) was conducted in order to test for association between sex and height category (below, within and over the estimated height range). No statistically significant association was found between sex and height category (two-tailed, $df=2$, $N=31$, $p = 0.313$).

Although a larger proportion of males (81.3%) showed stature below WHO expectations compared to females (60.0%) and indeterminate individuals (22.2%), this difference is not statistically significant, due to the small sample size and uneven distribution among categories.

Table16. Age distribution of subadult individuals by stature at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Number of individuals (n)	Estimated height below WHO range (n, %)	Estimated height within WHO range (n, %)	Estimated height over WHO range (n, %)
<1	16	7 (43.8%)	6 (37.5%)	3 (18.8%)
1–5	5	5 (100.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
5–10	9	5 (55.6%)	4 (44.6%)	0 (0%)
10–15	1	1 (100.0%)	0 (%)	0 (0%)
15–20	7	5 (71.4%)	2 (28.6%)	0 (0%)
>20	2	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	0 (0%)
Total	40	24 (60.0%)	13 (32.5%)	3 (7.5%)

When examined by age category, 60.0% of all subadult individuals exhibited stature below the WHO reference range. The frequency of below-expected height increased in the age groups 1–5 (100%), and in the 5–10 (55.6%). Differences in deviation from the expected height ranges were assessed between individuals aged 0–1 years and those older than 1 year. The Chi-Square test confirmed a statistically significant relationship between age category and height status ($\chi^2=5.879$. $df=10$, $N=40$, $p = 0.044$), indicating that growth deficits were more frequent among younger group of subadults, aged 0–1 years. This suggests the presence of cumulative stress factors affecting growth during the earliest stages of development that affected the next phase.

6. 4. Paleopathological analysis of the subadult population from the Ostojićevo necropolis

6. 4. 1. Skeletal changes of potential traumatic or possible therapeutic nature

At the Ostojićevo necropolis, the presence of traumas of various etiologies was analyzed on both the cranial and postcranial skeleton. A total of 61 individuals from the entire child sample were examined, while 13 individuals were excluded from this analysis due to insufficient preservation of skeletal elements, where only one or a few small fragments of a single cranial or postcranial bone were preserved.

The characterization of trauma includes two main categories: blunt force trauma and sharp force trauma (Cohen et al., 2012). In addition to the type of injury, the anatomical location of each trauma was also recorded (cranial and postcranial skeleton).

Traumatic injuries of unknown etiology were identified in a total of 8 individuals. Due to the poor overall preservation of the subadult skeletal material from the Ostojićevo necropolis, where certain skeletal elements are entirely absent in individuals, it was not possible to determine the precise prevalence of trauma in the sample.

Traumas were observed in four subadult male individuals, two female individuals, and two individuals of undetermined sex.

Table 17. Sex Distribution of Subadult Individuals with traumatic injuries (Ostojićevo).

Biological sex	Total analysed sample	Number of individuals with trauma (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	21	4	19.00%
Female	25	2	8.0%
Undetermined	15	2	13.3%
Total	61	8	13.1%

Traumatic injuries were observed in 8 individuals from the analyzed sample of 61 subadults. Among these, four were male (19.0% of males), two were female (8.0% of females), and two were of undetermined sex (13.3%). Statistical analysis using Fisher’s Exact Test, excluding individuals of undetermined sex, showed no significant difference in the prevalence of trauma between males and

females (df=1, N=52, p = 0.297 one-tailed). These results indicate that, within this sample, traumatic injuries did not vary significantly according to biological sex.

The age of individuals with traumatic injuries ranges from 38 gestational weeks to 7.5 years.

Table 18. Age distribution of subadult individuals with traumatic injuries at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with traumatic injuries	Percentage of individuals with trauma within Age group (%)
<1	31	5	16.10%
1–5	8	2	25.00%
5–10	11	1	9.10%
10–15	-	-	-
15–20	8	0	0.00%
>20	3	0	0.00%
Total	61	8	13.10%

The highest prevalence was noted in children aged 1–5 years (25.0%), followed by those under one year of age (16.1%), and the lowest in the 5–10-year category (9.1%), with no cases observed in individuals over 15 years.

Table 19. Grouped age categories.

Age category	Trauma present	Trauma absent
<5 years	7	32
≥5 years	1	21
Total	8	61

Statistical analysis using Fisher’s Exact Test, after grouping ages into <5 years and ≥5 years, showed no significant difference in trauma prevalence between younger and older subadults (df=1, N=61, p = 0.136, one tailed). These results suggest that traumatic injuries were relatively rare in the Ostojićevo sample and did not vary significantly with age. However, the obtained results regarding the frequency of trauma in the sample must be interpreted with caution due to the large number of individuals for whom not all skeletal elements on which trauma could have occurred were preserved.

Table 20. Trauma type and anatomical location.

Grave Number	Age	Biological sex	Trauma type	Anatomical location
Ostojićevo 1	6-7.5 monts	Female	Sharp force	Cranium
Ostojićevo 24	38-40 gestational weeks	Not estimated	Sharp force	Postcranium
Ostojićevo 157	6.5-7.5 years	Male	Sharp force	Cranium
Ostojićevo 163	1.5 years	Male	Sharp force	Cranium
Ostojićevo 173	3.5-4.5 years	Female	Blunt force	Cranium
Ostojićevo 183	10.5 months	Male	Sharp force	Cranium
Ostojićevo 195	10.5-12 months	Male	Sharp force	Cranium and postcranium
Ostojićevo 198	0-6 months	Not estimated	Sharp force	Cranium

Among the eight individuals exhibiting signs of trauma, six (75.0%) showed injuries exclusively on the cranium, one (12.5%) exhibited trauma solely on the postcranial skeleton, while one individual (12.5%) displayed evidence of trauma on both the cranial and postcranial elements.

Sharp force trauma was observed in seven individuals (87.5%), while blunt force trauma was recorded in one individual (12.5%), indicating that sharp force injuries were predominant within the sample.

Description of traumas:

Grave Ostojićevo 1

On the left parietal bone near the parietal tuber, three sharp force incisions were recorded, oriented vertically and parallel to the temporal suture. The first incision is superficial (20.91×1.32 mm), the second penetrates the endocranium and likely occurred when soft tissues were present (9.52×0.42 mm) and the third is superficial near the lambdoid suture (18.39×1.71 mm). Additionally, two irregular circular openings were observed at the parietal tuber (diameters 2.62 mm and 1.41 mm; 1.6 mm apart), of uncertain origin, possibly porotic lesions or trauma/intervention.

Grave Ostojićevo 24

On the right femur, at the distal third of the diaphysis on the anterior surface, three horizontal incisions consistent with sharp force trauma were observed. Each incision measures approximately 7 mm in length and 1 mm in width, with an inter-incision distance of about 6 mm.

Ostojićevo 157

On the right parietal bone, at the junction of the lambdoid and sagittal sutures, an irregular perforation was observed, measuring 3.69×6.76 mm, accompanied by two shallow semicircular incisions, approximately 200 mm in length and 2 mm in width. The incision profiles are of unclear shape. In both

cases, the injuries are consistent with sharp force trauma that likely occurred while soft tissues were still present.

Ostojicevo 163

On the posterior part of the left parietal bone, a narrow incision was observed, measuring approximately 10 mm in length and 1 mm in width. The injury is consistent with sharp force trauma and likely occurred while soft tissues were still present. The indentation is also visible on the endocranial surface of the parietal bone.

Ostojicevo 173

A blunt force trauma was observed on the frontal bone along the frontal suture, closer to the coronal suture, at the anterior third. The lesion consists of a shallow depression, oval in shape, measuring 6.61 × 8.91 mm, with visible healing traces. Surrounding the fracture on the parietal bone, fine porosity (~1 mm) and signs of vascularization were noted. Extending from the center of the lesion approximately 10 mm below up to the coronal suture, an irregular fracture follows the frontline suture for a total length of 40 mm and continues obliquely onto the parietal bone for 30 mm. At the lesion site, a thin endocranial crack is present, while the central fracture is visible on both the endocranial surfaces of the frontal and parietal bones.

Figure 14. Grave Ostojicevo 173. Frontal and parietal bone blunt force trauma: depression and oblique fracture lines

Ostojicevo 183

On the right parietal bone, near the mastoid suture, a semicircular incision was observed, approximately 9.60 mm in length and 1 mm in width. The incision profile is unclear, and it penetrates the endocranium, with transverse openings smaller than 1 mm. Bone periosteal reaction and new bone formation are present around the lesion.

Ostojicevo 195

Left supraorbital ridge (frontal bone): A sharp force incision with a V-shaped profile was observed above the left supraorbital ridge, measuring 12.50 mm in width, 5.21 mm in height, and 2.47 mm in depth. The trauma likely occurred while soft tissues were present. The cortical bone was penetrated, reaching the spongy tissue, but the endocranium remained intact. No periosteal reaction is observed along the margins of the lesion. Right femur: On the posterior aspect of the right femur, at the level of the linea aspera just below the lesser trochanter, a horizontal sharp force incision with a V-shaped profile was recorded, measuring 6.39×1 mm, with a depth of approximately 1 mm. The injury occurred while soft tissues were present and remained confined to the cortex. No periosteal reaction is observed along the margins of the lesion.

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On the right parietal bone, near the junction of the lambdoid and sagittal sutures, evidence of a circular lesion was observed, with a preserved diameter of approximately 25 mm and loss of bone at the central portion, suggestive of a traumatic event. Additionally, on an occipital bone fragment, a sharp incision measuring approximately 10 mm in length and 1 mm in width was documented, consistent with sharp force trauma that likely occurred in the presence of soft tissues. Both lesions demonstrate morphological characteristics indicative of perimortem cranial trauma, though the precise etiology of the parietal lesion remains uncertain due to partial bone loss.

6. 4. 2. Metabolic diseases

6. 4. 2. 1. Prevalence of *Cribra orbitalia* in the Ostojicevo necropolis subadult population

A total of 43 individuals of the Ostojicevo subadult sample had at least one preserved superior orbital roof (left or right) available for the analysis. Of these 31 (72.1 %) individuals exhibited *Cribra orbitalia*, while 12 (27.9 %) individuals with at least one preserved orbital roof showed no porotic changes on the orbital surface.

Table 21. Prevalence of *Cribra orbitalia* in subadult sample at the Ostojicevo necropolis.

Cribra orbitalia	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Present	31	72.1 %
Absent	12	27.9 %
Total	43	100.00 %

Of the total of 31 individuals exhibiting *Cribra orbitalia* in 18 (58.1 %) cases were assigned score of 2, indicating a cluster of mostly fine foramina covering a small area ($\leq 1 \text{ cm}^2$) on the orbital roof. The remaining 13 individuals (41.9 %) were assigned score of 3, reflecting a substantial area ($>1 \text{ cm}^2$) covered by small foramina with a tendency to cluster.

Individuals presenting with *Cribra orbitalia* encompassed a broad age range, from 38 gestational weeks to 25 years, reflecting perinatal and all postnatal developmental stages.

Table 22. Prevalence of individuals with *Cribra orbitalia* within the different Age groups.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with Cribra orbitalia	Percentage of individuals with Cribra within Age group (%)
<1	21	15	71.4 %
1–5	6	5	83.3 %
5–10	7	5	71.4 %
10–15	-	-	-
15–20	6	4	66.7 %
>20	3	2	66.7 %
Total	43	31	72.1 %

Figure 15. Number of individuals with *Cribra orbitalia* in different Age categories.

Age-specific analysis showed the highest prevalence among children aged 1–5 years (83.3%), with generally high frequencies across all other age groups, indicating widespread childhood stress in the Ostojićevo subadult population.

Some of the age categories have very small categories with very small sample sizes. Fisher's exact test was conducted by testing differences between three age groups: less than 1 year, 1–10 years and more than 10 years. *Cribra orbitalia* prevalence was 71.4% in individuals <1 year, 76.9% in the 1–10 years group, and 66.7% in those >10 years. Fisher's exact test revealed no statistically significant differences between groups (df=2, N=43, p=0.909, two-tailed), indicating a broadly consistent distribution of *Cribra orbitalia* in different age groups in the Ostojićevo subadult sample.

Regarding the sex of individuals exhibiting *Cribra orbitalia*, of the total sample of 31 subadults, 10 (66.7 %) were male, 19 (86.4%) were female, and 2 (33.3 %) individuals could not be sexed. *Cribra orbitalia* was observed in both sexes, with a slightly higher representation among females.

Table 23. Sex Distribution of Subadult Individuals with *Cribra orbitalia* (Ostojićevo).

Biological sex	Total sample (n)	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	15	10	66.7%
Female	22	19	86.4%
Undetermined	6	2	33.3%
Total	43	31	72.1 %

A Fisher's exact test was conducted to evaluate sex differences in the prevalence of the *Cribra orbitalia*. The analysis revealed no significant differences in prevalence between males (66.7 %) and females (86.4 %) (df= 1, N=37, two-tailed, p = 0.228 one-tailed. p=0.154), suggesting that porotic changes were equally distributed among sexes.

6. 4. 3. Prevalence of Porotic hyperostosis in the Ostojićevo necropolis subadult population

Of a total sample of 74 subadult individuals, 50 had at least one parietal bone preserved allowing for observation of porotic hyperostosis. In 27 individuals of the analyzed sample, porotic lesions of parietal bones were observed, and they represent 54 % of the total sample.

When considering the distribution of individuals with porotic hyperostosis by sex, 12 individuals (50.0%) were female, 10 individuals (54.5%) were male, while in 5 individuals (62.5%) sex could not be determined. The distribution of lesions shows no marked differences between males and females, suggesting that both sexes were similarly affected by the underlying stressors responsible for the development of porotic hyperostosis.

Table 24. Sex distribution of individuals with porotic hyperostosis at the Ostojićevo subadult sample.

Biological Sex	Total sample (n)	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	20	10	50.0%
Female	22	12	54.5%
Undetermined	8	5	62.5%
Total	50	27	54.0%

Statistical analysis using Fisher's exact test ($df = 1$, $N = 42$, $p = 0.506$, two-tailed) indicates that the observed difference in the prevalence of porotic hyperostosis between males and females is not statistically significant. This suggests that both sexes were equally represented in the sample with porotic hyperostosis at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

With regards to age distribution of subadult individuals with porotic hyperostosis, the observed cases encompassed a wide developmental range, from 38 gestational weeks to 17.5 years of age.

Table 25. Age distribution of subadult individuals with porotic hyperostosis at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with porotic hyperostosis	Percentage of individuals with PH within Age group (%)
<1	23	14	60.9%
1–5	8	6	75%
5–10	9	4	44.4%
10–15	-	-	-
15–20	7	3	42.9%
>20	3	-	0.0%
Total	50	27	54%

Since some of the age groups have very small categories with very small sample size, Chi-square test was conducted by testing differences between three age groups: less than 1 year, 1–10 years and more than 10 years.

Figure 16. Porotic hyperostosis age distribution in the Ostojićevo necropolis sample.

A Chi-square test of independence across the three age categories (<1 year, 1–10 years, >10 years) showed no statistically significant difference in porotic hyperostosis prevalence ($\chi^2 = 2.92$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.233$), indicating that the condition affected subadults relatively evenly across age groups. These results suggest that porotic hyperostosis affected subadults across age categories without significant variation, although prevalence was numerically higher among younger individuals.

6. 4. 4. Rickets in children from the Ostojićevo necropolis

Among the total analysed sample of 74 subadult individuals at the Ostojićevo necropolis, 51 exhibited sufficiently well-preserved postcranial skeletons and long bones, enabling the evaluation of potential skeletal deformities and alterations indicative of rickets. Out of the 51 examined subadult skeletons, 7 individuals (13.73%) showed long bone deformities consistent with rickets.

The individuals displaying long bone deformities were buried in graves marked as Ostojićevo 2, 77, 157, 183, 219, 231 and 275.

Table 26. Long bone deformities potentially associated with rickets at the Ostojićevo necropolis subadult group.

Presence and absence of long bone deformities	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Individuals with long bone deformities (potentially rickets)	7	13.73%
Individuals without long bone deformities	44	86.27%
Analysed subadult skeletons	51	100.00%

By analyzing sex-specific peptides, the biological sex was determined for all seven individuals exhibiting long bone deformities. The sample included three female and four male individuals.

Table 27. Biological sex distribution of individuals with long bone deformities indicative of rickets from the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Biological sex	Number of individuals without rickets (n)	Number of individuals with rickets (n)	Percentage within sex category (%)
Females	18	3	14.29%
Males	15	4	21.05%
Total	33	7	17.50%

A total of 33 individuals of known biological sex were also analysed for the long bone deformities associated with rickets. In order to determine potential association between sex of subadult individuals and rickets indicators Fisher's exact test was performed, and no statistically significant association was found between biological sex and long bone deformities in the sample (two-tailed, $p=0.674$, $N=33$, $df=1$).

Two individuals exhibiting long bone deformities were younger than one year of age, one belonged to the 1–5-year age category, and two individuals were between 5 and 10 years old. No cases of long bone deformities were recorded among individuals aged 10–15 years. Two individuals aged 15–20 years displayed skeletal changes consistent with rickets. When interpreting the age distribution, it should be noted that the 10–15-year age category is underrepresented in the sample, containing only one individual from the entire assemblage. It can be concluded that the distribution of individuals with rickets is approximately equal across all age categories.

The occurrence of long bone deformities in both male and female subadult individuals in all age categories, with exception of the 10–15-year age category that was underrepresented in the sample, may suggest a significant metabolic disturbances in the population of children from Ostojićevo who did not survived.

Deformities and other changes potentially associated with rickets were observed on one or more bones of the upper and lower limbs. In an individual from grave Ostojićevo 2 (female individual; estimated age: 7.5 months), the femoral diaphysis, as well as the tibial diaphysis and proximal epiphysis, exhibited posterior bowing and tilting. Additionally, a deformity of the acromial end of the clavicle was observed, accompanied by delayed clavicular growth relative to the other elements of the postcranial skeleton, and dental development. In a 4.5 year old male individual interred in a grave Ostojićevo 77, the proximal epiphysis of left and right ulna and proximal epiphysis of left and right tibiae exhibited posterior bowing and tilting. In the individual buried in grave Ostojićevo 183 (10.5-month-old male individual), posterior curvature was observed on the proximal epiphyses of both ulnae and the right tibia. A 8.5–9 year-old male buried in grave Ostojićevo 219 exhibited multiple signs consistent with rickets, including posterior bowing of the diaphyses of both ulnae, anterior bowing of the diaphyses

and lateral tilting of the distal epiphyses of both femora, and posterior tilting of the proximal epiphyses of both tibiae, indicating skeletal changes affecting both upper and lower limbs in these individuals.

In the individual buried in grave Ostojićevo 157 (a 6.5–7.5-year-old male individual), a posterior bowing was observed on the diaphysis of the left ulna. In a 16.5-17.5 old female individual buried in a grave Ostojićevo 231 anterior bowing of the diaphyses of both femora was observed, along with a mild medial torsion of distal epiphysis. Similar changes in both femora were also observed in male individual, 16.5-17.5 years old interred in a grave Ostojićevo 275. In these cases, skeletal deformities were restricted to a single limb group, presenting exclusively in either the upper or lower extremities.

Figure 17. Age distribution of individuals with long bone deformities.

6. 4. 5. Scurvy in Children from the Ostojićevo Necropolis

During the skeletal analysis, the following elements were examined for pathological manifestations of scurvy: cranial porosity and new bone deposition on the frontal, parietal, occipital, zygomatic, temporal, sphenoid, maxilla, and mandible bones, as well as postcranial lesions affecting the ribs, scapula, metaphyses of long bones, and iliac portions of the pelvis. Additionally, the analysis included endocranial changes, such as endocranial lesions, *serpens endocrania symmetrica*, and other nonspecific meningeal reactions. Individuals exhibiting three or more skeletal manifestations were scored as positive, indicating suspected presence of this nutritional deficiency during childhood.

Skeletal manifestations of scurvy were analyzed in 47 subadult individuals with preserved long bones available for reliable assessment. Among these, 26 individuals (55.3 %) exhibited a higher number of skeletal manifestations consistent with this nutritional deficiency, while 21 individuals exhibited no scurvy indicators.

Table 28. Prevalence of suspected scurvy in subadult individuals at the Ostojićevo necropolis sample.

Category	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Suspected scurvy cases	26	55.3%
Negative for scurvy indicators	21	44.7%
Total	47	100.00%

Table 29. Sex distribution of subadults with suspected scurvy at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Biological sex	Total sample (n)	Suspected scurvy cases	Negative for scurvy indicators (n)	Percentage of suspected scurvy cases in sample (%)
Male	19	13	6	68.4%
Female	21	10	11	47.6%
Not estimated	7	3	4	42.86%
Total	47	26	21	55.3%

Among those with identified sex, 13 of 19 males (68.4%) and 10 of 21 females (47.6%) exhibited these manifestations. Statistical analysis using the Chi-square test showed no significant difference between males and females in the presence of scurvy ($\chi^2 = 1.77$, $df = 1$, $N=40$, $p = 0.184$). Three individuals with unidentified sex were also positively scored. These results indicate that, although a slightly higher proportion of males were affected, the distribution of scurvy-related skeletal manifestations does not differ significantly between sexes in this sample.

Skeletal changes associated with scurvy were observed in individuals ranging in age from 36 gestational weeks to 25 years.

Table 30. Age distribution of subadult individuals with skeletal manifestations of scurvy at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with scurvy indicators	Percentage of individuals with scurvy within Age group (%)
<1	19	13	68.4%
1–5	8	4	50.00%
5–10	10	5	50.00%

10–15	1	-	0
15–20	6	2	33.33%
>20	3	1	33.33%
Total	47	26	%

The highest prevalence was observed among the youngest individuals, under one year of age (68.4%), followed by children aged 1–5 years (50.0%) and 5–10 years (50.0%). In contrast, the lowest frequencies were recorded in the older age categories, with 33.3% in individuals aged 15–20 years and over 20 years, while no scurvy indicators were observed in the single individual aged 10–15 years probably because of underrepresentation of this age category within the sample.

Statistical analysis using Fisher’s Exact Test was conducted in order to analyse differences between skeletal indicators of scurvy in children younger than 1 year and older age categories, revealing no significant association between age and the presence of skeletal indicators of scurvy (df=1, N=47, one-tailed, $p = 0.076$). Although the differences did not reach statistical significance, the data suggest a weak tendency toward a higher prevalence of scurvy indicators in the youngest age category.

In order to analyse whether the presence of skeletal indicators of scurvy is associated with stunted longitudinal bone growth a Chi-square test was conducted to examine whether deviations in skeletal growth differed between individuals with and without scurvy.

Table 31. Longitudinal growth deviations and skeletal indicators of scurvy.

Growth deviations	Scurvy absent	Scurvy present	Total
No deviations	4	5	9
Slower growth	9	9	18
Faster growth	1	1	2
Total	14	15	29

The analysis included 29 individuals, and 15 (51.72%) individuals exhibited skeletal indicators of scurvy, while 14 (48.28%) did not. The results showed no statistically significant difference in growth stunting between the individuals with and without scurvy ($\chi^2 = 0.077$, df=2, N=29, $p = 0.962$). These results suggest that the presence of scurvy was not associated with deviations in skeletal growth within this sample.

6. 5. Infectious diseases

6. 5. 1. Presence of pathological changes consistent with tuberculosis infection

Out of the total sample of 74 individuals whose skeletal remains were analyzed, 13 individuals had preserved thoracic and lumbar vertebrae, allowing for a macroscopic examination of the vertebral bodies and the identification of lytic lesions on their surfaces, following the protocol proposed by Steckel et al., (2005).

Lytic lesions potentially associated with active tuberculosis were in 6 out of 13 individuals for whom analysis of thoracic and lumbar vertebrae was possible. The individuals displaying lytic lesions were buried in graves marked as Ostojićevo 14, 18, 77, 134, 205, and 275. Among the six individuals exhibiting vertebral lesions, ribs were preserved in a fragmented condition in five cases (In the case of the individual buried in grave 134, ribs were not available for analysis). However, no pathological changes or lesions suggestive of tuberculosis were detected on these elements.

Table 32. Presence of lytic lesions among individuals with preserved thoracic and lumbar vertebra.

Presence or absence of vertebral lesions	Number of individuals (n)	Percentage (%)
Individuals with preserved thoracic and lumbar vertebrae (analyzed)	13	100.00%
Individuals with lytic lesions	6	46.15%
Individuals without lytic lesions	7	53.85%

The proportion of individuals exhibiting lytic lesions potentially associated with tuberculosis is relatively high, with 46.15% of analyzed vertebrae showing pathological changes. The notable prevalence of vertebral lesions in the analysed young individuals suggests that the population may have experienced high exposure to tuberculosis even during early childhood.

Among the 13 individuals whose vertebrae were examined, biological sex could be established for 11 individuals through the analysis of sex-specific peptides, revealing 7 females and 4 males.

Among the individuals with identified lesions, three were female and two were male, while for one individual, sex determination based on peptide analysis was not possible due to the absence of dentition in the available material.

Table 33. Distribution of vertebral lesions by biological sex of individuals.

Biological sex	Number of individuals without lesions	Number of individuals with lesion	Percentage of individuals with lesions (%)
Female	4	3	42.86%

Male	2	2	50.00%
Total	6	5	45.45%

In this small sample, vertebral lesions are observed in both sexes, but Fisher’s Exact Test indicates no statistically significant association between biological sex and presence of lesions (one-tailed $p = 0.652$, $N = 11$, $df = 1$).

Regarding the age distribution of individuals with identified lesions, two individuals were younger than one year, and one individual belonged to the 1–5-year age category. Two individuals with lesions were in the 5–10-year age group. No individuals with vertebral lesions were observed in the 10–15-year category, while one individual belonged to the 15–20-year age group. The majority of individuals (five of six recorded cases) are under 10 years of age (83.33%). It should be noted that the 10–15-year age group is underrepresented, with only one individual in the entire sample of subadults from the Ostojićevo necropolis.

The obtained data might suggest that younger children in this population were particularly vulnerable, when exposed to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Previous research on the modern population has shown that younger children, especially under the 5 years of age are more prone to developing tuberculosis, which is associated with an immaturity of the immune system and limited ability to contain primary infection with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. In children under five years of age, disseminated and extrapulmonary form of a disease, including skeletal form of tuberculosis, occur more frequently than in older children and adults (Marais et al., 2004; Kampmann et al., 2015)

Figure 18. Age distribution of subadult individuals with vertebral lesions.

6. 5. 2. Potential Indicators of Malaria in the Subadult Sample from Ostojićevo

Following Smith-Guzmán (2015), who demonstrated a correlation between malaria and five skeletal indicators: cribra orbitalia (CO), cribra humeri (HC), cribra femora (FC), spinal porosity (SP), and periostitis (P) in modern Ugandan populations, the subadult skeletal material from the Ostojićevo necropolis was analyzed for macroscopic pathological changes indicative of malaria. For differential diagnosis, the following formula was applied: $C_i = 1$ if $\{(CO \text{ or } HC \text{ or } FC = 1) \text{ and } (SP \text{ or } P = 1)\}$; else

$C_i = 0$. Here, C_i represents the classification of an individual as a potential case of malaria. This approach allowed the identification of individuals in whom the observed changes support a potential diagnosis of malaria.

Pathological skeletal changes indicative of malaria could be analyzed in 30 subadult individuals. Of the total analyzed skeletal remains, 21 (70%) individuals exhibited skeletal manifestations that could indicate potential infestation from the genus *Plasmodium*.

Table 34. Prevalence of skeletal manifestations indicative of malaria infestation in subadult individuals from Ostojićevo.

Skeletal manifestations of malaria	Number of individuals (n)	Percentages
Present	21	70.00%
Absent	9	30.00%
Total	30	100.00%

Skeletal manifestations potentially associated with malaria infestation were observed in both sexes. Among males (n = 14), 8 individuals (57.1%) exhibited these manifestations, whereas 6 individuals (42.9%) did not. Among females (n = 13), 10 individuals (76.9%) showed the manifestations, while 3 (23.1%) did not.

Table 35. Sex based distribution of skeletal manifestations indicative of malaria at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Sex	Present (%)	Absent (%)	Total
Male	8 (57.1%)	6 (42.9%)	14
Female	10 (76.9%)	3 (23.1%)	13
Not Estimated	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	3
Total	21	9	30

Statistical analysis using a Chi-square test (excluding individuals with undetermined sex) revealed no significant difference between males and females ($\chi^2 = 1.18$, $df = 1$, $N=27$, $p = 0.276$), indicating that the presence of these skeletal manifestations was similarly distributed across sexes in this sample.

In terms of age, individuals showing skeletal manifestations potentially linked to malarial infestation ranged from the 38th week of gestation to 25 years in the analyzed sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Table 36. Age distribution of subadult individuals with skeletal manifestations linked to malaria at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with skeletal manifestation of malaria	Percentage of individuals skeletal manifestation of malaria (%)
<1	10	9	90.00%
1–5	5	3	60.00%
5–10	7	6	85.7%
10–15	-	-	-
15–20	5	2	40.00%
>20	3	1	33.3%
Total	30	21	70.00%

Skeletal manifestations potentially associated with malarial infestation were recorded across all age groups at the Ostojićevo necropolis. Individuals younger than one year exhibited the highest proportion of skeletal manifestations (90.0%), followed by those aged 5–10 years (85.7%) and 1–5 years (60.0%). The frequency decreased among older individuals, reaching 40.0% in the 15–20-year group and 33.3% in adults over 20 years of age. It should be noted that the 10–15-year age category is underrepresented in the overall sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis. When grouped into broader age categories (<1 year, 1–10 years, and >10 years), statistical analysis using the Chi-square test revealed a significant difference in the distribution of skeletal manifestations between age groups ($\chi^2 = 5.07$, $df = 2$, $N=30$, $p = 0.048$), indicating a higher prevalence among the youngest individuals.

Figure 19. Skeletal manifestations of malaria age distribution in the Ostojićevo necropolis sample.

A high prevalence of individuals exhibiting skeletal manifestations consistent with malaria infestation was observed, reaching 70% of the analyzed sample. The youngest age group, up to 5 years, showed

the highest prevalence of these skeletal changes. In contrast, no statistically significant difference was found between boys and girls regarding the presence of these manifestations.

6. 5. 3. *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES)

Out of the total sample of 74 individuals, it was possible to analyse the endocranial surface in 59 individuals. Of the 59 individuals whose endocranial surfaces were available for analysis, *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES) was observed in 5 individuals, representing 8.47% of the total sample.

Figure 20. *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES) observed on both the left and right parietal bones of a 1.5-year-old boy (Grave Ostojićevo 163).

Table 37. Frequency of *Serpense endocrania symmetrica* (SES) in the analyzed sample at Ostojićevo necropolis.

Sample category	Number of individuals (n)	Percentages (%)
Endocranial surfaces analyzed	59	100.00%
Individuals with SES	5	8.47%
Individual without SES	54	91.53%

The graves in question, where the subadult individuals with recorded SES were interred, are designated as Ostojićevo 1, 24, 73, 163, and 195.

Among the five individuals exhibiting evidence of *Serpens Endocrania Symmetrica* (SES), biological sex was successfully determined in four cases, three males and one female. All affected individuals belong to the youngest age categories, with the estimated age at death ranging from approximately 38–40 gestational weeks to 1.5 years, indicating the manifestation of this condition predominantly in perinatal and early infancy stages.

Table38. Sex and age distribution of subadult individuals with *Serpens Endocrania Symmetrica* (SES) from the Ostojićevo Necropolis.

Grave No	Biological Sex	Estimated Age	Presence of SES	Percentages (known sex) (%)
Ostojićevo 1	Female	6-7.5 months	Yes	25.00%
Ostojićevo 24	-	38-40 gestational weeks	Yes	-
Ostojićevo 73	Male	7.5 months	Yes	25.00%
Ostojićevo 163	Male	1.5 year	Yes	25.00%
Ostojićevo 195	Male	10.5-12 months	Yes	25.00%
Total	-	-	5/59	100.00%

Within the sample of individuals exhibiting the *Serpense endocrania symmetrica* (SES), for whom the biological sex was determined, males constitute the majority (75%), while females represent 25 %. Although male children are somewhat more represented in the sample, the small sample size does not allow for a definitive conclusion regarding the possible frequency of this condition among boys and girls.

Due to the limited number of individuals exhibiting SES (n = 5) within the sample from Ostojićevo necropolis, statistical analyses were restricted to descriptive measures.

The correlation between *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES) and potential indicators of tuberculosis infection could not be assessed, as individuals exhibiting SES lacked preserved skeletal elements, particularly thoracic and lumbar vertebrae necessary of confirming or refusing the presence of skeletal manifestation of tuberculosis.

The presence of scurvy related lesions was observed in 25 individuals of the total sample. Of the five individuals exhibiting *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES), four (16% of the sample with scurvy related skeletal changes) also presented the skeletal changes characteristic of the nutritional deficiency scurvy. In one individual (Grave Ostojićevo 73) skeletal preservation was insufficient to reliably assess the presence or absence of lesions indicative of scurvy. The co-occurrence of SES and scurvy-related lesions suggests a possible association between these pathological changes, consistent with the observations of Abegg et al. (2020), who proposed that SES may represent part of a broader physiological response to nutritional deficiencies and metabolic stress in early childhood. However because of the small sample size, this correlation should be interpreted with caution.

6. 5. 4. Mastoiditis in subadults at the Ostojićevo necropolis

The total sample of 36 individuals was analysed, in whom one or both temporal bones, including mastoid processus was preserved. In 7 (19.04 %) out of 36 cases lesions on the surface of the mastoid process, with or without an associated periosteal reaction, were observed.

Table 39. Frequency of mastoid process lesions in the subadult sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Observation	Number of individuals	Percentages (%)
Total subadult individuals analysed	36	100.00%
Individuals with mastoid processus lesions/periosteal reaction	7	19.04%
Individuals without mastoid processus lesions/periosteal reaction	29	80.6 %

Of these 7 individuals with mastoid processus lesions, three were male (42.9 %), four were female (57.1 %). The age of individuals exhibiting changes on the mastoid process ranged from 10 to 25 years. Overall, this data emphasizes that mastoid process lesions affected both sexes and a wide age range.

Table40. Age, sex, and sex distribution of subadult individuals with mastoid process lesions (Ostojićevo Necropolis).

Grave number	Age	Biological sex
Ostojićevo 102	16.5 years	Female
Ostojićevo 104	15.5 years	Female
Ostojićevo 108 A	25 years	Male
Ostojićevo 179	6.5 years	Male
Ostojićevo 218	10.5 months	Female
Ostojićevo 245	24.78 years	Male
Ostojićevo 276	5.5-6 years	Female

Figure 21. Lesions on the Mastoid Process of the Right Temporal bone. Child aged 5.5–6 years (Grave Ostojićevo 276).

6. 6. Dental pathologies

6. 6. 1. Enamel hypoplasia

Enamel hypoplasia was analysed in a sample of 42 individuals. In 7 individuals whose dentitions were preserved, it was not possible to observe enamel hypoplasia due to poor preservation and discoloration of the enamel surface. Linear enamel hypoplasia was observed in 8 subadult individuals (19.05%) and no enamel hypoplasia was detected in 34 individuals (80.95%).

Table 41. Prevalence of enamel hypoplasia.

Category	Number of individuals (n)	Percentages (%)
With enamel hypoplasia	8	19.05%
Without enamel hypoplasia	34	80.95%
Total	42	100.0%

Enamel hypoplasia was observed in both sexes, with a higher prevalence among males. Of the 22 females in the sample, 3 individuals exhibited hypoplasia, corresponding to 13.64%, whereas 5 out of 20 males showed hypoplasia, representing 25% of the male sample.

Table 42. Sex distribution of enamel hypoplasia.

Sex	Hypoplasia present (n, %)	Hypoplasia absent (n, %)	Total
Male	3 (13.64%)	19 (86.4%)	22
Female	5 (25.0%)	15 (75.0%)	20
Total	8	34	42

To assess whether the observed difference in enamel hypoplasia prevalence between sexes was statistically significant, Fisher's exact two-tailed analysis was performed. The results indicated no statistically significant difference between males and females (df=1, N=42, two-tailed, $p = 0.445$; one-tailed, $p=0.294$), suggesting that, although hypoplasia appeared more frequent in males (males-25%; females-13.6%), this difference could be due to chance.

The prevalence of enamel hypoplasia varied across age groups, with the highest proportion observed in the 5–10 years group (44.4%), followed by 1–5 years (25.0%) and less than 1 year old (6.3%). No cases were recorded in individuals aged 10–15, 15–20, or more than 20 years old.

Table 43. Age distribution of subadult individuals with enamel hypoplasia at the Ostojicevo necropolis.

Age	Total sample	Individuals with enamel hypoplasia	Percentage of individuals with EH within Age group (%)
<1	16	1	6.3%
1–5	8	2	25.0%
5–10	9	4	44.4%
10–15	0	0	-
15–20	6	0	0%
>20	3	0	0%
Total	42	8	19.05%

To evaluate whether the occurrence of enamel hypoplasia was associated with age, a Chi-square test of independence was performed, with Monte Carlo, one-sided approximation used to account for small expected frequencies. The Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 8.45$, df=4, N=42, $p = 0.074$), indicated that the

differences in hypoplasia prevalence across age groups were not statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

6. 6. 2. Dental caries

Dental caries were examined in a total of 46 individuals, with only a single case observed in the entire sample, indicating an overall very low prevalence (2.2%).

The individual from grave Ostojićevo 89, was a male, estimated to be 1–1.5 years of age, exhibited a single dental caries lesion. The lesion was located on the buccal surface of tooth 75 and was oval in shape, measuring 0.98×0.67 mm. Individual Ostojićevo 89, except caries lesions that were observed showed the nonspecific indicators of stress such as *Cribra orbitalia*, porotic hyperostosis, and skeletal indicators of scurvy.

6. 7. Prevalence of pathological changes on skeletal remains in total subadult sample at the Ostojićevo necropolis

In 52 subadult individuals (70.3%) pathological changes were observed on skeletal remains. In 22 subadult individuals there were no skeletal changes observed (29.7%). The absence of skeletal indicators of past diseases in the Ostojićevo sample does not necessarily signify a good health, but in the majority of cases a poor skeletal preservation, and in some instances potential pathological conditions that did not leave traces on the skeletons.

In order to analyse differences in the frequency of skeletal pathologies in male and female subadults in a total of 49 individuals of estimated sex total count of observed skeletal pathologies was estimated. Maximal count was 13 skeletal changes or indicators of certain diseases including: SES and other nonspecific meningeal reactions, mastoiditis, *Cribra orbitalia*, *Cribra humera*, *Cribra femora*, porotic hyperostosis, periostitis, skeletal indicators of scurvy, rickets, tuberculosis, malaria and dental pathologies (hypoplasia and caries).

A Mann-Whitney U test was performed to examine the differences in the number of pathological changes in boys and girls at the Ostojićevo necropolis. The sample consisted of 49 individuals in total (25 females and 24 males). The mean rank for females (MR=25.54) was slightly higher than in males (MR=24.44) suggesting a marginally greater occurrence of skeletal pathologies in females than in males. However the difference between groups was minimal. As the p-value was greater than 0.05 (U=286.50, Z =-0.27, p=.785), the observed differences between males and females didn't reach statistical significance, suggesting that skeletal pathologies were present in both groups at the similar extent.

Figure 22. Boxplot displaying distribution of skeletal pathologies in female (N=25) and male (N=24) subadult individuals at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

6. 8. Funerary recipients

Of the 103 burial vessels recorded during the excavation of the Ostojićevo site, a total of 87 vessels, preserved to varying degrees, are currently available for analysis. A number of vessels are in a fragmented state, which makes it impossible to directly measure all dimensions included in this study. Consequently, vessel volume could be reconstructed for 46 vessels, while vessel height was measured for 48 vessels.

The vessel with the largest volume measured 61,500 cm³ (Grave Ostojićevo 195), whereas the smallest vessel had a volume of 3,550 cm³ (Grave Ostojićevo 47). The tallest vessel measures 62 cm in height (Grave Ostojićevo 195), whereas the shortest vessel is only 22.5 cm high (Grave Ostojićevo 47). Across these ranges, vessels displayed substantial variability with respect to both their volume and height.

Table44. Funerary vessel capacity and height.

Grave number	Funerary vessel capacity (cm ³)	Funerary vessel height (cm)
Ostojicevo 1	16700	37.5
Ostojicevo 2	14450	38.3
Ostojicevo 10	10504	34.1
Ostojicevo 11	-	32.5
Ostojicevo 12	12010	36.4
Ostojicevo 13	16900	41.2
Ostojicevo 15	8550	29.3
Ostojicevo 16	12553	29.5
Ostojicevo 20	12000	32.2
Ostojicevo 22	10013	37.6
Ostojicevo 24	18170	34.5
Ostojicevo 26	32400	49.1
Ostojicevo 27	14653	39.0
Ostojicevo 32	15470	39.5
Ostojicevo 33	15075	41.0
Ostojicevo 37	14915	39.2
Ostojicevo 45	8000	31.0
Ostojicevo 47	3550	22.5
Ostojicevo 55	-	53.5
Ostojicevo 61	4750	26.2
Ostojicevo 70	10350	32.4
Ostojicevo 73	30556	48.0
Ostojicevo 74	18250	39.0

Ostojicevo 76	25000	46.5
Ostojicevo 77	30556	48.0
Ostojicevo 83	5050	25.4
Ostojicevo 125	14950	39.6
Ostojicevo 132	9410	23.4
Ostojicevo 149	17300	43.7
Ostojicevo 163	18700	37.3
Ostojicevo 172	6750	28.4
Ostojicevo 173	36000	56.6
Ostojicevo 178	8000	33.4
Ostojicevo 187	10405	33.2
Ostojicevo 195	61500	62.0
Ostojicevo 200	24550	49.0
Ostojicevo 206	18450	35.2
Ostojicevo 239	10250	31.8
Ostojicevo 240	12700	30.2
Ostojicevo 243	14050	34.5
Ostojicevo 247	18325	42.6
Ostojicevo 249	16950	39.4
Ostojicevo 252	12000	32.2
Ostojicevo 253	9950	32.0
Ostojicevo 259	10650	34.0
Ostojicevo 261	16100	40.4
Ostojicevo 267	7100	28.5

Figure 23. A histogram that illustrates the capacity of funerary containers at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Figure 24. A histogram that illustrates the height of the funerary vessels at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

6. 8. 1. Funerary vessel capacity

Of the 103 vessels found at the Ostojićevo necropolis, 46 were fully reconstructed, enabling volume measurements. The skeletons of 24 children buried in vessels with measured volumes were sufficiently preserved and accessible for analysis. The children from the preserved and reconstructed vessels ranged in age from 30 gestational weeks to 4.5 years.

In eight individuals from the preserved vessels, stature could be reconstructed from long bone measurements, enabling an evaluation of the potential correlation between vessel volume and child height.

Table 45. Height of individuals and vessel volume.

Individual	Vessel volume (cm ³)	Height of children (cm)
Ostojićevo 1	16700	49.91
Ostojićevo 2	14450	64.39
Ostojićevo 12	12010	51.83

Ostojićevo 15	8550	50.49
Ostojićevo 20	12000	52.12
Ostojićevo 24	18170	56.86
Ostojićevo 77	52900	97.97
Ostojićevo 195	61500	69.16

A Pearson correlation indicated a strong positive and statistically significant association between vessel volume and child height ($r = 0.780$, $N = 8$, two-tailed $p = 0.02$), and it demonstrates that taller children tended to be buried in larger vessels.

Figure 25. Boxplot displaying correlation between vessel volume and stature of children.

6. 8. 2. Funerary vessel height

Of the 103 recorded funerary vessels at the Ostojićevo necropolis during the excavations a total of 48 vessel degrees of preservation was sufficient for measuring vessel height. The skeletons of 25 children buried in vessels with measured vessel height were sufficiently preserved and accessible for analysis. The children from the measured vessels ranged in age from 30 gestational weeks to 4.5 years. The stature of children was reconstructed in eight subadult individuals.

Table 46. Height of individuals and vessel height.

Individual	Vessel height (cm)	Height of children (cm)
Ostojicevo 1	37.5	49.91
Ostojicevo 2	38.3	64.39
Ostojicevo 12	36.4	51.83
Ostojicevo 15	29.3	50.49
Ostojicevo 20	32.2	52.12
Ostojicevo 24	34.5	56.86
Ostojicevo 77	61.9	97.97
Ostojicevo 195	62	69.16

A Pearson correlation test was conducted to examine the relationship between children's estimated stature and the height of the ceramic vessels in which they were buried. The results showed a strong positive and statistically significant correlation between stature and vessel height (two-tailed, $r = 0.841$, $N = 8$, $p = 0.009$). Correlation suggests that taller children tended to be buried in taller vessels.

Figure 26. Boxplot displaying correlation between vessel height and stature of children.

6. 8. 3. Funerary vessel types and sex of subadults

All recorded vessel types (six types) were produced in various dimensions, with variations in height, rim diameter and vessel capacity. Differences were also recorded in forms, type of handles and decorations. Based on these distinctions the following types of funerary vessel were recorded: A, B, C, D, E, F.

For the purpose of typological analysis 87 out of 103 excavated burial vessels were sufficiently preserved and suitable for the study. The biological sex was established for 23 subadults for whom funerary vessel typology could also be established.

Both sexes were represented in the sample, of 23 individuals buried in vessels 13 were males (56.5%), and 10 were females (43.5%).

Table 47. Funerary vessel types and biological sex of subadults.

Sex	Vessel type	A	B	C	D	E	F	Total
Boys		7	1	2	2	1	0	13
Girls		7	0	0	3	0	0	10
Total		14	1	2	5	1	0	23

A chi-square test was conducted to examine the association between sex of individuals and type of burial receptacles. The test indicated no statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 3.875$, $df = 4$, $N=23$, $p = 0.423$), suggesting that the distribution of vessel types does not differ across the sexes.

The distribution of funerary vessel types across sexes was examined using Fisher’s Exact Test. Tests were performed for each vessel type (comparing presence vs. absence of a given vessel type between boys and girls) ($N=23$). The results show no statistical significance association for any vessel type.

Table 48. Fisher’s exact test results (vessel type association with biological sex).

Vessel type	p-value
A	0.669
B	1.000
C	0.486
D	0.618
E	1.000
F	1.000

Since all p -values are greater than 0.05, no statistically significant relationship was found between the funerary vessel type and the biological sex of subadult individuals in this sample. Also based on obtained data, there is no clear trend suggesting that one sex was preferentially buried in a particular vessel type.

6. 8. 4. Age structure of subadult individuals inside and outside the funerary recipients

The age structure of individuals buried in vessels and those buried outside of them, and whether there are significant differences between these two groups when considering the age of the subadult individuals was investigated, using a sample of 74 individuals whose skeletons were available for analysis. For 72 individuals of the entire analysed sample, and of known age, it was possible to determine the manner of burial, specifically whether they were buried inside or outside the funerary recipient.

Out of the total number of 72 subadult individuals, 44 (61.1%) were buried in funerary containers, while 28 (38.9%) individuals were buried outside of funerary containers.

Table 49. The age structure of individuals inside and outside the vessels.

Age groups	With burial vessels	Without burial vessels	Total
Less than 1 year	38 (52.8%)	4 (5.6%)	42 (58.3%)
1-5 years	4 (5.6%)	3 (4.2%)	7 (9.7%)

5-10 years	2 (2.8%)	9 (12.5%)	11 (15.3%)
More than 10 years	0 (0%)	12 (16.7%)	12 (16.7%)
Total	44 (61.1%)	28 (38.9%)	72 (100.0%)

Individuals buried in burial vessels show an age range spanning from newborn to 8.5 years, with the majority being under 1 year old. Children under one year of age were 86% of those buried in vessels, with a relatively small proportion of children from 1-5 years of age (14%).

Burial in vessels ceases around the age of 6, with the exception of one individual (Grave Ostojićevo 18) aged 8.5 years, while children older than 8.5 years are buried exclusively outside of funerary recipients. Burials without vessels display a much wider age range from newborn to 25 years of age. A small portion of those buried without vessels were younger than 5 years (25%), while the majority (75%) were more than 5 years old. This pattern demonstrates that the non-vessel burials were predominantly reserved for older groups of subadults.

Figure 27. Boxplot representing a range of individuals buried inside and outside of funerary recipients.

A Mann–Whitney U test showed a statistically significant difference in age between individuals buried with and without funerary vessels ($U = 102.00$, $Z = -5.98$, $p < .001$). Individuals buried without vessels

had significantly higher ages (Mean Rank = 54.86) compared to those buried in vessels (Mean Rank = 24.82).

Table 50. Mann–Whitney U test results for age by burial type.

Burial type	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks
Without vessel	28	54.86	1536.00
With vessel	44	24.82	1092.00
Total	72		

Table 51. Test statistics.

Test	Age
Mann-Whitney U	102.000
Wilcoxon W	1092.000
Z	-5.979
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

This indicates that vessel burials were predominantly associated with much younger individuals in the Ostojićevo subadult sample, while older children (Older than 8.5) were buried exclusively without vessels.

6. 9. Grave goods in subadult at the Ostojićevo necropolis

The presence and number of grave goods were analyzed in a total of 74 individuals whose skeletal remains were available for study. The analysis examined whether the number of grave goods in individual graves was associated with sex, age of the individuals, or the presence or absence of a burial container.

In a total of 49 individuals (66.2%), no grave goods were recorded accompanying the child burials, while at least one grave item or more was found in 25 individuals (33.8%).

Table 52. Number of grave goods by sex.

Sex	No grave goods	1 item	2 items	3 items	4 items	Total
Male	13 (50.0%)	7 (26.9%)	0 (0.0%)	1(3.8%)	1(3.8%)	22
Female	17 (56.7%)	8 (26.7%)	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	27

Not estimated	19 (76.0%)	4 (16.0%)	2 (8.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	25
Total	49 (66.2%)	19 (25.7%)	3 (4.1%)	2 (2.7%)	1 (1.4%)	74

A Chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine the relationship between biological sex of children and the number of grave goods among the analyzed individuals. The observed distribution of grave goods by sex is presented in Table 55. The results indicated no statistically significant association between sex and grave goods ($\chi^2(8)=7.25$, $p=0.51$, $df=8$, $N=74$). Expected frequencies under the null hypothesis are shown in Table 56.

Table 53. Expected frequencies of grave goods by sex under the null hypothesis.

Sex	No grave goods	1 item	2 items	3 items	4 items
Male	14.57	5.65	0.89	0.59	0.30
Female	17.88	6.93	1.09	0.73	0.36
Not estimated	16.55	6.42	1.01	0.68	0.34

These results suggest that, in this sample, the presence or number of grave goods does not differ by sex. In order to analyse the relation between age at death and number of grave goods, grave items were counted in a subadult sample of 74 individuals of determined age. It was observed that infants under the age of one year, in most cases, were buried without any additional grave goods (33; 78.6%).

Table 54. Observed number of grave goods by age group.

Age group	No grave goods	1 item	2 items	3 items	4 items	Total
Less than 1 year	33 (78.6%)	8 (19.0%)	1 (2.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	42
1-10 years	10 (45.5%)	6 (27.3%)	1 (4.5%)	2 (9.1%)	1 (4.5%)	22
More than 10 years	6 (46.2%)	5 (38.5%)	1 (7.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	13
Total	49	19	3	2	1	74

To examine the relation between age and a number of grave items in more detail, a Chi-square test of independence was conducted.

The results showed no statistically significant association between age category and the number of grave goods ($\chi^2(8, N=74)=13.27$, $p=0.10$). Nevertheless, a clear trend is evident in which older children (1–10 years and more than 10 years) were more frequently buried with one or more grave

goods compared to infants. This pattern may suggest a gradual increase in the social or symbolic status of the child with age.

6. 9. 1. The association between the quantity of grave goods and general health status

The number of grave goods in individual burials was compared with the frequency of pathological changes in children to investigate a possible association between richer grave inventories and better health status. The analysis was conducted on a total sample of 74 individuals.

Pearson correlation analysis revealed a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.133$, $N = 74$, $p = 0.260$), which was not statistically significant, indicating no linear association between the quantity of grave goods and the occurrence of pathological changes. Similarly, Spearman's rank correlation showed a weak positive correlation ($\rho = 0.083$, $N = 74$, $p = 0.482$), also not statistically significant.

Figure 28. Boxplot representing a pathologies distribution by number of grave goods in subadults from the Ostojićevo.

Table55. Pathological changes and number of grave goods in subadult burials at Ostojićevo necropolis (N = 74).

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Stn. Deviation
Number of pathologies	74	0	10	2.54	2.544
Number of grave goods	74	0	4	.47	.815

Table56. Correlation analysis.

Test	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	N
Pearson	0.133	0.260	74
Spearman's test	0.083	0.482	74

These results suggest that the number of grave goods in children's burials at the Ostojićevo necropolis does not correspond to differences in overall health status

6. 10. Burial orientation of adults and subadults at the Ostojićevo necropolis

The burial orientation of children of known biological sex were analysed on a total sample of 45 subadult and 43 adult individuals. Four different burial orientations were observed in the sample: North-South, South-North, East-West and West-East.

Table 57. Burial orientation of adult individuals of estimated biological sex at the Ostojićevo necropolis during the Middle Bronze Age.

Sex	North-South	South-North	East-West	West-East	Total
Male	9 (60.0%)	3 (20.0%)	3 (20.0%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (100.0%)
Female	2 (7.1%)	24 (85.7%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (7.1%)	28 (100.0%)
Total	11 (25.6%)	27 (62.8%)	3 (7.0%)	2 (4.7%)	43 (100.0%)

Table 58. Burial orientation of subadult individuals of estimated biological sex at the Ostojićevo necropolis during the Middle Bronze Age.

Sex	North-South	South-North	East-West	West-East	Total
Boys	15 (62.5%)	2 (8.3%)	5 (20.8%)	2 (8.3%)	24 (100.0%)

Girls	6 (28.6%)	13 (61.9%)	1 (4.8%)	1 (4.8%)	21 (100.0%)
Total	21 (46.7%)	15 (33.3%)	6 (13.3%)	3 (6.7%)	45 (100.0%)

The results showed that dominant and equally represented orientations are north-south and south-north in both children and adults. In addition to these, east-west and west-east orientations are also present, or the aforementioned orientations with certain deviations. The same orientations of skeletons are observed in adult individuals at the necropolis.

In order to analyse association of burial orientation and biological sex in children and adults Chi-square test of independence was performed. The analysis of burial orientation at the Ostojićevo necropolis reveals a significant association between sex and orientation in both adults and subadults. Adult males were predominantly oriented North–South (60%), whereas females were mainly oriented south-north (85.7%) ($\chi^2 (3) = 24.06, p < 0.000, N=43, df=3$). Similarly, subadult boys (N = 24) were most often oriented north-south (62.5%), while subadult girls (N = 21) were most frequently oriented south-north (61.9%) ($\chi^2 (3) = 14.79, p = 0.002, N=45, df=3$). These patterns remain statistically significant when low frequency east-west orientations are combined to meet chi-square assumptions. Overall, the data suggest a consistent sex-based pattern in burial orientation across age groups, with males tending toward north-south and females toward south-north.

This demonstrates a significant association between specific burial orientation and the biological sex of individuals. Since similar orientation patterns are observed in children, including those buried in vessels, we can conclude that sex-specific burial practices were present from the earliest stages of life.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Paleopathological profiles of young girls and boys at the necropolis in Ostojićevo reveal numerous details about the daily lives of children within the settlement, whose precise location remains unknown. Everyday life in prehistory, as well as today, wasn't simple and communities faced numerous challenges living in their environment. One of the major challenges was illness and suffering. Deprived of proper medicines and medical care that could have helped the sick, disease progressed unhindered in their natural course and the youngest members of the community, who were the focus of this analysis, required long-term care. In the end, this struggle and care, in the case of our subadult sample, sadly culminated in the lethal outcome.

Even before all things began, children could have been born stillborn, have a lower birth weight, or, for various reasons, experience slower development and reduced growth.

7. 1. Age at death of children

Analysis of the age structure of children from Ostojićevo revealed a disproportionately high number of individuals under one year of age. Individuals under 1 year of age, including perinatal and neonates, accounted for 42 individuals (56.75%) of the sample, indicating a high proportion of very young children. The age categories range from 1–10 years category included in total 20 individuals (27.09%). Individuals older than 10 years totaled 12 (16.28%), representing older children and adolescents. This categorization highlights the predominance of perinates, neonates and youngest infants in the necropolis, while older subadults and adolescents were comparatively less represented.

Neonatal and infant mortality during the Bronze Age was generally exceptionally high. For instance, in the Armenoi necropolis near Rethymnon (Greece), child mortality reached 69%, comparable to contemporary infant mortality rates in West Africa according to World Health Organisation reports. This high mortality can be attributed to increased population densities, leading to greater exposure to pathogens (Mc George, 2011). A similar pattern of mortality among the youngest age categories is also observed at the Ostojićevo necropolis, which prompted a search for the causes of such high mortality among the youngest individuals.

1. 1. 1. Live and Stillbirth at Ostojićevo necropolis

The treatment of stillborn children in contemporary cultures, as well as we can conclude based on ethnological sources, is known to vary considerably, being conditioned by diverse cultural and religious practices (Ayebare et al., 2021). What differs from one case to another and from one community to another is funerary right, and whether the burial was conducted swiftly and anonymously, or in accordance with rites similar to those intended for adults or live born children, performed under the child's given name and family name and with a presence of relatives (Arach et al., 2023). The place of interment also varies. There are few reasons why stillborn children were treated differently in death. Foremost is the question whether they were regarded as full members of the community, as individuals who had never passed the transitional rites that society deemed essential (Chebet et al.,; Forth 2025). Other factors may include high child mortality, the stigma surrounding stillbirth, or sheer fear (Crow 2020). Funerary rituals also serve to inscribe deceased into the collective memory of the group, perhaps one reason why those who had never truly lived were excluded. In the archaeological context, it is often possible to identify an individual as a newborn, but not to determine whether the child was live-born or stillborn.

One of the important questions that this study seeks to address is how society during the Middle Bronze Age at the Ostojićevo necropolis treated stillborn and live-born children. The distinctive feature of the

Ostojićevo necropolis during this period lies in the fact that children. Beginning from the age of newborns, were buried within the perimeter of the necropolis alongside adults, whereas the funerary rite reserved for children younger than seven years involved interment within a ceramic vessel. In total, 103 individuals under the age of seven were interred following placement within ceramic containers, whereas older subadults and adult individuals were deposited directly in the ground without the use of funerary vessels. Preterm and potentially stillborn infants at the Ostojićevo necropolis were also treated in the same manner as older children, being carefully buried in funerary vessels. This practice represents a distinctive burial tradition, unparalleled during this period in the region, and it is also novel when compared with the older Early Bronze Age horizon (Girić 1995; Girić 1996) at the Ostojićevo necropolis, where children were not interred in vessels and no individuals younger than 18 months were buried inside the necropolis's perimeter.

The age distribution of children indicates a predominance of infant and early childhood mortality. This suggests that the first years of life were the most critical period for survival in the Ostojićevo community. But were all the newborns in the necropolis actually live-born, and did they have any chance of survival from the very beginning?

Regarding the potentially stillborn and definitively preterm individuals at the Ostojićevo necropolis, it can be concluded that, like other individuals, they were interred within the necropolis perimeter.

The results of statistical analysis indicate that among the youngest individuals interred, both boys and girls are represented, and that in the case of potentially stillborn individuals, both sexes are equally represented. Therefore we can conclude that the biological sex of newborn children did not influence the decision whether they should be interred inside the necropolis.

Similar to other very young individuals, the potentially stillborn males and females were interred in burial receptacles. Male individuals were buried in the expected male orientation (north-south). In contrast, one female individual was buried in the opposite, typically male, orientation. Given the very small sample size, no definitive conclusions can be drawn regarding whether a distinct funerary norm was applied for stillborn female children or whether a different burial practice was followed in this case.

Preterm birth or stillbirth, therefore, does not seem to have affected the funerary ritual or set these individuals apart from other children. They were regarded and interred with the same care and attention, reflecting the community's respect and concern for every child, regardless of their brief existence in this world, carefully extending funerary rituals to them as well.

7. 2. Sex distribution of subadults at Ostojićevo

The sex distribution of subadults from the Ostojićevo necropolis reveals patterns in survivorship and mortality in those two biological groups. Male infants and young children (under 5 years of age) are slightly more numerous in the sample, suggesting higher male vulnerability during the early life phases. This pattern is commonly observed in prehistoric populations, due to biological fragility and susceptibility to disease and nutritional stress (Lewis 2006). In contrast females are more represented in older childhood and adolescence (5–20 years), which may reflect higher mortality in later childhood phases and early adolescence. The above observation can be made with some reservation, because if birth sex ratios are roughly equal and male children experience higher early mortality, the surviving population in older age groups will tend to be increasingly female. The trend observed in female samples could result from a combination of different biological factors: rapid growth, disease susceptibility, hormonal changes and nutritional stress. In this stage of late childhood and on the threshold of adulthood, socio-cultural factors such as increased workload and early pregnancies may also affect survivorship in females (Mays 2010). Overall, these patterns indicate that both biological and environmental factors influenced survival in the subadult population, with early life being

particularly critical for males, while later childhood and adolescence may have posed greater risks for females.

7. 3. Diseases, Trauma, and the Growth and Development of Children

In 52 individuals (70.3%) pathological changes were observed on the skeletal remains. The absence of pathological changes in the remaining 22 individuals can be explained not only by the lack of disease, but also by the possibility that the course of illness was too short to leave visible traces on the skeletal material. Additionally, the poor preservation of skeletal remains in part of the sample may have contributed to the non-detection of pathological changes. The observed pathological changes were, by their nature, the result of nutritional deficiencies, and consequences of infectious diseases. Traumatic changes on the skeleton were considered, observed and analysed separately, as they are not a direct consequence of the child's overall health, but rather largely the result of accident or human intervention or intention.

Analysis of the total number of skeletal pathological changes in boys and girls, excluding trauma, indicates that these changes are equally prevalent in both sexes. Observed differences between males and females, in favor of a higher prevalence of skeletal lesions in female subadults, didn't reach statistical significance.

7. 3. 1. Trauma

Regarding traumas, in the majority of cases they involved sharp-force injuries to the cranial skeleton, observed in 8 individuals (13.1% of the analyzed sample). The most commonly observed type of trauma involved the parietal bones, typically presenting as incisions approximately 1 mm wide, with varying depth and length (Grave Ostojićevo 1, 24, 163, 198). Also semicircular shallow incisions were recorded in the sample (Grave Ostojićevo 157, 183). In individuals interred in grave Ostojićevo 157 and Ostojićevo 198 a circular defect was identified on the right parietal bone near the junction of the lambdoid and sagittal sutures, characterized by bone loss in the central area. The morphology of the lesion is consistent with perimortem cranial trauma, although the exact cause remains uncertain due to the incomplete preservation of the affected region. Similar traumas in previous research were referred to as symbolic trepanations (Bereczki and Marcsik 2005; Stefanović 2012). Regarding postcranial trauma, two cases were identified on the femora. Both exhibit a pattern consistent with the most common type of sharp force incision observed on the cranial bones, narrow, linear cuts of approximately uniform 1 mm width, though varying in depth and length (Graves Ostojićevo 22, 195).

The recurrent pattern of three morphologically consistent types of sharp force trauma observed on the cranial bones (parietal bones), most not penetrating the endocranial cavity, suggests the use of a uniform instrument type, while no excessive force was applied during the use of this instrument. The repetitive and localized nature of these lesions may indicate deliberate actions, potentially associated with a form of therapeutic or medical intervention targeting the cranial soft tissues. In two individuals with sharp-force trauma on the cranial surface, endocranially there was also evidence of *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* or other non-specific meningeal reactions (Graves Ostojićevo 1, 163), while in the individual buried in grave 163, alongside the endocranial changes, there is also evidence of porotic hyperostosis across the entire surface of the parietal bones and lytic lesions on the frontal bone, supporting the hypothesis that these injuries were attempts of a medical treatment.

All recorded traumas were observed in individuals up to 7.5 years of age, while injuries affected both sexes without statistically significant differences. The question remains open as to why the youngest individuals among the entire subadult specimen in the Ostojićevo necropolis were the subject of these procedures.

7.3.2. Disease

To reconstruct the presence of certain nutritional deficiencies and metabolic disorders in the child population from the Ostojićevo necropolis, nonspecific markers of nutritional stress (*Cribra orbitalia* and porotic hyperostosis) as well as skeletal indicators potentially reflecting deficiencies in vitamin C (scurvy) and vitamin D (rickets) were analyzed. This analysis revealed significant dietary deficiencies among the children, with their prevalence in the subadult sample reflecting deficiencies in their nutrition and potentially also the shortcomings in occupational strategies of this population.

The analysis of *Cribra orbitalia* (CO) revealed no statistically significant differences in prevalence of CO in the Ostojićevo sample between sexes and different age groups. However, what stands out in this sample is the exceptionally high prevalence of these porotic lesions in the entire subadult cohort, reaching 72.1%, indicating widespread chronic stress and potential nutritional deficiencies among children in this population. Prevalence levels exceeding 70 % are rarely documented in archaeological records, and typically are restricted to population under severe nutritional deficiencies and stress. Among adults at the Ostojićevo necropolis the prevalence of 45.3% was recorded (Pompeani 2020). The difference between adults and children could be due to the generally greater fragility of children and their susceptibility to nutritional stress and infections, or alternatively as a result of the remodeling of lesions during growth (Stuart-Macadam 1989; Driscoll 2001). Such rates, as observed in the Ostojićevo subadult sample are recorded in a few cases, including the Bronze Age Yanghai population in Xinjiang where 75% of individuals under 16 years of age exhibited CO (Zhang, Quanchao, et al. 2006), and in some medieval assemblages from the Iberian Peninsula, where prevalence rates reached up to 78% (Mangas-Carrasco and López-Costas 2021). The high prevalence observed in these samples has been explained by a monotonous diet, one based almost exclusively on meat at the Bronze Age site of Yanghai in China, and on marine dietary sources on the Iberian Peninsula during the medieval period. An alternative etiology proposed for these lesions is parasitic infestation, which could also lead to nutritional deficiencies due to the activity of parasitic organisms. In all age categories from the Ostojićevo sample a broadly consistent distribution of *Cribra orbitalia* was observed, indicating a constant nutritional and metabolic stress during the course of childhood.

Porotic hyperostosis observed on the parietal bones was also frequent in the child population during the Middle Bronze Age. The prevalence of porotic hyperostosis in the Ostojićevo sample (54.0%) was very high. The frequency of the porotic hyperostosis in other archaeological samples is similar to that observed at Ostojićevo. Prevalence among subadults in the Bronze Age Yanghai population in China reached approximately 60% (Zhang, Quanchao, et al. 2006), while medieval populations from the Iberian Peninsula showed prevalence rates around 42% (Mangas-Carrasco and López-Costas 2021). These values were interpreted as chronic physiological stress, nutritional deficiencies or parasitic infections that could affect subadult health.

The relatively balanced distribution of porotic hyperostosis between boys and girls at Ostojićevo, with no statistically significant differences observed, suggests that both sexes were exposed to comparable physiological stressors within the population.

The age range of individuals exhibiting porotic hyperostosis extended from 38 gestational weeks to 17.5 years. This pattern indicates that the condition affected individuals from the perinatal through late juvenile period, suggesting prolonged exposure to physiological stressors throughout early life. The prevalence of porotic hyperostosis among observable subadult individuals was 54.0% (27/50). When analyzed by age, lesions were most frequent in infants under 1 year (60.9%) and in children aged 1–10 years (58.8%), while prevalence decreased in older subadults aged 15–20 years (42.9%) and was absent in individuals over 20 years. The statistical analysis indicates that, although younger subadults (less than 1 year and 1–10 years old) show numerically higher prevalence of porotic hyperostosis compared

to older subadults (older than 10 years), these differences are not statistically significant, suggesting that the condition affected individuals relatively evenly across these age categories.

Both nonspecific stress markers thus appear almost equally frequently in both sexes and across all age categories, ruling out the possibility that any one of these biological groups had more favorable conditions or better access to resources. Based on the prevalence of these conditions, it can also be concluded that the conditions were extremely unfavorable for all biological categories.

Skeletal markers that indicated deficiencies of vitamins C and D showed also high frequencies within the subadult population.

Analysis of the subadult sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis revealed a high proportion of individuals exhibiting skeletal indicators of scurvy (55.3%). No statistically significant differences were observed between sexes in the distribution of these indicators, while significant differences were recorded among age groups. The highest prevalence was observed in individuals younger than one year (68.4%), followed by a gradual decrease in the 1–10-year age group (50%), and a further decline in the 15–20-year category.

Today, scurvy is considered a very rare disease in the pediatric population and seldom occurs before the third month of life. However, exceptional neonatal cases have been described in clinical practice (Chowdhury et al., 2022). The causes of neonatal scurvy can include extremely poor or inadequate maternal nutrition, as described in clinical practice in cases where the mother has been on a prolonged monotonous diet lacking sufficient vitamin C (Jackson and Park 1935). Regarding the child population from Ostojićevo, it appears, particularly given the large number of children under one year potentially affected by scurvy, that maternal nutrition during gestation was likely inadequate. The clinical picture observed in children with scurvy includes stunted growth and delayed psychomotor development, as well as skeletal deformities, along with pronounced external symptoms such as fever, joint pain and swelling, and gingival bleeding (Chalouhi 2020). Thus, this nutritional deficiency in children, as well as in the broader population, could have been a significant factor negatively affecting overall quality of life.

Since scurvy in children affects growth and development, an important question arises as to whether individuals exhibiting skeletal manifestations of scurvy also show evidence of growth retardation and whether differences exist in long bone growth. Within the analysed sample of 29 individuals for whom the stature and scurvy status were recorded no statistically significant association was found between scurvy and growth stunting. This result might also among other factors be influenced by relatively small sample size.

Indicators of rickets in the subadult Ostojićevo sample were found in 7 individuals (13.73% of the analysed sample). No statistically significant association was found between the age, biological sex and rickets skeletal manifestations, and all biological categories were equally represented in the sample.

The period of a child's development during which a vitamin D nutritional deficiency occurs can also be inferred from whether long bone deformities appear exclusively in the upper limbs or are present in all long bones. The deformities of the long bones are the consequence of the pressure of carrying a weight of the body itself. During the child's crawling phase (from 6-12 months of age) the deformities of upper limbs can occur (grave Ostojićevo 157). In cases where the deformity develops and active rickets is present during the walking phase (after 12 months of age), curvature of the long bones of the lower limbs is expected (grave Ostojićevo 2, 231, 275). In all long bones deformities are expected in cases when the rickets was active in both phases (grave Ostojićevo 77, 183, 219) (Mays et al., 2006; Giuffra 2013; Pitre et al., 2023). In the Ostojićevo subadult sample all examples of rickets associated deformity patterns were observed. This indicates that the children at all stages of motor development were affected by the vitamin D deficiency.

The etiology of this condition in affected individuals at Ostojićevo may be influenced by various factors and it is hard to determine. Among the most significant that can be considered are insufficient

dietary intake of vitamin D, exclusive breastfeeding by mothers who were vitamin D deficient and restricted exposure to sunlight (Pettifor 2004).

Pathological changes in the skeletal remains of children from Ostojićevo, indicative of nutritional deficiencies, are highly prevalent. These may potentially result from shorter or longer periods of famine experienced by the children themselves, as well as by their mothers during pregnancy and lactation. Alternatively, the high frequency of indicators of nutritional deficiency could be attributed to parasitic infestations, and in the case of rickets, limited exposure to sunlight.

Living conditions, population density, cohabitation with domestic animals and contacts with wild ones, sanitary circumstances, occupational habits, as well as environmental conditions, all these factors can influence the spreading of the number of pathogens (Brotwell 1991; Mitchell 2003).

In the sample of children from the Ostojićevo necropolis, infectious diseases and nonspecific skeletal manifestations of infections caused by various pathogens were analyzed: tuberculosis, caused by bacteria *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Mycobacterium bovis* (Brites and Gagneux 2015); vector-borne malaria caused by *Plasmodium* species (Gozalo et al., 2024); mastoiditis, as a consequence of the ear canal infection caused by various viral and bacterial pathogens (Boenninghaus and Lenarz 2005; Flohr and Schultz 2009); as well as *serpens endocrania symmetrica* and nonspecific meningeal reactions, which may result from different infectious processes (Schultz 2001).

The analyzed infections have the potential to reveal the dynamic relationship between the community and its environment, the nature of contact with animals and human beings, and provide some insight into the living conditions of the children. In the time before antibiotics when the majority of the diseases took their natural course the sufferings of the sick were enormous. A part of these difficult times is reflected in the skeletal lesions that developed during the progression of the disease, and by recording them we in a way read these periods of struggle anew in the osteological record.

One of the such infectious diseases that may testify to poor living conditions, as well as to intensive contact with domestic animals or the feeding of infants with animal milk, is tuberculosis (Cosivi et al., 1998). The proportion of individuals exhibiting lytic lesions potentially associated with tuberculosis is relatively high, with 46.15% of analyzed vertebrae showing pathological changes. The notable prevalence of vertebral lesions in the analysed young individuals suggests that the population may have experienced high exposure to tuberculosis even during early childhood.

Serpens endocrania symmetrica (SES) was identified in 5 individuals (8.47%) within the analyzed sample, all aged between birth and 1.5 years. This distinctive endocranial alteration has been associated with several pathological conditions, both infectious and metabolic in nature, including meningitis, tuberculosis and scurvy. Unfortunately, due to poor preservation of the vertebrae in this sample, it was not possible to examine the correlation between SES and vertebral lesions that may indicate tuberculosis. In 4 of 5 individuals with SES skeletal changes consistent with scurvy were also observed, which points to a potential association between these conditions.

When considering the method applied in this research, paleopathological diagnoses for malaria are inherently constrained by the lack of information about individual symptoms, making it difficult to assign specific diseases (Smith-Guzman 2015). In the Ostojićevo subadult sample, skeletal manifestations were used as substitutes for clinical symptoms and laboratory tests that would allow a definitive diagnosis of malaria. This also represents a limitation for establishing a definitive diagnosis in individual cases and determining the prevalence of malaria within the entire analyzed sample.

Nevertheless, the high prevalence of individuals exhibiting skeletal pathological changes consistent with malaria at the Ostojićevo necropolis (70.00 %) supports the rationale for further research and additional analyses in the future. For definitive confirmation of potential malaria presence in the sample, future analyses of ancient DNA would be essential. Ancient DNA analysis has proven to be a reliable method for identifying malaria infections in archaeological remains (Michel et al., 2024).

Regarding the distribution of potential skeletal indicators of malaria in the sample, statistical analysis showed an approximately equal distribution between both sexes. The highest prevalence, with respect to age categories, was recorded in children under one year of age. This observation raises several questions concerning the exposure of different age groups to disease-carrying vectors.

Malaria infestation is an important topic for future research because, in addition to ecological factors such as proximity to vector habitats (mosquitoes), including wetlands that inevitably expose populations to vector-borne transmission, malaria prevalence can also provide valuable insights into the occupational activities and lifestyles of specific groups. In contemporary populations, higher malaria prevalence is strongly influenced by mobility and outdoor activities during peak mosquito activity periods. A study in Taraba State, Nigeria, found the highest malaria prevalence among traders who spent most of their time moving and outdoors, compared to populations that spent more time indoors (Toure et al., 2025). Similarly, the analysis of skeletal manifestations in the Ostojićevo population and future ancient DNA analysis, could help reconstruct the occupational activities and lifestyle habits of different age groups during the warmer season. Determining whether the youngest individuals spent most of their time outside their homes could reveal that, unfortunately, they were exposed to vectors, which in turn subjected them to pathogens and adversely affected their health.

When considering mastoiditis, ages of affected individuals range widely, from 10.5 months to 25 years, indicating that mastoid process lesions occurred across a broad spectrum of subadult development. Both young children (under 1 year) and young adults (over 20 years) are represented, suggesting that susceptibility to mastoid infections or chronic changes was not restricted to a specific age group in this population.

Regarding biological sex, four individuals are female (57.1% of the affected sample) and three are male (42.9%), showing a slightly higher representation of females among affected individuals. This may reflect random variation in this relatively small sample of 36 observed individuals with preserved temporal bones.

In the Ostojićevo subadult sample, 19.04% of individuals exhibited lesions on the mastoid process indicative of mastoiditis. This prevalence is substantially higher than that observed in modern populations, where only 0.002% of children with acute otitis media progress to mastoiditis following the introduction of antibiotics. In the pre-antibiotic era 20 % of cases were complicated by acute mastoiditis, often leading to severe intracranial sequelae (NIH 2023), similar to that observed in the Ostojićevo subadult sample. In the sample of ancient American Pueblo Indians, before European contacts Ochi et al., (2018) reports that 25 % of skulls examined show arrested mastoid pneumatization, which is interpreted as past mastoiditis involvement. Comparing this context with a sample from Ostojićevo (19.04 %) the prevalence of mastoiditis at the Middle Bronze Age necropolis children falls within the range of elevated middle-ear disease seen in ancient populations. It can be concluded that mastoiditis, along with the associated pain and health complications, posed a serious threat to the health and well-being, if not the very lives, of many children from the population buried at Ostojićevo.

With regard to dental pathologies, an exceptionally low prevalence of both caries and enamel hypoplasia was observed. In the Ostojićevo sample, a very low incidence of caries lesions was recorded, which can be attributed to several factors. First, there is generally a lower prevalence of caries in children compared to adults. In infants, this is especially true because breastfeeding provides a highly hygienic form of nutrition, resulting in fewer caries lesions, whereas the risk of caries increases with the introduction of solid foods (Lönnnerdal 2000; Stránská et al., 2015). In addition to other mechanisms through which weaning induces physiological stress, this represents another pathway by which early childhood stress can manifest.

In addition, other factors may contribute to the low prevalence of caries, such as a high level of dental hygiene and, on the other hand, the consumption of foods whose residues would not promote carbohydrate fermentation in the oral cavity (cariogenic food) (Sanz and Chambrone 2022).

The presence of enamel hypoplasia, which occurs in early childhood (up to ten years of age), although not statistically significant due to the small sample, shows a trend in which individuals with enamel hypoplasia appear to die earlier and do not reach the juvenile period, based on the sample from the Ostojićevo necropolis. Among adult individuals, a decreasing trend in the prevalence of linear enamel hypoplasia was observed in age categories above 20 years, ranging from 23.3% in individuals aged 20–30 years to 12.5% in those over 40 years, indicating a noticeable trend of reduced enamel hypoplasia frequency (Pompeani 2020). In the subadult Ostojićevo sample, enamel hypoplasia might be the indicator of extreme nutritional and general physiological stress. Enamel hypoplasia is observed in both sexes with no significant association between biological sex and enamel defect.

7.3.3. Growth and development

One of the most important indicators of good general health in children is their growth and development, as well as reaching developmental milestones at the appropriate time (World Health Organisation 2006). The growth and development of children from the Ostojićevo necropolis were analyzed by approximating their height and weight and comparing these measures with the ranges predicted by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2006). Skeletal growth and development were also compared with individual dental age, which is expected to correspond most closely to chronological age (Saunders et al., 1993; Cardoso 2007).

The majority of individuals in the analyzed sample (71.9%) exhibited slower long bone growth compared to their estimated dental age. Slower growth showed no association with the biological sex of the subadult individuals, while accelerated growth relative to dental age was observed exclusively in male individuals; however, this pattern is based on a very small sample of only three individuals, which is insufficient for drawing deeper conclusions about this trend in the Ostojićevo subadults.

Statistical analysis indicated that the likelihood of experiencing slower growth relative to the expected tempo based on dental age does not differ between different age categories. This indicates that children in all age groups exhibit growth delays relative to the expected ranges.

The majority of subadult individuals in the Ostojićevo necropolis sample exhibited delayed growth, which appears to be largely attributable to malnutrition in children and probably maternal malnourishing. This conclusion is supported by the presence of skeletal indicators such as *Cribra orbitalia* (72.1%) and porotic hyperostosis (54%), as well as cumulative changes potentially indicative of rickets (13.73%) and scurvy (55.3%), with some signs even observed in neonates. Future research should therefore focus on gaining deeper insights into the diet of this population, particularly the nutrition of mothers and children.

When considering the body height and weight of the children from the Ostojićevo necropolis, a large proportion of individuals exhibit values below those expected for normal physiological growth in modern populations. A high prevalence of undernutrition (54.5%) and below-expected stature (60%) was observed. These findings are consistent with other bioarchaeological indicators, particularly the presence of pathological lesions suggesting various metabolic imbalances, nutritional deficiencies, and diseases associated with pathogenic influences. No statistically significant differences were found between males and females in the prevalence of undernutrition or reduced stature, indicating that occupational stress and access to resources were likely similar for all children in the Ostojićevo population. Regarding stature, the 1–5-year-old age category shows the highest proportion of

individuals with shorter-than-expected growth, a result that is statistically significant. This pattern likely reflects the cumulative effects of stress factors experienced during the first year of life, which continued to influence growth and development in subsequent years. Clearly, this also reflects the fragility of the youngest age groups and their greater susceptibility to all external stressors, which certainly contributed to their higher representation in the overall sample.

Social and economic circumstances in the Bronze Age affected the overall health of the population, as supported by paleopathological evidence. High prevalence of nutritional deficiencies, infectious disease indicators, and growth impairments among children indicates that living conditions, diet, and exposure to pathogens significantly influenced their wellbeing. These findings suggest that broader social and ecological factors shaped health outcomes in this population.

The hypothesis proposing that children's health correlates with biological sex and age is only partially confirmed. In terms of health, no significant differences were observed between boys and girls, suggesting that access to resources, exposure to pathogens, and health risks were similar regardless of biological sex.

In contrast, age played a clear role, with younger children showing higher susceptibility to nutritional deficiencies, infectious diseases, trauma, and growth delays, confirming the age-related aspect of the hypothesis. Due to the short lifespan of these individuals, in most cases we cannot discuss the osteological paradox (Wood et al., 1992), in which a higher number of lesions would indicate greater resilience and robustness, because children with pronounced pathological lesions died at a very young age. In the younger age categories, elevated mortality is evident, as reflected in their proportionally higher representation within the Ostojićevo necropolis sample. Beyond social determinants, biological factors likely played a critical role in this increased mortality and in the greater prevalence of pathological lesions observed in the skeletal remains. A key consideration is the heightened vulnerability of this age group due to immunological immaturity. Insufficiently developed immune defenses in children, when exposed to pathogens, could have resulted in elevated mortality during critical stages of early development (Ygberg and Nilsson 2012).

7. 4. Funerary recipients, grave goods and burial orientations

The care once evident in the lives of the youngest is now reflected in the rites of their burial. Infants and very young children are laid to rest within funerary vessels, accompanied by few grave goods and their orientation follows a sex-specific pattern, similar to that observed among adult individuals. Among the analyzed subadult burials, boys were most frequently oriented north-south (62.5%), whereas girls were predominantly oriented south-north (61.9%). The fact that these orientations were consistently applied to both adults and children implies that this practice was an enduring and meaningful element of the community's funerary tradition.

Funerary vessels, made in a range of forms and sizes, were chosen to fit the stature of the children. The observed variability in the dimensions of preserved funerary vessels suggests potential selection criteria associated with vessel choice for the burial ritual of children. This raises a research question regarding whether these vessels were purposefully chosen for burial of individual children, according to specific metric parameters, such as stature, or they were crafted specifically for the purpose of an individual child's burial. Comparative statistical analysis between the vessel volume and the stature of the children indicates statistically significant and clearly observable trend: taller children tend to be interred in vessels with larger capacities and height. This result may suggest an association between the child's physical stature and the size of the funerary vessel. The key question is whether the cessation of

burials in funerary vessels was a consequence of the practical impossibility of placing children in the containers, due to the lack of sufficiently large vessels, or a result of a change in the social status of these children. The tallest child aged 8.5 years buried in a container measured approximately 105 cm (Grave Ostojićevo 18). Older children were interred exclusively outside containers, yet there are instances where children of even greater estimated stature were laid to rest outside vessels, despite being younger than the child in Grave Ostojićevo 18 (Grave Ostojićevo 4 – aged 5.5 years, stature 116 cm; Grave Ostojićevo 160 – aged 7.5 years, stature 107 cm; Grave Ostojićevo 165 – aged 7.5 years, stature 137 cm). From this, we may infer that the shift in burial practice at this age was guided by practical considerations, though this does not preclude subtle changes in social status that remain invisible and cannot be discerned from the material remnants of this population. These changes perhaps are determined by an age threshold, or by some new social role or rite of passage.

In seeking to determine whether any element of burial practice besides the orientation of the deceased was sex-specific, attention was also given to types of funerary vessels. Questions considered include whether certain vessel forms were reserved for boys or girls, and ultimately, whether both boys and girls were buried in funerary vessels. Based on the analyzed vessel types and the sex of the individuals buried in vessels it can be concluded that both boys and girls were interred in such ceramic containers, with boys representing 56.5% and girls 43.5% of the sample. It can be concluded based on obtained data that vessel burial among the youngest individuals was not reserved for only one sex, but that both were almost equally represented in the analyzed sample. There is also no statistically significant association between the sex of the children and the vessel type, meaning that there was no vessel form that was typical for boys or for girls, even though differences in the shape, decoration, and manufacturing techniques of the vessels were observed. One possible reason for this diversity is chronological in nature. Over the course of time (1650–1550 BCE) at the Ostojićevo necropolis, which was in use for an entire century, preferences in vessel selection, as well as styles of decoration and methods of ceramic production and firing, may have changed. Beyond chronologically conditioned differences, the material culture of the Ostojićevo necropolis reflects the influences of diverse neighboring cultures and intercultural contacts, which may have shaped the selection of burial vessels. Milašinović et al. (2024) observe that the pithos-type vessel analyzed in this study, classified as type C without handles, exhibits clear analogies with vessels attributed to the Kosider group (Kovács 1984). Comparable parallels are also documented in an urn from grave 79 at the Hügelgräber culture necropolis of Tápé, near Szeged, which contained the remains of a child (Trogmayer 1975), corresponding to grave Ostojićevo 47.

Regarding the age of individuals buried in funerary containers, a statistically significant association was observed between individual age and burial in or outside a container, with the youngest individuals being in majority of cases buried in vessels. The oldest child buried in a vessel was 8.5 years old (Grave Ostojićevo 18). The consistency and high frequency of this burial practice for the youngest children indicate its importance, as well as the distinctive status of younger children compared to older ones.

The number of grave goods among children is very low, and it may be stated that the individual graves were generally poorly furnished. With regard to differences in the frequency of grave goods among subadults at the Ostojićevo cemetery, no statistically significant distinction was observed between girls and boys. Certain differences, although not statistically significant, perhaps due to the small sample size, appear between age categories. Grave goods are least frequently recorded among the youngest individuals (under the one year of age), while the burial assemblages of older children tend to be more elaborate, with a greater number of items.

However, it should be noted that the majority of individuals were buried without grave goods (66.2%), which greatly limits the ability to draw firm conclusions regarding whether social status changed with age and the acquisition of new roles within the community, changes that might be symbolically reflected in the number and diversity of grave goods. Most individuals were excluded from the analysis due to the absence of grave goods, which further complicates interpretation.

Analysis of the association between the number of grave goods and the frequency of pathological changes showed a weak, non-significant correlation, suggesting no evident link between burial richness and the health status of children. Any potential link between social rank and health, assuming that burials with more grave goods reflect higher social status, was not observable in the analyzed sample. Instead, the number of grave goods was found to be associated exclusively with the age of the children. For future research, it will be necessary to undertake a comparative analysis of grave goods between subadult and adult individuals.

Another challenge relates to how funerary vessels of children should be treated analytically. The question remains as to the actual significance of this funerary assemblage and the extent of effort and resources invested in its selection and production. Younger children (up to 8.5 years) may lack grave goods, but, unlike older individuals, they were interred in relatively large funerary containers. This indicates that the community invested considerable effort and resources in the burial ritual of its youngest members, even without adding other types of grave items during the burial.

One of the hypotheses considered in this research, proposing that funerary practices correlate with sex of children, is partially confirmed. Burial orientation shows clear sex-based patterns: boys were predominantly oriented north-south, whereas girls were most often oriented south-north, reflecting the same patterns observed among adults at the Ostojićevo necropolis. In contrast, no significant sex-based differences were observed in the number of grave goods or in the choice of funerary vessels. Age-related differences in funerary norms are evident, as younger children were mainly buried in funerary vessels, while older children, from around six years of age, were predominantly buried outside of vessels.

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In conclusion, the bioarchaeological analysis of children from the Ostojićevo necropolis revealed a population affected by notable health challenges. The results indicated that children experienced considerable physiological stress, reflected in high infant and early childhood mortality and a notable prevalence of skeletal markers associated with malnutrition, metabolic disorders, and infectious disease. Evidence of growth delays and nonspecific stress markers points to a challenging living environment, in which the youngest members of the community were particularly vulnerable. A large number of skeletal indicators potentially reflecting the presence of infectious diseases were observed in the Ostojićevo subadult skeletal series. Future investigations of the Ostojićevo necropolis should prioritize ancient DNA analysis to detect and confirm the presence of *Plasmodium* species, the causative agents of malaria, and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*, responsible for tuberculosis infection. Although the observed skeletal changes may serve as indicators of these infections, they do not constitute definitive evidence of pathogen presence.

Funerary rituals demonstrated that the children were integrated into the collective symbolic system and ritual norms, which is manifested through a gender-based burial orientation consistent with that recorded in the adult population. The consistent use of funerary vessels, especially for the youngest individuals, highlights a culturally significant practice that likely reflects beliefs surrounding infancy and the transition into the social sphere. Although no strong indications of social differentiation were found in grave goods or burial treatment on the basis of sex or health status, patterns in funerary recipient selection and age at transition out of vessel burials suggest that age, and potentially body

shape and size, structured mortuary behavior. All children, including those who may have been stillborn, were laid to rest within the Ostojićevo necropolis in the same funerary context as older children and adults. This reveals that from the very beginning of life, children were integrated into the community's established mortuary customs. No differences were observed between boys and girls in any measured aspect, indicating that, although binary gender distinctions were evident from an early age in the funerary ritual, there is no evidence that boys and girls were treated differently in ways that could have affected their health.

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Figure 1. Map of Serbia showing the location of Ostojićevo site.

Figure 2. Map showing the spatial distribution of graves in the Middle Bronze Age horizon at the Ostojićevo necropolis. The map was produced in *Adobe Illustrator* based on a map of the Ostojićevo site in documentation from the National Museum of Kikinda.

Figure 3. Retroalveolar radiograph of the mandible with dentition. Grave Ostojićevo 285 (Photo: Bojan Petrović and Marija Marin).

Figure 4. Orthopantomogram of the mandible with dentition. Grave Ostojićevo 275 (Photo: Bojan Petrović and Marija Marin).

Figure 5 a. Burial Vessel - Grave 173 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 5 b. Burial Vessel - Grave 20 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 5 c. Burial Vessel - Grave 26 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 6. Burial Vessel - Grave 70 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 7. Burial Vessel - Grave 16 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 8. Burial vessel from the grave Ostojićevo 195 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 9. Grave 37 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 10. Grave 75 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 11. Burial Vessel - Grave 10 (Photo: Parditka, Gyoergyi-National Museum Kikinda).

Figure 12. Neonatal line visible under transmitted light microscopy at 50x magnification, observed on tooth 63. Grave 218.

Figure 13 a. Neonatal line not visible under light microscopy at 50x magnification, observed on tooth 61, Grave 48.

Figure 13 b. Ostojićevo-Grave 48. Photo: National Museum Kikinda.

Figure 14. Grave Ostojićevo 173. Frontal and parietal bone blunt force trauma: depression and oblique fracture lines.

Figure 15. Number of individuals with Cribra orbitalia in different Age categories.

Figure 16. Porotic hyperostosis age distribution in the Ostojićevo necropolis sample.

Figure 17. Age distribution of individuals with long bone deformities.

Figure 18. Age distribution of individuals with vertebral lesions.

Figure 19. Skeletal manifestations of malaria age distribution in the Ostojićevo necropolis sample.

Figure 20. *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (SES) observed on both the left and right parietal bones of a 1.5-year-old boy (Grave Ostojićevo 163).

Figure 21. Lesions on the Mastoid Process of the Right Temporal Bone, Child Aged 5.5–6 Years (Grave Ostojićevo 276).

Figure 22. Boxplot displaying distribution of skeletal pathologies in female (N=25) and male (N=24) subadult individuals at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Figure 23. A histogram that illustrates the capacity of funerary containers at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Figure 24. A histogram that illustrates the height of the funerary vessels at the Ostojićevo necropolis.

Figure 25. Boxplot displaying correlation between vessel volume and stature of children.

Figure 26. Boxplot displaying correlation between vessel height and stature of children.

Figure 27. Boxplot representing a range of individuals buried inside and outside of funerary recipients.
Figure 28. Boxplot representing a pathologies distribution by number of grave goods in subadults from the Ostojićevo.

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APPENDIX 1.

Table 1. Age, biological sex and total number of pathological changes in the analysed sample.

Site	Grave number	Age (Mean; Years)	Sex (Peptide based)	Total number of pathological changes recorded
Ostojicevo	1	0.56	Female	5
Ostojicevo	2	0.62	Female	6
Ostojicevo	4	5.5	N/A	2
Ostojicevo	5	0.88	Female	2
Ostojicevo	10	0.125	N/A	1
Ostojicevo	12	0 (34-36 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	13	0.88	Female	1
Ostojicevo	14	8.5	Female	4
Ostojicevo	15	0 (34 gestational week)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	16	0 (36 gestational weeks)	N/A	1
Ostojicevo	17A	15	Male	0
Ostojicevo	18	8,5	Female	3
Ostojicevo	19	0.375	Female	4
Ostojicevo	20	0 (34 gestational weeks)	Male	0
Ostojicevo	24	0 (38-40 gestational weeks)	N/A	6
Ostojicevo	26	0 (30 gestational weeks)	N/A	0

Ostojicevo	32	0 (38 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	37	0.625	Male	2
Ostojicevo	38	17	Male	1
Ostojicevo	39	0.82	Male	0
Ostojicevo	48	0.125	Male	2
Ostojicevo	70	0 (36-38 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	73	0.625	Male	1
Ostojicevo	76	0.08	N/A	1
Ostojicevo	77	4.5	Male	10
Ostojicevo	84	0 (34 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	89	1.25	Male	9
Ostojicevo	91	0	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	96	0.88	Male	4
Ostojicevo	102	16.5	Female	4
Ostojicevo	104	25	Female	7
Ostojicevo	108A	15.5	Male	4
Ostojicevo	111	8.5	Female	3
Ostojicevo	112	4.5	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	124	0 (38 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	130	6.5	Female	5
Ostojicevo	133	0.0625	Female	2

Ostojicevo	133A	0 (34-38 gestational weeks)	N/A	1
Ostojicevo	134	0.75	N/A	4
Ostojicevo	146	16	Female	1
Ostojicevo	150	0.0625	N/A	4
Ostojicevo	157	7	Male	6
Ostojicevo	160	7.5	Male	0
Ostojicevo	163	1.5	Male	3
Ostojicevo	165	7.5	Male	2
Ostojicevo	170	0 (32-38 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	173	3.75	Female	2
Ostojicevo	176	23.12	Female	2
Ostojicevo	177	0.375	Male	3
Ostojicevo	179	6.5	Male	5
Ostojicevo	183	0.88	Male	7
Ostojicevo	187	0 (32-40 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	195	0.94	Male	6
Ostojicevo	198	0.25	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	205	0.08	Female	6
Ostojicevo	207	4.75	Male	5
Ostojicevo	218	0.88	Female	4
Ostojicevo	219	8.75	Female	7

Ostojicevo	231	16	Female	6
Ostojicevo	237	19.5	Female	0
Ostojicevo	238A	16	Female	1
Ostojicevo	238B	0.5	N/A	1
Ostojicevo	240	0 (30-32 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	242	0.375	Female	1
Ostojicevo	243	0 (32 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	245	24.78	Male	2
Ostojicevo	247	0.5	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	248	1.5	Female	3
Ostojicevo	249	0.75	Male	0
Ostojicevo	261	0 (30-34 gestational weeks)	N/A	0
Ostojicevo	275	16	Male	8
Ostojicevo	276	5.75	Female	3
Ostojicevo	277	2.3	Male	3
Ostojicevo	285	3.5	Female	2

APPENDIX 2.

Codebook of pathological variables in table 1: MST denotes mastoiditis (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); TRM denotes trauma (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); SES denotes *Serpens endocrania symmetrica* (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); CO L denotes presence of *Cribra orbitalia* on the left orbital roof (A score 1 indicates absence, 2–3 indicate the degree of the porosity, and N/A indicates Not Available); CO R denotes presence of *Cribra orbitalia* on the right orbital roof (A score 1 indicates absence, 2–3 indicate the degree of the porosity, and N/A indicates Not Available); CO A denotes *Cribra orbitalia* active/healed (For variable a score 0 indicates absence of CO; 1 indicates healed, 2 indicates active CO, and N/A indicates Not Available); CH denotes *Cribra humera* (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); CF denotes *Cribra femora* (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); SCV denotes scurvy (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); RCT denotes rickets (A score of 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); PS denotes periostitis (A score 1 indicates absence, 2–5 indicate the degree of the porosity, and N/A indicates Not Available); PH denotes porotic hyperostosis (A score 1 indicates absence, 2–3 indicate the degree of the porosity, and 0 indicates Not Available); TBC denotes tuberculosis (A score 1 indicates absence, 2 indicate presence, and 0 indicates Not Available), MLR denotes malaria (A score 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates the presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); EH denotes enamel hypoplasia (A score 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates the presence, and N/A indicates Not Available); DC denotes dental caries (A score 0 indicates absence, 1 indicates the presence, and N/A indicates Not Available).

Table 1. Skeletal Pathologies in Subadult Individuals from the Ostojićevo Necropolis.

Gr. No.	Age Y	Sex	MST	TRM	SES	CO L	CO R	CO A	CH	CF	SCV	RCT	PS	PH	TBC	MLR	EH	DC
1	0.56	1	0	1	1	1	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	2	2	0	1	N/A	0
2	0.62	1	0	0	0	2	N/A	2	N/A	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
4	5.5	N/A	0	0	0	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	N/A	N/A

5	0.88	1	0	0	0	2	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	2	0	N/A	0	0
10	0.125	N/A	N/A	0	0	3	3	2	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
12	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	1	1	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
13	0.88	1	N/A	0	0	N/A	3	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	0	0
14	8.5	1	0	0	N/A	3	3	2	N/A	0	0	0	3	1	2	1	0	0
15	0	N/A	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A									
16	0	N/A	0	N/A	1	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A						
17A	15	2	N/A	0	0	0	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A						
18	8,5	1	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	0
19	0.375	1	0	0	0	N/A	2	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	2	1	0	1	0	0
20	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	0	N/A	0	0
24	0	N/A	N/A	1	1	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	5	2	0	1	N/A	N/A

26	0	N/A	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A									
32	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
37	0.625	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	1	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	0	0
38	17	2	N/A	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
39	0.82	2	N/A	0	0	1	1	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
48	0.125	2	N/A	0	0	2	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	3	0	N/A	0	0
70	0	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A						
73	0.625	2	N/A	0	1	N/A	2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A							
76	0.08	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A							
77	4.5	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	5	2	2	1	1	0
84	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A											
89	1.25	2	0	0	0	3	N/A	2	1	1	1	0	4	1	0	1	1	1

91	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A											
96	0.88	2	0	0	0	3	3	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	4	1	0	1	0	0
102	16.5	1	1	0	0	3	N/A	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
104	25	1	1	0	0	1	2	2	N/A	1	1	0	4	1	0	1	0	0
108A	15.5	2	1	0	0	N/A	3	2	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	N/A	0	0
111	8.5	1	0	0	0	N/A	2	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	3	0	N/A	0	0
112	4.5	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A						
124	0	N/A	0	0	0	N/A	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A							
130	6.5	1	0	0	0	N/A	2	2	0	0	1	0	3	1	0	1	1	0
133	0.062	1	N/A	0	0	1	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	2	3	0	N/A	0	0
133A	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	0	2	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
134	0.75	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	3	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A

146	16	1	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	N/A	0	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	
150	0.062	N/A	N/A	0	0	2	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	4	3	0	1	N/A	N/A	
157	7	2	0	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	1	1	N/A	1	1	1	1	0	
160	7.5	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	
163	1.5	2	0	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	3	0	0	0	0	
165	7.5	2	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	0	3	0	0	N/A	1	0	
170	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A												
173	3.75	1	0	1	0	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	2	0	N/A	1	0	
176	23.12	1	0	0	0	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	
177	0.375	2	0	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	4	3	0	N/A	0	0	
179	6.5	2	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	4	2	0	N/A	1	0	
183	0.88	2	0	1	0	2	1	2	N/A	1	1	1	5	3	0	1	0	0	

187	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A											
195	0.94	2	N/A	1	1	1	2	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	5	1	0	1	0	0
198	0.25	N/A	N/A	1	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A								
205	0.08	1	0	0	0	3	3	2	0	0	1	0	2	2	2	1	0	0
207	4.75	2	0	0	0	3	3	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	2	3	0	1	0	0
218	0.88	1	1	0	0	2	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	2	0	N/A	0	0
219	8.75	1	0	0	0	3	N/A	2	0	1	1	1	4	3	0	1	0	0
231	16	1	0	0	0	N/A	3	2	0	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	0	0
237	19.5	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
238A	16	1	0	0	0	N/A	2	0	N/A	0	0							
238B	0.5	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	3	0	N/A	N/A	N/A							
240	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A							

242	0.375	1	N/A	0	0	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	0	N/A	0	0
243	0	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A											
245	24.78	2	1	0	0	N/A	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0
247	0.5	N/A	1	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A										
248	1.5	1	N/A	0	0	N/A	2	2	N/A	N/A	0	0	2	2	0	N/A	0	0
249	0.75	2	N/A	0	0	N/A	N/A	0										
261	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	1	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
275	16	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	N/A	0
276	5.75	1	1	0	0	N/A	1	0	N/A	N/A	0	0	2	3	0	N/A	N/A	0
277	2.3	2	0	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	0	3	1	0	0	0	0
285	3.5	1	N/A	0	0	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	3	0	N/A	0	0

APPENDIX 3.

Codebook of metric variables in table 1. All measurements are expressed in millimeters (mm). The symbol “-” denotes bones that were not preserved or not present. HL L denotes left humerus maximal length; HR L denotes right humerus maximal length; UL L denotes left ulna maximal length; UR L denotes right ulna maximal length; RL L denotes left radius maximal length; RR L: denotes right radius maximal length; FL L denotes left femur maximal length; FR L denotes right femur maximal length; TL L denotes left tibia maximal length; TR L denotes right tibia maximal length; FIL L denotes left fibula maximal length; FIR L denotes right fibula maximal length; H AP denotes anteroposterior diameter of humerus; T AP denotes anteroposterior diameter of tibia; F AP denotes anteroposterior diameter of femur.

Table 1. Postcranial Skeletal Metrics of Subadult Individuals.

Gr. No.	HL L (mm)	HR L (mm)	UL L (mm)	UR L (mm)	RL L (mm)	RR L (mm)	FL L (mm)	FR L (mm)	TL L (mm)	TR L (mm)	FIL L (mm)	FIR L (mm)	H AP (Mean; mm)	T AP (Mean; mm)	F AP (Mean; mm)
1	-	-	-	-	-	-	81.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.71
2	85.12	-	64.63	-	62.54	-	109.87	-	-	88	-	82.53	7.45	-	7.63
4	190	187	141	139	152	155	266	268	-	-	-	-	12.98	-	16.02
5	-	-	-	-	-	-	106	105	83	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	61.6	-	-	-	-
12	54.77	55.22	54.65	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	158.1	-	-	141.13	-	128.94	236	-	-	-	-	-	13.26	-	15.89

15	-	-	-	-	-	-	59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17A	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	326	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.72
18	165	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.74	-	-
19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	58.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	-	-	-	-	56.65	-	-	67.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
38	305	-	-	-	235	231	-	438	-	-	-	365	-	-	-
39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

73	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
77	164	163	-	-	117	116	206	207	165	-	158	159	3.74	-	17.05
84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
89	-	107.07	-	-	-	-	132.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.81
91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
96	-	-	-	-	-	-	123	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
102	-	243	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.34	-	-
104	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
108A	-	250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.98	-	-
111	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
112	-	170	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10.26	-	-
124	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
130	-	160	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.56	-	-

133	65	-	-	-	-	-	-	84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
133A	-	53	-	-	-	-	-	51	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
134	-	-	80	-	-	-	116	-	-	-	98	-	-	-	-
146	-	-	-	-	-	-	420	-	-	-	325	-	-	-	22.27
150	-	-	-	-	-	-	90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
157	139	-	-	-	-	-	206	-	-	-	-	-	11.15	-	13.12
160	-	-	-	-	-	-	230	235	-	-	-	-	-	-	13.52
163	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
165	-	230	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.43
170	-	-	45.1	-	45.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
173	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
176	293	301	24.1	24.5	22.3	22.5	-	398	-	-	325	-	20.17	-	22.26
177	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
179	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

183	93.57	-	-	-	-	74.66	119.32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
187	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
195	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	116.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
198	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
205	-	-	-	-	52.83	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
207	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
218	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
219	226	220	180.3	178	160.9	165	355	-	-	-	-	-	18.08	-	16.69
231	270	272	213	214	192	193	-	-	-	-	-	295	18.03	-	-
237	-	-	-	-	-	-	325	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21.17
238A	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
238B	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
240	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
242	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

243	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
245	320	318	-	-	-	-	412	-	-	-	-	-	21.02	-	25.52
247	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
248	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
249	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
261	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
275	271	275	243	245	217	218	383	-	-	-	298	299	19.48	-	24.3
276	-	-	-	-	-	-	250	250.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.74
277	93	-	-	-	-	-	119	118	-	-	-	-	11	-	10
285	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

BIOGRAPHY

Marija Marin is a physical anthropologist at the Laboratory for Bioarchaeology, Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade. She was born on 25 August 1984 in Zemun. She completed her graduate studies in the Department of Archaeology in 2013 and her master's studies in 2015. In the same year, she enrolled in doctoral studies under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Sofija Stefanović and Prof. Dr. Marko Porčić. Since 2024, she has been working at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, as a Research Associate, and as part of the INFANO project team (Principal Investigator: Prof. Dr. Sofija Stefanović), funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia.

Her research focuses on the health status of prehistoric populations, with a particular interest in the Middle Bronze Age in the Pannonian Basin, as well as on paleopathological alterations in human skeletal remains and the methodological approaches for estimating individual age at death.

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Наслов рада _____

Ментор _____

Изјављујем да је штампана верзија мог докторског рада истоветна електронској верзији коју сам предао/ла ради похрањена у **Дигиталном репозиторијуму Универзитета у Београду**.

Дозвољавам да се објаве моји лични подаци везани за добијање академског назива доктора наука, као што су име и презиме, година и место рођења и датум одбране рада.

Ови лични подаци могу се објавити на мрежним страницама дигиталне библиотеке, у електронском каталогу и у публикацијама Универзитета у Београду.

Потпис аутора

У Београду, _____

Изјава о коришћењу

Овлашћујем Универзитетску библиотеку „Светозар Марковић“ да у Дигитални репозиторијум Универзитета у Београду унесе моју докторску дисертацију под насловом:

која је моје ауторско дело.

Дисертацију са свим прилозима предао/ла сам у електронском формату погодном за трајно архивирање.

Моју докторску дисертацију похрањену у Дигиталном репозиторијуму Универзитета у Београду и доступну у отвореном приступу могу да користе сви који поштују одредбе садржане у одабраном типу лиценце Креативне заједнице (Creative Commons) за коју сам се одлучио/ла.

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(Молимо да заокружите само једну од шест понуђених лиценци.
Кратак опис лиценци је саставни део ове изјаве).

Потпис аутора

У Београду, _____

1. **Ауторство.** Дозвољаваате умножавање, дистрибуцију и јавно саопштавање дела, и прераде, ако се наведе име аутора на начин одређен од стране аутора или даваоца лиценце, чак и у комерцијалне сврхе. Ово је најслободнија од свих лиценци.
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5. **Ауторство – без прерада.** Дозвољаваате умножавање, дистрибуцију и јавно саопштавање дела, без промена, преобликовања или употребе дела у свом делу, ако се наведе име аутора на начин одређен од стране аутора или даваоца лиценце. Ова лиценца дозвољава комерцијалну употребу дела.
6. **Ауторство – делити под истим условима.** Дозвољаваате умножавање, дистрибуцију и јавно саопштавање дела, и прераде, ако се наведе име аутора на начин одређен од стране аутора или даваоца лиценце и ако се прерада дистрибуира под истом или сличном лиценцом. Ова лиценца дозвољава комерцијалну употребу дела и прерада. Слична је софтверским лиценцама, односно лиценцама отвореног кода.